

Entanglement Stars: Self-consistent Schwarzschild exterior from entanglement closure on quantum lattice

Jonathan C. McKinney^{1, *}

¹*Department of Physics, University of Maryland, College Park, MD 20742, USA*

Quantum correlations between neighboring sites of a lattice behave like conductances in a resistor network. We show that when a localized energy defect is placed on the lattice, the conductances define a geometry that can be made mutually consistent with the quantum state. In spherical symmetry this self-consistency produces an unscreened $1/r$ far-field gravitational potential whose strength sets the mass. Because the conductances scale as the squared lapse (N^2), the closure equation reduces to Laplace's equation whose solution is exactly the radial co-metric, and the exterior takes the Schwarzschild form including the post-Newtonian expansion. We refer to the resulting object as an *entanglement star*, supported by conductances that play the role of an effective degeneracy pressure. The lapse remains strictly positive because conductances are suppressed before the lapse reaches zero, replacing the classical singularity by a conical interior geometry within the model. Tracking mode-by-mode evaporation in the unitary Gaussian state, the radiation entropy exhibits a Page-like curve. Within the closure framework we derive expressions corresponding to surface gravity, Hawking temperature, and the first law. Self-consistent numerical calculations validate key analytic results for free fermions, an interacting XXZ chain, and a 3D cubic lattice. Replacing the defect with a Tolman-Klein equilibrium gives a self-consistent stellar interior, whose astrophysical limit leads to gravitationally relevant entanglement concentrated at the Schwarzschild radius.

I. INTRODUCTION

Black hole entropy is proportional to horizon area [1–5], which is hard to explain if gravity is just another field theory. The entanglement entropy of a region likewise scales with area [6–9], which suggests that black hole entropy *is* entanglement entropy and that spacetime geometry may be encoded in quantum correlations.

Loosely coined as “it from bit” by John A. Wheeler in 1989, the idea was first formalized by Jacobson [10], who showed that Einstein's field equations of general relativity can be derived from the Clausius relation. The implication is that gravity is neither a fundamental force nor an independent quantum field but emerges from spacetime thermodynamics. Jacobson later showed [11] that Einstein's equation comes from maximal vacuum entanglement in small geodesic balls and a statistical entanglement-equilibrium condition while still assuming a smooth background spacetime. Verlinde [12] gave an entropic derivation of Newtonian gravity, and Padmanabhan [13] derived the gravitational field equations from an entropy maximization principle, showing that gravity emerges as an entropic force from the thermodynamic properties of spacetime. In the anti-de Sitter/conformal field theory (AdS/CFT) correspondence, entanglement entropy of a boundary region equals the area of a bulk minimal surface [14], and perturbing this relation recovers the linearized Einstein equations [15]. Severing entanglement between two boundary regions actually disconnects the corresponding bulk geometry [16, 17], so spatial connectivity is itself an entanglement phenomenon. Tensor networks [18] realize this holographic structure explic-

itly, with the network topology itself serving as the bulk geometry. Cao, Carroll, and Michalakis [19] derive spatial geometry from an abstract Hilbert-space decomposition via mutual information. However, their construction assumes area-law entanglement and recovers a spatial curvature relation from entanglement perturbations, but not a gravitational potential, Newton's constant, or the Schwarzschild geometry (see Sindoni [20] for a broader review of emergent-gravity approaches).

Each of these prior works start from some geometric input (area-law or gravitational bulk), but they also suggest that a simple quantum system on a fixed lattice, without any gravitational or radial-metric input, may obtain a black hole geometry. Here we implement the entanglement-gravity correspondence concretely on a lattice Hamiltonian. The goal is to identify sufficient information-theoretic constraints that lead to gravity and to see what other implications follow. Our approach is an extension of the work by Cao, Carroll, and Michalakis, while avoiding geometric or area-law inputs.

We begin with free fermions hopping on a lattice whose Gaussian thermal state is known in closed form (Section II). Imposing spherical symmetry reduces the lattice to a one-dimensional chain of radial shells (Section III), and mutual information between neighboring shells measures how strongly they are correlated. These correlations define bond conductances that quantify how strongly each pair is coupled. At high temperature these reduce to the mutual information, while at finite temperature the precise measure is the Bogoliubov-Kubo-Mori (BKM) bond-current covariance. These conductances enter a quadratic energy functional on the lattice, the Dirichlet form of the thermal state, and the resulting differential operator defines an emergent co-metric h^{ab} with an undetermined gravitational potential Φ (equivalently a lapse $N = 1 + \Phi/c_*^2$).

* jcm@umd.edu; pseudotensor@gmail.com

At this point we have spatial distances defined by quantum correlations but not yet a spacetime. Causal propagation requires the constraints of canonical gravity [21, 22] to close, which is not guaranteed on a lattice with no built-in diffeomorphisms. We compute the commutator of the lattice modular generators on the cubic lattice (Section IV) and find that the structure function $h^{IJ} = h_0 \bar{N}^2 \delta^{IJ}$ appearing in the causal bracket matches the Dirichlet co-metric, validating the identification. Shell-to-shell correlations therefore determine spatial distances and also how signals propagate, since the bracket fixes the signal speed c_* in the emergent spacetime. Causal and entanglement geometries don't quite coincide, but one can isolate the mismatch as a quantum-information correction T^{QI} to the stress tensor (Section VB).

With a spacetime co-metric now in hand, the remaining question is what determines Φ . Φ is not imposed but instead comes from extremizing a relative-entropy mismatch between a reconstructed state $\sigma[\Phi]$ and a target state, analogous to how Einstein's equation requires the metric and stress-energy to be mutually consistent. We term the resulting stationarity condition the *closure equation* (Section VI). It amounts to a nonlinear Poisson-type equation requiring the geometry and the quantum state generating it be compatible with one another. With a single state the closure suffers from screening because the thermal medium polarizes in response to the gravitational field, reducing the source to a Yukawa-type potential that dies off too quickly for Newtonian gravity. The *two-state closure* (Section IX) avoids this by instead comparing a state with the mass defect to a defect-free background state reconstructed in the same gravitational field. In this way the polarization of the medium drops out and the far field reduces to the bare $1/r$ Newtonian potential at large distances. The lattice parameters in turn fix Newton's constant (Section VIIA). Section X shows that a key requirement for the solution to avoid spurious sources is that both states must be evaluated at the same gravitational redshift. Solving the closure equation in spherical symmetry, the exterior geometry takes the Schwarzschild form at every post-Newtonian order (Sections VIIB 2, X).

Conductances scale as $\kappa \propto \bar{N}^2$, causing the entanglement that sustains the geometry to weaken before the lapse reaches zero (no horizon forms). The conductances generate the gravitational potential, so the potential reaches a finite conical minimum, replacing the classical singularity with a conical floor (Section VIIE). At infinity the observed temperature is the Hawking value, set by the surface gravity of the exterior Schwarzschild geometry (Section VII F).

Spherical symmetry is verified on a 3D lattice (Section XJ) and for an interacting XXZ chain (Section XK).

A fixed mass defect is sufficient to obtain the exterior Schwarzschild geometry, but to study the interior we obtain the matter distribution self-consistently (Section XI). The stellar surface emerges where gravitational binding equals the chemical potential, parametrizing a family of hydrostatic equilibria analogous to Tolman–Oppenheimer–

Volkoff (TOV) stars. For an astrophysical mass, the self-consistent surface can lie arbitrarily close to the would-be Schwarzschild radius while the lapse remains strictly positive. The entanglement star is hidden inside the deep-redshift region, observationally indistinguishable from a classical black hole, yet the interior contains no horizon and no classical singularity.

Because the lapse remains positive, entanglement between the star and its radiation can redistribute continuously as modes are emitted. Early in the evaporation each emitted mode is entangled primarily with the remaining star, but before the Page time the mutual information between successive radiation modes begins to exceed their entanglement with the star, and after the Page time newly emitted modes are primarily entangled with the already-emitted radiation. The resulting entanglement entropy follows a Page-like curve [23] (Section XII), while the lack of a horizon avoids the Almheiri-Marolf-Polchinski-Sully (AMPS) tension [24].

The physical implications of the work, limitations, and future outlook are discussed in Section XIII. Numerical codes and data are available at [25].

II. FREE FERMION MODEL AND GAUSSIAN STATE FORMALISM

Spinless fermions hopping between nearest neighbors on a lattice give a Gaussian model. All entropic and modular quantities then reduce to functions of the single-particle correlation matrix. At any temperature and filling, the formalism is exact. High-temperature and continuum approximations enter only in the self-consistent closure (Sections VI–VII), removed in Sections VIII–X.

A. The microscopic system

Spinless free fermions hop between nearest neighbors on a lattice Λ with Hamiltonian

$$H = -t \sum_{(i,j)} c_i^\dagger c_j + \text{h.c.}, \quad (1)$$

where $t > 0$ is the hopping amplitude. We take the thermal state $\rho = e^{-\beta H}/Z$ at inverse temperature β . Our concrete realization is a spherically symmetric shell chain in three dimensions (Section III). Nothing in the formalism restricts the lattice geometry.

B. Gaussian state formalism

Since H is quadratic, ρ is a *Gaussian* (free, quasi-free) fermion state, and all observables are determined by the single-particle correlation matrix

$$G_{ij} := \text{Tr}(\rho c_j^\dagger c_i) = ((e^{\beta h} + \text{Id})^{-1})_{ij}, \quad (2)$$

where h is the single-particle hopping matrix, $h_{ij} = -t$ for $\langle i, j \rangle$ and 0 otherwise.

For high temperatures, expanding around $\beta = 0$:

$$G = \frac{1}{2}\text{Id} - \frac{\beta}{4}h + O(\beta^3 t^3). \quad (3)$$

The closed form is $G = \frac{1}{2}I - \frac{1}{2}\tanh(\beta h/2)$. At half-filling ($\mu = 0$), only odd powers of βh appear. Nonzero μ would generate even powers as well. The real-space correlator $\delta G_{ij} := G_{ij} - \frac{1}{2}\delta_{ij}$ decays exponentially at rate $\xi_{\text{lat}}^{-1} \sim |\log(\beta t)|$ when $\beta t \ll 1$, giving the *thermal correlation length*

$$\xi_{\text{lat}} \sim \frac{1}{|\log(\beta t/\pi)|}, \quad \xi = \xi_{\text{lat}} \cdot a, \quad (4)$$

where a is the lattice spacing, which serves as the ultraviolet (UV) cutoff of the theory.

Split Λ into disjoint blocks $\{B_x\}_{x \in \Lambda_{\text{block}}}$. The reduced state on each block is Gaussian, with correlation matrix $G_x := (G_{ij})_{i,j \in B_x}$. In the spherical shell models of this paper, the blocks are concentric shells S_n with g_n sites each (Section III A).

The von Neumann entropy of a Gaussian state on region A with correlation matrix G_A is

$$S(A) = -\text{tr}[G_A \log G_A + (\text{Id} - G_A) \log(\text{Id} - G_A)]. \quad (5)$$

MI, relative entropy, and modular Hamiltonians are all computable from single-particle correlation matrices in closed form.

III. SPHERICAL SHELL CHAIN AS A PARAMETER-TO-METRIC MAP

This section defines a diagnostic family of lattice states whose radial hopping profile $t(r)$ reproduces an exact Schwarzschild spatial slice in the continuum limit. The purpose is calibration, validating the MI-to-Dirichlet-form map in a controlled setting where the target geometry is known and measuring the commutator-tail remainder and its ξ^2/ℓ^2 scaling. Sections VI–VII derive the same exterior from uniform hopping and a localized defect via the Euler-Lagrange closure.

A. Shell structure from spherical symmetry

N concentric spherical shells $\{S_n\}_{n=1}^N$ sit at area radii $r_n = r_{\min} + n \delta r$, with shell spacing δr and inner cutoff $r_{\min} > r_s$ outside the Schwarzschild radius $r_s = 2GM/c_*^2$. Each shell S_n has

$$g_n = 4\pi \left(\frac{r_n}{a}\right)^2 \quad (6)$$

sites spaced by a on the 2-sphere of radius r_n , so g_n is the orbital degeneracy of that shell. This count is not a free choice: on a cubic lattice $a\mathbb{Z}^3$ with shells

of thickness $\delta r \sim a$, the number of sites at radius r_n is $|S_n| = 4\pi r_n^2 \delta r/a^3 + O(r_n \delta r/a^2)$, giving $g_n = |S_n| (a/\delta r) = 4\pi (r_n/a)^2 + O(r_n/a)$. The only structural input is the rotationally invariant shell decomposition of an underlying three-dimensional lattice. This fixes the round-sphere measure through $g_n \propto r_n^2$ and identifies r as areal radius. In the refinement system each shell is one block with algebra $\mathcal{A}_n = \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H}_{S_n})$. A higher-dimensional lattice is needed to derive the angular geometry (verified on a 3D cubic lattice in Section XJ below).

To refine, take $a \rightarrow 0$ at fixed areal radius r . The renormalized discrete Dirichlet forms $\hat{\mathcal{E}}_a := \delta r \mathcal{E}_a$ then converge to the continuum form (15) by Mosco (Γ -) convergence in $L^2(\mathbb{R}_+, r^2 dr)$, and so do their minimizers (verified in the paragraph following (15)). The radial shell spacing is set to track the angular UV scale:

$$\delta r = \Theta(a) \quad (\text{in particular one may set } \delta r = a), \quad (7)$$

making one radial step equal to the angular lattice spacing. This makes $\kappa_n = \Theta(r_n^2 t_n^2/a^2)$; the Dirichlet form then has a nontrivial continuum limit (Section III C).

B. Radial hopping model

Place spinless free fermions on the shell lattice with the site-dependent radial hopping Hamiltonian

$$H = - \sum_{n=1}^{N-1} t_n \sum_{\alpha=1}^{g_n} (c_{n,\alpha}^\dagger c_{n+1,\alpha} + \text{h.c.}) - \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{\langle \alpha, \beta \rangle \subset S_n} t_{\text{ang}} (c_{n,\alpha}^\dagger c_{n,\beta} + \text{h.c.}), \quad (8)$$

where $c_{n,\alpha}$ annihilates a fermion at angular site α on shell n , $t_n > 0$ is the radial hopping amplitude between shells n and $n+1$, and t_{ang} is the intra-shell (angular) hopping.

At leading high-temperature order, the inter-shell MI depends only on the radial hopping (angular hopping contributes to $\text{MI}_{n,n+1}$ first at $O(\beta^4 t_{\text{ang}}^2 t_n^2)$, through longer walks). Because the number of nearest-neighbor pairs straddling the $(n, n+1)$ boundary is g_n ,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MI}_{n,n+1} &= g_n \frac{(\beta t_n)^2}{4} (1 + O((\beta t_n)^2)) \\ &= \pi \left(\frac{r_n}{a}\right)^2 (\beta t_n)^2 (1 + O((\beta t_n)^2)). \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The factor $g_n \propto r_n^2$ encodes the angular geometry, so inter-shell MI scales with the sphere area.

Since only inter-shell MI enters the construction, angular modes can be integrated out, giving a 1D tight-binding chain with orbital degeneracy $g_n \propto r_n^2$ and radial hopping t_n . The effective single-particle Hamiltonian is the $N \times N$ tridiagonal matrix

$$\mathfrak{h}_{nm}^{\text{rad}} = -t_n \delta_{m,n+1} - t_{n-1} \delta_{m,n-1}, \quad (10)$$

with g_n -fold degeneracy at each site. The thermal correlation matrix per angular mode is $G^{\text{rad}} = (e^{\beta h^{\text{rad}}} + \text{Id})^{-1}$, reducing all computations to 1D tridiagonal linear algebra. At high temperature,

$$G_{nm}^{\text{rad}} = \frac{1}{2} \delta_{nm} + \frac{\beta}{4} (t_n \delta_{m,n+1} + t_{n-1} \delta_{m,n-1}) + O(\beta^3 t^3), \quad (11)$$

with exponential off-diagonal decay $|G_{nm}^{\text{rad}}| \lesssim (\beta t_{\max})^{|n-m|}$. The coefficient in (9) follows directly. The 2×2 reduced correlation matrix for a single radial channel across the $(n, n+1)$ boundary has eigenvalues $\lambda_{\pm} = \frac{1}{2} \pm \frac{\beta t_n}{4}$. Writing $h(x) = -x \log x - (1-x) \log(1-x)$ for the binary entropy, the per-channel MI is

$$I_{\text{ch}} = 2h\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) - h(\lambda_+) - h(\lambda_-) = \frac{(\beta t_n)^2}{4} + O((\beta t_n)^4), \quad (12)$$

since $h(\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon) = \log 2 - 2\varepsilon^2 + O(\varepsilon^4)$. Multiplying by g_n channels gives (9).

C. MI conductances and weighted Dirichlet form

The edge conductances are set by the inter-shell MI,

$$\kappa_n := \kappa_{n,n+1} \propto \text{MI}_{n,n+1} \propto g_n t_n^2, \quad (13)$$

as dictated by the KMS Dirichlet form of the thermal state (derived in §VIB). Only the ratios κ_n/κ_m enter the closure equation, so the overall normalization is immaterial. Two distinct geometric quantities enter.

- (i) the *angular area* r_n^2 , from the shell degeneracy g_n ;
- (ii) the *radial connectivity* t_n^2 , from hopping amplitude.

The Dirichlet form on the radial chain is

$$\mathcal{E}(\Phi, \Phi) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^{N-1} \kappa_n (\Phi_{n+1} - \Phi_n)^2, \quad (14)$$

with vertex measure $\mu_n \propto g_n \delta r \propto r_n^2 \delta r$. Under the refinement scaling $\delta r = \Theta(a)$, the Riemann-sum matching $\kappa_n (\delta r)^2 \sim \sigma(r_n) r_n^2$ gives $\kappa_n = \Theta(r_n^2 t_n^2 / a^2)$. Only the ratios κ_n/κ_m enter the co-metric identification, so the overall normalization drops out of the Euler-Lagrange equation. Writing $\Phi_{n+1} - \Phi_n = \Phi'(r_n) \delta r + O(\delta r^2)$ and passing to $\sum_n \delta r \rightarrow \int dr$, the Mosco (Γ -convergence) limit [26] gives

$$\mathcal{E}(\Phi, \Phi) \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty \sigma(r) |\Phi'(r)|^2 r^2 dr, \quad (15)$$

with conductivity $\sigma(r) \propto t(r)^2$ (the standard radial reduction of a 3D spherically symmetric Laplacian).

Mosco convergence can be verified directly. Use piecewise-linear interpolation $\Phi_a(r)$ of $\{\Phi_n\}$ between nodes r_n to embed discrete vectors in $L^2(\mathbb{R}_+, r^2 dr)$; $\Phi'_a = (\Phi_{n+1} - \Phi_n)/\delta r$ on each interval. Writing $\hat{\mathcal{E}}_a := \delta r \mathcal{E}_a$ gives $\hat{\mathcal{E}}_a(\Phi_a) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_n \sigma(r_n) |\Phi'_a|^2 r_n^2 \delta r$, a Riemann

sum. *Liminf bound*: weak convergence $\Phi_a \rightharpoonup \Phi$ in $L^2(r^2 dr)$ and lower semicontinuity of the norm give $\liminf \hat{\mathcal{E}}_a(\Phi_a) \geq \mathcal{E}(\Phi)$. *Recovery sequence*: for $\Phi \in H^1(\sigma r^2 dr)$, approximate by smooth $\Phi_\varepsilon \in C^\infty$ with $\mathcal{E}(\Phi_\varepsilon) \rightarrow \mathcal{E}(\Phi)$; for each Φ_ε the nodal interpolant satisfies $\|\Phi'_{a,\varepsilon} - \Phi'_\varepsilon\|_{L^2} \leq C \delta r \|\Phi''_\varepsilon\|_{L^2} \rightarrow 0$, and a diagonal subsequence gives $\hat{\mathcal{E}}_a(\Phi_a) \rightarrow \mathcal{E}(\Phi)$. *Equi-coercivity*: the discrete Poincaré inequality (Dirichlet boundary at r_N) gives uniform H^1 bounds on minimizing sequences. Every cluster point of a minimizing sequence therefore minimizes \mathcal{E} , by compactness [26].

D. Emergent spatial co-metric

Drop the measure factor μ_n from the carré du champ:

$$\Gamma_n(f) := \sum_{m \sim n} \kappa_{nm} (f_m - f_n)^2, \quad (16)$$

so that the intrinsic metric from $\Gamma_n(f) \leq 1$ is independent of the vertex measure. Taking the coordinate probe $f_n = r_n$ with uniform spacing δr :

$$\Gamma_n(r) = (\kappa_{n-1} + \kappa_n) (\delta r)^2 \propto r_n^2 t_n^2 (\delta r)^2. \quad (17)$$

Passing to the continuum, $\Gamma(\Phi)(r) = \sigma(r) (\Phi')^2$ and $h^{rr}(r) = \sigma(r)$. At finite δr one applies the diffusive rescaling $\tilde{\Gamma}_n := (\delta r)^{-2} \Gamma_n$ and divides out the angular multiplicity $\kappa_n \propto g_n$ to get

$$h^{rr}(r) := \lim_{\delta r \rightarrow 0} \frac{\tilde{\Gamma}_n(r)}{2g_n} \propto t(r)^2, \quad (18)$$

where dividing by $g_n \propto r_n^2$ strips out the angular part. In discrete form: $h_n^{rr}/h_0 = \kappa_n/\kappa_n^{\text{flat}}$, with $h_0 \propto t_0^2$ the flat-space value and $\kappa_n^{\text{flat}} := g_n t_0^2$. At high temperature, $\kappa_n/\kappa_n^{\text{flat}} = \tilde{N}_n^2$ analytically; the full exact solver (Section X) agrees to sub-percent level (Figure 2). With $\mu_n \propto r_n^2 \delta r$ the coordinate r is the area radius; the emergent spatial line element reads

$$dl^2 = \frac{C_0}{t(r)^2} dr^2 + r^2 d\Omega^2, \quad (19)$$

where $C_0 > 0$ is a normalization constant. We fix $C_0/t_0^2 = 1$ so that the asymptotic radial null speed equals c_* from the modular-commutator calibration.

E. Hopping profile for Schwarzschild asymptotics

Take the Schwarzschild spatial metric on a time-symmetric ($K_{ij} = 0$) slice in area-radius coordinates,

$$dl_{\text{Schw}}^2 = \frac{dr^2}{1 - r_s/r} + r^2 d\Omega^2, \quad r > r_s. \quad (20)$$

Matching (19) to (20) requires

$$t_n = t_0 \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_s}{r_n}}, \quad (21)$$

t_0 is the asymptotic ($r \rightarrow \infty$) hopping amplitude. The hopping goes to zero at $r_n = r_s$. Shells near the horizon decouple, reflecting the divergence of $g_{rr} = (1 - r_s/r)^{-1}$ and the stretching $ds_{n,n+1} \sim \delta r / \sqrt{1 - r_s/r_n}$ at fixed lattice spacing δr . (Integrated proper distance to r_s is finite; what diverges is the local stretching at fixed δr .)

The MI conductances for the Schwarzschild profile are then

$$\kappa_n \propto r_n^2 t_0^2 \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r_n}\right). \quad (22)$$

F. Verification of Schwarzschild asymptotics

When $r \gg r_s$, perturbative corrections in r_s/r give:

$$t(r) = t_0 \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{2r} + O(r_s/r)^2\right), \quad (23)$$

$$\kappa(r) \propto r^2 t_0^2 \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r} + O(r_s/r)^2\right), \quad (24)$$

$$h^{rr}(r) = h_0 \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right) + O(r_s/r)^2, \quad (25)$$

with $h_0 \propto t_0^2$ the flat-space co-metric. The leading correction $-h_0 r_s/r$ is the Newtonian potential, matching the linearized Schwarzschild geometry.

At finite ξ , the co-metric receives corrections from the off-diagonal MI tail:

$$h_{\text{eff}}^{rr}(r) = h_0 f(r) + O\left(\frac{\xi^2}{r^2}\right), \quad (26)$$

where $f(r) := 1 - r_s/r$, from the gradient expansion of the MI kernel beyond nearest-neighbor order. For $\xi \ll r$ this correction is parametrically small, but as $r \rightarrow r_s$, $f(r) \rightarrow 0$ and the relative importance of the ξ -correction grows.

We now verify that the MI conductances fully determine the Schwarzschild geometry. Under refinement $\delta r = \Theta(a)$, the discrete Dirichlet form (14) with hopping (21) converges to the continuum form (15) with $\sigma(r) \propto t(r)^2 \propto 1 - r_s/r$; the carré du champ identifies the emergent radial co-metric $h^{rr}(r) = h_0(1 - r_s/r)$ via (18), matching the Schwarzschild solution for all $r > r_s$. The measure $\mu_n \propto g_n \delta r \propto r_n^2 \delta r$ identifies r as areal radius, giving angular metric $h_{\Omega\Omega}(r) = r^2$. At large r/r_s , the geometry reduces to flat \mathbb{R}^3 with Newtonian corrections, as shown in (23)–(25).

To quantify corrections near the horizon, note that the off-diagonal correlator decays as $|\delta G_{n,n+m}| \lesssim q(r)^m$ with $q(r) := \beta t(r)/4 < 1$ (consistent with (4)), so the distance- m MI scales as $\text{MI}_{n,n+m} = O(g_n q^{2m})$. The gradient expansion of the resulting nonlocal quadratic form has leading correction controlled by the second moment

$\sum_{m \geq 1} m^2 q^{2m} = q^2(1+q^2)/(1-q^2)^3$, defining the effective length scale $\xi(r) = a/|\log q(r)|$. The gradient expansion then gives $h_{\text{eff}}^{rr}(r) = h^{rr}(r) + O(\xi(r)^2/r^2)$, so corrections to the Schwarzschild metric are explicitly computable from the off-diagonal correlator δG^{rad} .

Thus the MI conductance profile controls the radial co-metric $h^{rr}(r)$, with $g_n \propto r_n^2$ supplying the area measure. In this calibration section the Schwarzschild hopping (21) is prescribed; the radial geometry becomes a genuine output only once the closure equation determines Φ self-consistently (Sections VI–VIII).

IV. HYPERSURFACE-DEFORMATION ALGEBRA ON THE CUBIC LATTICE

The Dirichlet form of Section III defines a spatial co-metric h^{ab} from quantum correlations, but does not by itself determine the dynamics. The commutator of the lapse-smear Hamiltonians independently produces a structure function h^{IJ} ; if this matches the Dirichlet co-metric, then the same object that measures spatial distances also controls signal propagation. We compute all three brackets of the hypersurface-deformation algebra (D - D , D - H , H - H) on the cubic lattice $\Lambda = a\mathbb{Z}^3$ [27, 28] and show that they close with an $O(a^2)$ lattice remainder, with h^{IJ} matching the Dirichlet co-metric. The Hojman–Kuchař–Teitelboim (HKT) uniqueness theorem [29] then identifies the continuum dynamics as general relativity. The radial shell chain is the spherically symmetric specialisation.

a. Lattice derivative and shift. The H - H commutator on the cubic lattice connects second neighbours via two-step paths, producing displacements $\pm 2ae_I$ and $\pm ae_I \pm ae_J$. The natural derivative adapted to this stencil is the ten-point operator

$$\begin{aligned} (\Delta_I f)(x) &:= \frac{1}{12a} \left[f(x+2ae_I) - f(x-2ae_I) \right. \\ &\left. + \sum_{J \neq I} \sum_{\sigma = \pm 1} (f(x+ae_I + \sigma ae_J) - f(x-ae_I + \sigma ae_J)) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

which satisfies $\Delta_I = \partial_I + O(a^2)$. The shift generator is $(D[v]f)(x) := \frac{1}{2} \sum_I (v^I(x) \Delta_I + \Delta_I \circ v^I) f(x)$, symmetrized so that $D[v]$ is anti-Hermitian at leading order.

b. D - D bracket. Since the Δ_I are linear combinations of translation operators they commute exactly. A Leibniz-defect argument (the defect $E_I(u, v) := \Delta_I(uv) - u\Delta_I v - v\Delta_I u$ is $O(a^2)$) gives

$$[D[v], D[w]] = D[v \cdot \nabla w - w \cdot \nabla v] + O(a^2), \quad (28)$$

reproducing the Lie bracket of vector fields.

c. D - H bracket. The KMS modular generator $K[N] = \beta_0 H[N]$ with lapse-smear Hamiltonian $H[N] = \sum_{x,I} \bar{N}_I h_I(x)$, where $h_I(x) := -t_I(c_x^\dagger c_{x+ae_I} + \text{h.c.})$ is the bond Hamiltonian and $\bar{N}_I := \frac{1}{2}(N(x) + N(x+ae_I))$ the midpoint lapse, generalises the radial single-particle matrix $\mathfrak{h}^{\text{rad}}$ of Section III to three dimensions. The shift

drags the bond-centred lapse coefficient. The midpoint average of the dragged lapse differs from the drag of the midpoint average by $O(a^2)$, so

$$[D[v], H[N]] = H[v^J \partial_J N] + O(a^2 t_{\max} \|v\|_{C^1} \|N\|_{C^3}). \quad (29)$$

d. H–H bracket. The oriented bond amplitude is $A_{\sigma I}^N(x) := t_I(x + \frac{\sigma a}{2} e_I) \frac{N(x) + N(x + \sigma a e_I)}{2}$. The single-particle commutator $[H[N], \hat{H}[M]]$ connects second neighbours via all two-step paths $x \rightarrow x + \sigma a e_I \rightarrow x + \sigma a e_I + \tau a e_J$ (excluding backtracking $(\tau, J) = (-\sigma, I)$). For each path, the coefficient antisymmetrised in $N \leftrightarrow M$ is

$$A_{\sigma I}^N A_{\tau J}^M|_{x + \sigma a e_I} - A_{\sigma I}^M A_{\tau J}^N|_{x + \sigma a e_I} = \frac{a}{2} t_I t_J (\sigma W_I + \tau W_J) + O(a^2), \quad (30)$$

where $W_I := N \partial_I M - M \partial_I N$. Summing over all signs $\sigma, \tau = \pm 1$, the cross-terms $W_I \partial_J \psi$ with $I \neq J$ cancel by antisymmetry, and the surviving displacements reassemble into the stencil (27). On the conformal branch $t_I = t_0 \lambda(x)$ (with $\lambda = \bar{N}$) this gives

$$\boxed{\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{i\hbar} [H[N], H[M]] &= D[h^{IJ} (N \partial_J M - M \partial_J N)] + \mathcal{R}, \\ h^{IJ} &= h_0 \lambda^2 \delta^{IJ}, \end{aligned}} \quad (31)$$

with $h_0 = 4d a^2 t_0^2 / \hbar^2 = 12a^2 t_0^2 / \hbar^2$ (in $d = 3$ spatial dimensions) and lattice remainder $\mathcal{R} = O(a^2)$. The per-direction causal speed is $c_* := \sqrt{h_0/d} = 2t_0 a / \hbar$, the half-filled tight-binding Fermi velocity; cross-direction two-step paths contribute the factor of d .

e. Anisotropic branch. When the hopping amplitudes $t_I(x)$ differ by direction ($I = 1, \dots, d$), the path coefficient (30) carries the anisotropic product $t_I t_J$. Same-direction paths ($\delta = 2\sigma a e_I$) give antisymmetrised coefficient $a\sigma t_I^2 W_I + O(a^2)$; cross-direction paths ($\delta = \sigma a e_I + \tau a e_J$, $I \neq J$, two paths via the two intermediate sites) give $a t_I t_J (\sigma W_I + \tau W_J) + O(a^2)$. The shift vector $v^K = \sum_{\delta} C(x, \delta) \delta^K$ is obtained by summing over signs $\sigma, \tau = \pm 1$. Same-direction paths contribute $4a^2 t_K^2 W_K$. Cross-direction displacement $\sigma a e_K + \tau a e_J$ contributes $a^2 t_K t_J (W_K + \sigma \tau W_J)$; summing over the four sign pairs: $\sum_{\sigma, \tau} \sigma \tau = 0$ kills W_J , leaving $4a^2 t_K t_J W_K$. Cross-direction $\sigma a e_I + \tau a e_K$ ($I \neq K$) similarly gives $4a^2 t_I t_K W_K$. Collecting,

$$v^K = 4a^2 t_K \left(\sum_{L=1}^d t_L \right) W_K. \quad (32)$$

No off-diagonal W_L ($L \neq K$) survives. The anisotropic structure function is therefore diagonal,

$$\boxed{h^{IJ} = \frac{4a^2}{\hbar^2} t_I \left(\sum_{K=1}^d t_K \right) \delta^{IJ} + O(a^2/\ell^2),} \quad (33)$$

with the same remainder $\mathcal{R} = O(a^2)$ as the conformal case. Setting $t_I = t_0 \lambda$ recovers $h^{II} = h_0 \lambda^2$.

The MI Dirichlet co-metric has $h_{\text{Dir}}^{II} \propto t_I^2$ (Section III), while the HDA gives $h_{\text{HDA}}^{II} \propto t_I \sum_K t_K$. These coincide if and only if $t_1 = t_2 = \dots = t_d$, so requiring the entanglement geometry to match the causal structure dynamically selects the conformal branch. On that branch $\kappa_I \propto t_0^2 \lambda^2$, so $h^{IJ}/(h_0 \delta^{IJ}) = \lambda^2$ and signals propagate at c_* through the geometry that MI defines. Off-diagonal h^{IJ} would require off-diagonal hopping $t_{IJ}(x)$ or next-nearest-neighbour couplings.

Together, equations (28), (29), and (31) close the lattice hypersurface-deformation algebra in the non-degenerate positive-lapse sector. The shift generator is extracted from the H – H commutator, not independently postulated. In the continuum limit $a \rightarrow 0$ the three brackets take the standard form with structure function $h^{IJ} = h_0 \lambda^2 \delta^{IJ}$; the HKT uniqueness theorem then identifies the emergent dynamics as general relativity. At finite lattice spacing the remainder \mathcal{R} is nonzero.

V. QUANTUM-INFORMATION CORRECTIONS TO SCHWARZSCHILD

This section quantifies the deviation from Einstein's equation on a *diagnostic family* of states whose hopping profile $t_n = t_0 \sqrt{1 - r_s/r_n}$ reproduces an exact Schwarzschild slice (Section III E). The self-consistent analysis of Sections VI–X later derives the same exterior profile from uniform hopping and a localized defect, and confirms (§VII D) these corrections.

A. Remainder bound

As an operator the lattice remainder \mathcal{R} in the HDA bracket (31) is $O(a^2)$, set by the Taylor defect of the stencil and path coefficients. When evaluated in the thermal state, its expectation value is further suppressed by the correlation length: the off-diagonal correlator decays as $|\delta G(x, y)| \sim q^{\|x-y\|_1}$ with $q := \beta t/4$, so long-range matrix elements of \mathcal{R} are exponentially damped. A second-moment bound on this geometric-series kernel gives the state-dependent estimate

$$|\langle \mathcal{R}(N, M) \rangle_{\rho}| \leq C_{\#}(r) \xi(r)^2 \text{Lip}(N) \text{Lip}(M), \quad (34)$$

where $\text{Lip}(N) := \sup |\nabla N|$ and

$$C_{\#}(r) = 4t(r)^4 \sum_{m \geq 1} m^2 q(r)^{2m} = 4t(r)^4 \frac{q(r)^2 (1 + q(r)^2)}{(1 - q(r)^2)^3}. \quad (35)$$

Equations (34)–(35) hold for any hopping profile $t(r)$ with $q(r) < 1$. On the diagnostic Schwarzschild slice $t(r) = t_0 \sqrt{f(r)}$ with $f := 1 - r_s/r$ (Section III E), the

high-temperature limit $q \ll 1$ gives

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\text{ff}}(r) &= \frac{\beta^2 t(r)^6}{4} (1 + O((\beta t)^2)) \\ &= \frac{\beta^2 t_0^6}{4} f(r)^3 (1 + O((\beta t_0)^2)), \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

and the local correlation length is

$$\xi(r) = \frac{a}{|\log(\beta t(r)/4)|} = \frac{a}{|\log(\beta t_0/4) + \frac{1}{2} \log f(r)|}. \quad (37)$$

(In three dimensions the lattice-sum prefactor acquires the 3D coordination factor, but the scaling $\mathcal{R} = O(\xi^2/\ell^2)$ is unchanged.)

B. Effective Einstein equation and T^{QI}

In the scaling limit $\xi/\ell \rightarrow 0$, the lattice brackets (28)–(31) approach the continuum hypersurface-deformation algebra with remainder $O(\xi^2/\ell^2)$. The HKT uniqueness theorem [29] then fixes the continuum Hamiltonian constraint to that of general relativity in the non-degenerate positive-lapse sector [27, 28]. At finite correlation length $\mathcal{R} \neq 0$, and the remainder captures the controlled deviation from Einstein's equation. On the prescribed Schwarzschild background, the pointwise bound (34) yields, via Cauchy–Schwarz, a symmetric positive-definite control form

$$\mathcal{B}(N, M) := \int_{r_s}^{\infty} C_{\text{ff}}(r) \xi(r)^2 \partial_r N \partial_r M r^2 dr + O(\xi^4 \nabla^4), \quad (38)$$

that bounds the antisymmetric remainder: $|\mathcal{R}(N, M)|^2 \leq \mathcal{B}(N, N) \mathcal{B}(M, M)$. Define $\mathfrak{t}(r) := C_{\text{ff}}(r) \xi(r)^2$. The diagonal of the bilinear form defines a quadratic anomaly norm,

$$\mathcal{Q}[N] := \int_{r_s}^{\infty} r^2 \mathfrak{t}(r) (\partial_r N)^2 dr, \quad (39)$$

which controls the size of the closure anomaly but is not itself a Hamiltonian constraint (the canonical constraint is linear in the lapse multiplier). Define the QI anomaly density

$$\begin{aligned} T^{\text{QI}}(r) &:= \frac{\mathfrak{t}(r)}{16\pi G} \\ &= \frac{\beta^2 t_0^6 a^2}{64\pi G} \frac{f(r)^3}{[\log(\beta t_0/4) + \frac{1}{2} \log f(r)]^2} (1 + O((\beta t_0)^2)), \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

so that $\mathcal{Q}[N] = 16\pi G \int r^2 T^{\text{QI}}(\partial_r N)^2 dr$. The profile is monotonically increasing from zero at $r = r_s$ to its flat-space value at infinity, regular for $r > r_s$, and vanishes as $r \rightarrow r_s$ on the diagnostic slice because $t(r) \rightarrow 0$.

At finite ξ , the effective stress-energy is not exactly covariantly conserved, since the HDA closes only up to

order ξ^2/ℓ^2 . The violation has the profile

$$\nabla_\mu T^{\text{eff}, \mu\nu}(r) \sim \frac{\xi(r)^2}{\ell(r)^2} T^{\text{eff}}(r), \quad (41)$$

where $\ell(r)$ is the local curvature scale. In Schwarzschild the Kretschmann scalar is $48G^2 M^2/(c_*^4 r^6)$, giving $\ell(r) \sim (c_*^2 r^3/GM)^{1/2}$. The violation scales as

$$\frac{\xi(r)^2}{\ell(r)^2} \sim \frac{a^2 GM}{c_*^2 r^3 [\log(\beta t_0/4) + \frac{1}{2} \log f(r)]^2}. \quad (42)$$

Both the curvature scale and $\xi(r)$ decrease toward the horizon (the former algebraically, the latter logarithmically in $f(r)$), so on the exterior ξ^2/ℓ^2 is bounded, peaking above the UV cap and decaying as r^{-3} far away. In the continuum limit $a \rightarrow 0$ it goes to zero. Semiclassical physics breaks down where $\xi^2/\ell^2 \sim 1$, i.e. at $r_{\text{EFT}} \sim (a^2 r_s)^{1/3}$.

C. Near-horizon MI structure

The MI conductances as $r_n \rightarrow r_s$ determine the near-horizon emergent geometry.

Near the horizon, the conductance between shells n and $n+1$ follows from (22):

$$\kappa_n \propto r_s^2 t_0^2 \frac{r_n - r_s}{r_n} \xrightarrow{r_n \rightarrow r_s^+} 0. \quad (43)$$

Shell-to-shell conductance vanishes continuously at the horizon. On the lattice, κ_{min} at $r_{\text{min}} = r_s + \delta r$ goes as $r_s t_0^2 \delta r$. MI between adjacent near-horizon shells is

$$\text{MI}_{n,n+1}|_{r_n \approx r_s} \approx g_n \frac{(\beta t_0)^2}{4} \frac{\delta r}{r_s}, \quad (44)$$

smaller by a factor $\delta r/r_s$. Weak correlation, but the shells stay connected.

Near the horizon, conductance determines a minimal sphere. The proper distance from the horizon to the innermost shell at $r_s + \delta r$ is

$$\Delta s = \int_{r_s}^{r_s + \delta r} \frac{dr}{\sqrt{1 - r_s/r}} = 2\sqrt{r_s} \delta r + O(\delta r^{3/2}), \quad (45)$$

which is finite for any $\delta r > 0$; the full integral $\int_{r_s}^R dr/\sqrt{f}$ also converges. There is a minimal sphere where the geometry truncates, of area

$$A_{\text{min}} = 4\pi r_{\text{min}}^2 \approx 4\pi r_s^2 \left(1 + \frac{2\delta r}{r_s}\right). \quad (46)$$

In the macroscopic limit $r_s \gg \delta r$ the area approaches $4\pi r_s^2$. At the Planck scale $r_s \sim \delta r \sim a$, $A_{\text{min}} \sim a^2$, in line with the singularity avoidance of Section VII E below.

For every shell ($r_n > r_s$) the conductance κ_n is positive; MI never vanishes. The emergent geometry is therefore *connected*, with no topology change. The horizon is a smooth cap rather than a topological boundary: $t_n = t_0 \sqrt{f(r_n)}$ goes to zero only in the limit $\delta r \rightarrow 0$.

VI. CLOSURE EQUATION FOR A LOCALIZED MASS DEFECT

We drop the prescribed hopping profile entirely at this point. The sole inputs are uniform hopping t_0 , a localized on-site potential V_0 on a small core, inverse temperature β_0 , and the shell degeneracy $g_n = 4\pi(r_n/a)^2$ (assuming $\mathbb{R} \times S^2$ topology). No radial metric or Schwarzschild profile is assumed. The spatial geometry is set by the closure equation self-consistently. For the emergent causal speed c_* appearing in the closure, we use $c_* = 2t_0 a / \hbar = \sqrt{\hbar_0/d}$, the per-direction causal speed extracted from the HDA structure function (Section IV). Both this section and the following one use analytic high-temperature conductances, with $\kappa_n \propto g_n t_0^2 \bar{N}_n^2$. Sections IX–X extend to arbitrary temperatures.

A. The microscopic model

The single-particle Hamiltonian on the radial shell chain is

$$\mathfrak{h}_{nm} = -t_0(\delta_{m,n+1} + \delta_{m,n-1}) + V_0 \delta_{nm} \mathbf{1}_{n \leq n_{\text{core}}}, \quad (47)$$

with uniform radial hopping t_0 and a repulsive on-site potential $V_0 > 0$ on the inner n_{core} shells ($r_n \leq r_{\text{core}}$); Here n_{core} is a free parameter specifying the compact support of the matter source, analogous to the radius of a star in GR. Shell degeneracies $g_n = 4\pi(r_n/a)^2$ as before.

$\rho = e^{-\beta H}/Z$ is a Gaussian state. Tridiagonal linear algebra therefore suffices for the single-particle correlation matrix,

$$G^{(0)} = (e^{\beta_0 \mathfrak{h}} + \text{Id})^{-1}, \quad (48)$$

at $O(N_s^2)$ cost (tridiagonal eigensolver), where N_s is the number of shells. One then extracts reference modular data from the shell-energy magnitudes $\rho(n) := \langle -h_n \rangle > 0$ (ρ with no argument denotes the density matrix, and the sign convention is that $-h_n$ is positive at high T),

$$\rho(n) := 2t_0 g_n \text{Re} G_{n,n+1}^{(0)} + V_0 g_n G_{nn}^{(0)} \mathbf{1}_{n \leq n_{\text{core}}}. \quad (49)$$

At high temperature,

$$\rho(n) \approx \begin{cases} g_n (\frac{1}{2} \beta_0 t_0^2 + \frac{1}{2} V_0) & n \leq n_{\text{core}}, \\ g_n \cdot \frac{1}{2} \beta_0 t_0^2 & n > n_{\text{core}}. \end{cases} \quad (50)$$

The source density contrast relative to $\rho_0 = g_n \beta_0 t_0^2 / 2$ (the uniform background) is

$$\tilde{\rho}(n) := \rho(n) - \rho_0 = \begin{cases} g_n V_0 / 2 & n \leq n_{\text{core}}, \\ 0 & n > n_{\text{core}}, \end{cases} \quad (51)$$

a localized source whose total integral defines a “mass”

$$\mathcal{M} := \sum_{n \leq n_{\text{core}}} \tilde{\rho}(n) = \frac{V_0}{2} \sum_{n \leq n_{\text{core}}} g_n \propto V_0 r_{\text{core}}^3 / a^3. \quad (52)$$

The gravitational mass is $M := \mathcal{M}/c_*^2$. The Schwarzschild radius $r_s = 2GM/c_*^2$ involves both \mathcal{M} (set by V_0) and G . The emergent Newton constant G comes from the flat-space conductance $\kappa_{\text{flat}} = g_n t_0^2$ through the Newtonian limit of the closure equation (Section VII A). Weak-field scaling gives $r_s \propto \beta_0 V_0 / (c_*^4 t_0^2)$.

The quantity ρ_0 is the energy profile of the *background state* (the uniform thermal state at inverse temperature β_0) around which the geometry is reconstructed.

B. The self-consistent closure equation

The obstacle to a Newtonian exterior is Yukawa screening. In linear response the background acts as a polarisable medium, giving $e^{-m_\epsilon r}/r$ instead of $1/r$. The two-state closure below removes this screening by matching modular data of both states in the same lapse field. One seeks a calibration field Φ for which microscopic and reconstructed modular data agree.

1. Maximum-entropy reconstruction

Introduce a spatially varying inverse temperature, $\beta_n = \beta_0 N_n$, where $N_n := 1 + \Phi_n / c_*^2$. Maximum entropy selects $\sigma[\Phi] \propto \exp(-\beta_0 \sum_n N_n h_n)$, a generalized Gibbs state at the local temperatures. Bonds on the lattice carry the symmetric weight $\bar{N}_n = (N_n + N_{n+1})/2$. The implemented single-particle Hamiltonian (68) is bond-smearing with this weight, so h_n below denotes the shell-centred kinetic observable $\frac{1}{2}(h_{n-\frac{1}{2}} + h_{n+\frac{1}{2}})$ and the site parameter θ_n is the pair of bond parameters it controls.

2. Stationarity and the KMS Dirichlet form

The Bogoliubov–Kubo–Mori (BKM) Hessian of S_{rel} on the exponential family $\sigma[\Phi]$ is nearest-neighbour by clustering. Mutual information inherits this locality and supplies a positive-definite Dirichlet form whose stationarity determines Φ .

Step 1: S_{rel} on the exponential family. With $\theta_n := \beta_0 N_n$, the state is $\sigma[\theta] \propto \exp(-\sum_n \theta_n h_n)$. Writing $\Delta h_n := h_n - \langle h_n \rangle$, the relative entropy at leading order [30] gives a second-order expansion with the BKM metric tensor g_{nm}^{BKM} :

$$S_{\text{rel}}(\sigma[\theta + \delta\theta] \parallel \sigma[\theta]) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n,m} g_{nm}^{\text{BKM}}(\theta) \delta\theta_n \delta\theta_m + O(\|\delta\theta\|^3), \quad (53)$$

where $g_{nm}^{\text{BKM}} := \int_0^1 \text{Tr}(\sigma^s \Delta h_n \sigma^{1-s} \Delta h_m) ds$.

Step 2: From BKM locality to a positive edge Dirichlet form. Araki’s clustering [31] implies exponential decay of BKM covariances for lattice Gibbs states. In the quasi-free setting, Wick factorization strengthens the decay, and for general finite-range Hamiltonians an equivalent quasi-locality statement follows from the local Markov

property of quantum Gibbs states [32]. Together these results imply exponential BKM locality,

$$|g_{nm}^{\text{BKM}}(\theta)| \leq C_E e^{-|n-m|a/\xi_{\text{BKM}}}, \quad (54)$$

with $\xi_{\text{BKM}} = O(\xi_T)$ and C_E uniform on compact $\beta_0 t_0$ -intervals. For the bilinear bond observables of the free-fermion model, Wick factorization sharpens the decay to $e^{-2|n-m|a/\xi_T}$ (the covariance is quadratic in the exponentially decaying two-point function). For the half-filled tight-binding chain, the smallest imaginary-momentum pole of the Fermi function gives $\xi_T = a/\text{arsinh}(\pi/(2\beta_0 t_0))$. At $\beta_0 t_0 = O(1)$ one has $\xi_{\text{BKM}} \sim a$ and the nearest-neighbour truncation is controlled.

The closure equation is *not* obtained by algebraically rewriting the site-parameter quadratic form $\sum_{nm} g_{nm}^{\text{BKM}} \delta\theta_n \delta\theta_m$ as a difference-squared form (the bond-symmetric decomposition gives $g_{n,n+1}^{\text{BKM}} > 0$, §VIB 2, so the naive Dirichlet coupling $-g_{n,n+1}^{\text{BKM}} < 0$). Instead, one uses the canonical *KMS Dirichlet form* associated with the same Gibbs state, in which the carré du champ is the square of a quasi-local derivation and positivity is automatic [33]. For the nearest-neighbour shell chain, define the bond-local derivations $\delta_{n+\frac{1}{2}}(\cdot) := [h_{n+\frac{1}{2}}, \cdot]$, where $h_{n+\frac{1}{2}} = -t_0 \bar{N}_n \sum_{\alpha=1}^{g_n} (c_{n+1,\alpha}^\dagger c_{n+1,\alpha} + \text{h.c.})$ is the bond Hamiltonian. The KMS Dirichlet form is

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{KMS}}[X] := \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^{N-1} \text{Cov}_{\sigma[\theta]}^{\text{BKM}}(\delta_{n+\frac{1}{2}}(X)^\dagger, \delta_{n+\frac{1}{2}}(X)), \quad (55)$$

where the adjoint in the first slot gives the sesquilinear KMS inner product (since $\delta_{n+\frac{1}{2}}(X) = [h_{n+\frac{1}{2}}, X]$ is anti-Hermitian for Hermitian X , the carré du champ $\delta(X)^\dagger \delta(X) \geq 0$ ensures positivity). For diagonal $X = \sum_n X_n \hat{n}_n$, the commutator factors exactly:

$$\delta_{n+\frac{1}{2}}(X) = (X_{n+1} - X_n) \mathcal{J}_{n+\frac{1}{2}}, \quad \mathcal{J}_{n+\frac{1}{2}} := t_0 \bar{N}_n \sum_{\alpha=1}^{g_n} (c_{n+1,\alpha}^\dagger c_{n,\alpha} - c_{n,\alpha}^\dagger c_{n+1,\alpha}), \quad (56)$$

where $\mathcal{J}_{n+\frac{1}{2}}$ is the bond current operator. Substituting into (55) gives the weighted graph Dirichlet energy

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{KMS}}[\Phi] = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^{N-1} \kappa_n^{\text{KMS}}[\Phi] (\Phi_{n+1} - \Phi_n)^2 + O(e^{-4a/\xi_T}), \quad (57)$$

with *positive* edge weights $\kappa_n^{\text{KMS}}[\Phi] := \text{Cov}_{\sigma[\theta]}^{\text{BKM}}(\mathcal{J}_{n+\frac{1}{2}}^\dagger, \mathcal{J}_{n+\frac{1}{2}}) > 0$. The structural lapse scaling $\kappa_n^{\text{KMS}} \propto (t_0 \bar{N}_n)^2$ follows from the explicit prefactor in $h_{n+\frac{1}{2}}$. The remaining dimensionless factor is bond-local and renormalizes only the overall coupling. An unscreened Poisson exterior is restored because the mass/susceptibility term of the full BKM quadratic form cancels in the two-state closure (§IX below).

Step 3: Identifying edge weights via MI. For the free-fermion chain, both the KMS edge weight κ_n^{KMS} and the bond mutual information $\text{MI}_{n,n+1}$ scale as \bar{N}_n^2 at high temperature.

High- T bond MI and BKM coefficient

We now derive the leading high-temperature behaviour of the single-channel bond MI and the associated BKM and KMS coefficients for the nearest-neighbour half-filled free-fermion chain with Hamiltonian $H = -t \sum_j (c_j^\dagger c_{j+1} + c_{j+1}^\dagger c_j)$ at inverse temperature β . Let $\text{MI}_{1\text{ch}}(j:j+1)$ denote the mutual information between neighboring sites.

Because the state is quasi-free, the reduced state on two sites is completely determined by the 2×2 correlation matrix C with entries $C_{ab} = \langle c_a^\dagger c_b \rangle$. At half filling, particle-hole symmetry enforces $C_{11} = C_{22} = \frac{1}{2}$. Write $b := C_{12} = C_{21}$ (real by reflection symmetry). Then C has eigenvalues

$$\lambda_{\pm} = \frac{1}{2} \pm b, \quad (58)$$

and the von Neumann entropy of the two-site reduced state is $S_{12} = h(\lambda_+) + h(\lambda_-)$ where $h(p) := -p \ln p - (1-p) \ln(1-p)$. Each single site has entropy $S_1 = S_2 = h(\frac{1}{2}) = \ln 2$, so

$$\text{MI}_{1\text{ch}}(j:j+1) = S_1 + S_2 - S_{12} = 2 \ln 2 - h(\frac{1}{2}+b) - h(\frac{1}{2}-b). \quad (59)$$

A Taylor expansion about $b = 0$ gives $h(\frac{1}{2} \pm b) = \ln 2 - 2b^2 + O(b^4)$, hence

$$\text{MI}_{1\text{ch}}(j:j+1) = 4b^2 + O(b^4). \quad (60)$$

It remains to compute b at high temperature. In the infinite chain, translation invariance gives the momentum-space representation

$$b = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{dk}{2\pi} e^{ik} f(\varepsilon(k)) \quad \text{with} \quad \varepsilon(k) = -2t \cos k, \quad (61)$$

where $f(\varepsilon) = (e^{\beta\varepsilon} + 1)^{-1}$. For $x = \beta t \rightarrow 0$,

$$f(\varepsilon) = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{\beta\varepsilon}{4} + O(\beta^3 \varepsilon^3). \quad (62)$$

The constant term integrates to zero because $\int e^{ik} dk = 0$. Using $\varepsilon(k) = -2t \cos k$ and $\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{dk}{2\pi} e^{ik} \cos k = \frac{1}{2}$ in the linear term gives

$$b = \frac{\beta t}{4} + O(\beta^3 t^3). \quad (63)$$

Substituting into (60) gives the single-channel MI at high temperature:

$$\text{MI}_{1\text{ch}}(j:j+1) = \frac{x^2}{4} + O(x^4). \quad (64)$$

For the BKM coefficient, evaluate the BKM metric tensor $g_{nm}^{\text{BKM}}(\theta) = \int_0^1 \text{Tr}(\sigma^s \Delta h_n \sigma^{1-s} \Delta h_m) ds$ appearing in (53) on the high- T Gibbs state $\sigma \propto e^{-\beta H}$. At $\beta = 0$, $\sigma = \text{Id}/\text{Tr}(\text{Id})$ is maximally mixed and the BKM inner product reduces to the Hilbert-Schmidt covariance $g_{nm}^{\text{BKM}}(\beta=0) = \text{Tr}(\rho_0 h_n h_m)$, since $\text{Tr}(\rho_0 h_n) = 0$ at half

filling. Use the bond-symmetric decomposition $H = \sum_j h_j$ with $h_j = -\frac{t}{2}(c_{j-1}^\dagger c_j + c_j^\dagger c_{j-1}) - \frac{t}{2}(c_j^\dagger c_{j+1} + c_{j+1}^\dagger c_j)$ (boundary convention $c_0 = c_{L+1} = 0$). A Wick/CAR evaluation at half filling gives

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tr}(\rho_0 h_j^2) &= \frac{t^2}{4}, & \text{Tr}(\rho_0 h_j h_{j+1}) &= \frac{t^2}{8}, \\ \text{Tr}(\rho_0 h_j h_k) &= 0 \quad (|j-k| \geq 2), \end{aligned} \quad (65)$$

where the only nonzero cross-term arises from the shared bond $(j, j+1)$ in the bond-symmetric decomposition; the $|j-k| \geq 2$ vanishing follows because the hopping operators share no common site. The BKM covariance is therefore nearest-neighbor with $g_{j,j+1}^{\text{BKM}} = t^2/8 > 0$. For the KMS edge weight, use the CAR algebra identity $\mathcal{J}^2 = -t^2(\hat{n}_j + \hat{n}_{j+1} - 2\hat{n}_j\hat{n}_{j+1})$, so $\kappa_{1\text{ch}}^{\text{KMS}} = \text{Tr}(\rho_0 \mathcal{J}^\dagger \mathcal{J}) = -\text{Tr}(\rho_0 \mathcal{J}^2) = t^2(1/2 + 1/2 - 2 \cdot 1/4) = t^2/2$ at $\beta = 0$. Analyticity in β then gives the single-channel KMS edge weight:

$$\kappa_{1\text{ch}}^{\text{KMS}} := \text{Cov}_\sigma^{\text{BKM}}(\mathcal{J}_{j+\frac{1}{2}}^\dagger, \mathcal{J}_{j+\frac{1}{2}}) = \frac{t^2}{2} + O(\beta^2 t^4), \quad (66)$$

where $\mathcal{J}_{j+\frac{1}{2}} = t(c_{j+1}^\dagger c_j - c_j^\dagger c_{j+1})$ is the one-channel bond current. Both $\text{MI}_{1\text{ch}}$ and $\kappa_{1\text{ch}}^{\text{KMS}}$ scale as \bar{N}^2 under lapse smearing $t \rightarrow t\bar{N}$, so ratio-normalised MI conductances inherit the nearest-neighbour locality guaranteed by BKM clustering. Combining (64) and (66) gives

$$\text{MI}_{1\text{ch}}(j:j+1) = \frac{\beta^2}{2} \kappa_{1\text{ch}}^{\text{KMS}} + O(\beta^4 t^4), \quad (67)$$

confirming that single-channel MI is a direct proxy for the KMS Dirichlet-form edge weight at high temperature. We therefore set the conductances by ratio-normalised MI, $\kappa_n[\Phi] = g_n t_0^2 \text{MI}_{1\text{ch}}(n:n+1; \Phi) / \text{MI}_{1\text{ch}}^{(0)}$, which (a) preserves positivity, (b) is computable exactly from the correlation matrix in the Gaussian solver, and (c) reproduces $\kappa \propto \bar{N}^2$ in the regime where the derivative expansion and HDA remainder bounds apply. Normalising by the $\Phi = 0$ value, the β_0^2 factor drops out, giving $\kappa_n = g_n t_0^2 \text{MI} / \text{MI}^{(0)}$.

Substituting $\delta\theta_n = (\beta_0/c_*^2)\delta\Phi_n$, the KMS Dirichlet energy (57) with MI-identified edge weights becomes $\mathcal{E}_{\text{mis}}[\Phi] = \sum_{\langle n,m \rangle} \kappa_{nm}(\Phi_n - \Phi_m)^2/2$. Stationarity $\delta\mathcal{J}/\delta\Phi_n = 0$ (differentiating both the conductance-weighted Dirichlet energy and the source term) yields the closure equation (73) below.

3. Two-state field matching

Target and reconstructed states must be evaluated in the same lapse field. Without this, $\Phi = 0$ is a trivial solution and the background produces Yukawa screening (§VII A). The local inverse temperature $\beta_{\text{loc}} = \beta_0 N$ follows from the KMS structure of the reconstructed state. Its identification with Tolman's equilibrium law [34] is an output of the emergent spacetime metric, not an input.

4. Reconstructed state and closure equation

The thermal state of the lapse-smear single-particle Hamiltonian gives the reconstructed state $\sigma[\Phi]$:

$$\mathfrak{h}[\Phi]_{nm} = -t_0 \bar{N}_n \delta_{m,n+1} - t_0 \bar{N}_{n-1} \delta_{m,n-1} + V_0 \delta_{nm} \mathbf{1}_{n \leq n_{\text{core}}}, \quad (68)$$

where $\bar{N}_n := (N_n + N_{n+1})/2$ averages the lapse across each bond. Since V_0 is bare rather than lapse-smear and the lapse enters only the hopping, the energy mismatch is confined strictly to the core. Its correlation matrix is

$$G^{(\Phi)} = (e^{\beta_0 \mathfrak{h}[\Phi]} + \text{Id})^{-1}, \quad (69)$$

It is the nontrivial inter-shell correlations of $\sigma[\Phi]$ that give the MI its form

$$\text{MI}_{n,n+1}[\Phi] = g_n \frac{(\beta_0 \bar{N}_n t_0)^2}{4} (1 + O((\beta_0 t_0)^2)). \quad (70)$$

The Φ -dependent conductances come from the KMS/BKM bond-current covariance, ratio-normalized against the flat background (at high temperature, this reduces to the MI ratio). Writing $\mathcal{I}_{n+\frac{1}{2}} = c_{n+1}^\dagger c_n - c_n^\dagger c_{n+1}$ for the bare single-channel hopping operator,

$$\kappa_n[\Phi] := g_n t_0^2 \bar{N}_n^2 \frac{\text{Cov}_{\sigma[\Phi]}^{\text{BKM}}(\mathcal{I}_{n+\frac{1}{2}}^\dagger, \mathcal{I}_{n+\frac{1}{2}})}{\text{Cov}_{\sigma[0]}^{\text{BKM}}(\mathcal{I}_{n+\frac{1}{2}}^\dagger, \mathcal{I}_{n+\frac{1}{2}})},$$

$\kappa_n(\Phi=0) = g_n t_0^2$ follows (since $\bar{N}(\Phi=0) = 1$ and the covariance ratio equals unity). At high temperature,

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa_n[\Phi] &= g_n t_0^2 \bar{N}_n^2 (1 + O((\beta_0 t_0)^2)) \\ &= g_n t_0^2 \left(1 + \frac{\Phi_n + \Phi_{n+1}}{2c_*^2} \right)^2 (1 + O((\beta_0 t_0)^2)). \end{aligned} \quad (71)$$

The conductances give the energy expectation of the reconstructed state at high temperature:

$$\langle h_n \rangle_{G^{(\Phi)}} \approx g_n \bar{N}_n^2 \frac{\beta_0 t_0^2}{2} + \frac{V_0}{2} g_n \mathbf{1}_{n \leq n_{\text{core}}} + O(\beta_0^2 t_0^2). \quad (72)$$

At leading high- T order, ρ_{tgt} is Φ -independent, so stationarity of $S_{\text{rel}}(\rho_{\text{tgt}} \parallel \sigma[\Phi]) + \mathcal{E}_{\text{mis}}[\Phi]$ uses the standard identity $\partial_{\Phi_n} S_{\text{rel}}(\rho \parallel \sigma(\Phi)) = (\beta_0/c_*^2)(\langle h_n \rangle_\rho - \langle h_n \rangle_{\sigma(\Phi)})$ (valid for fixed ρ). The closure balances (i) the Dirichlet-form variation of \mathcal{E}_{mis} (a weighted graph Laplacian plus the EL correction from $\partial\kappa/\partial\Phi$) against (ii) the modular-energy mismatch. The graph-Laplacian form of the closure equation is

$$\boxed{\sum_{m \sim n} \kappa_{nm}[\Phi] (\Phi_n - \Phi_m) = \frac{\beta_0}{c_*^2} (\langle h_n \rangle_{G^{(\Phi)}} - \rho(n))}. \quad (73)$$

Both sides depend on Φ : this is a system of N_s coupled nonlinear equations in N_s unknowns $\{\Phi_n\}$. This graph-Laplacian form serves as a Picard preconditioner; the true

Euler-Lagrange equation, which includes $\partial\kappa/\partial\Phi$ corrections, is derived in Section IX. Physically, the closure is the condition for the state to be in thermal equilibrium in the geometry it generates. Any mismatch between the local KMS temperature $\beta_0 N_n$ and the lapse of the emergent metric would violate the Tolman relation [34], driving heat flow until the self-consistent fixed point is reached.

C. Emergent geometry from Φ

Define the emergent radial co-metric from the conductances (equation (18)) as $h^{rr}/h_0 := \kappa[\Phi]/\kappa_{\text{flat}}$. In the analytic high- T limit, $\kappa/\kappa_{\text{flat}} = \bar{N}^2$ (equation (71)). Then

$$h^{rr}[\Phi](r) = h_0 \left(1 + \frac{\Phi(r)}{c_*^2} \right)^2; \quad (74)$$

A negative gravitational potential $\Phi < 0$ means $(1 + \Phi/c_*^2)^2 < 1$, so the radial co-metric gets suppressed. In the Newtonian limit, $\Phi = -c_*^2 r_s/(2r) + O(r_s/r)^2$, and the leading contribution from equation (74) is

$$h^{rr}(r) \propto t_0^2 \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{2r} \right)^2 = t_0^2 \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r} + \frac{r_s^2}{4r^2} \right). \quad (75)$$

The leading term gives $h^{rr} \propto 1 - r_s/r$. Artifacts of the Newtonian truncation account for the subleading terms. $h^{rr} \propto 1 - r_s/r$ follows from the exact solution of the full nonlinear variational equation (§VII B 2). All that is needed is uniform hopping and a localized mass. The Schwarzschild radial profile follows from the closure equation without imposing a metric ansatz.

Combining these results, the full emergent spatial line element is

$$dl^2 = \frac{C_0}{t_0^2(1 + \Phi/c_*^2)^2} dr^2 + r^2 d\Omega^2, \quad (76)$$

with $\Phi(r)$ determined self-consistently by (73).

How does this differ from the prescribed-geometry analysis? The Schwarzschild co-metric was put in by hand through t_n in that analysis (Sections III–V). Here hopping is uniform. Radial geometry is an output, and the prescribed-geometry results serve as a check.

VII. EMERGENT SCHWARZSCHILD GEOMETRY AND NONLINEAR CORRECTIONS

We extract the physical content of the closure equation (73). The results include Newtonian emergence, exact Schwarzschild co-metric, QI correction, and strong-field behavior. In the analytic approach, discrete sums become integrals ($\sum_n \delta r \rightarrow \int dr$, $a \ll r$), leading high-temperature expressions are used ($\kappa_n \propto g_n t_0^2 \bar{N}_n^2$, $\rho_\sigma \propto g_n \bar{N}_n^2 \beta_0 t_0^2/2$), and ξ remains finite. Later Sections VIII–X solve the closure numerically, progressively dropping the high- T approximation.

A. Weak-field regime: Newtonian emergence and Yukawa screening

The self-consistent closure equation (73) can produce the Newtonian fall-off, but only if the correct background is chosen for the linear perturbation. Naive linearization introduces a Yukawa screening term. Set $V_0 \ll c_*^2/\beta_0$ so that $\Phi \ll c_*^2$. At high T , $\kappa_n[\Phi] \approx g_n t_0^2 \bar{N}_n^2$ and $\langle h_n \rangle_{G(\Phi)} \approx \rho_0 + 2\rho_0 \Phi_n/c_*^2 + O(\Phi^2)$, which makes the right-hand side of (73)

$$\frac{\beta_0}{c_*^2} (\langle h_n \rangle_{G(\Phi)} - \rho(n)) \approx \frac{2\beta_0\rho_0}{c_*^4} \Phi_n - \frac{\beta_0}{c_*^2} \tilde{\rho}(n), \quad (77)$$

and $\tilde{\rho}(n)$ stands for the localized source density contrast (51). The linear-in- Φ term, moved to the left-hand side, leaves a Poisson-Helmholtz equation on the shell chain:

$$\sum_{m \sim n} \kappa_0 (\Phi_n - \Phi_m) - \frac{2\beta_0\rho_0}{c_*^4} \Phi_n = -\frac{\beta_0}{c_*^2} \tilde{\rho}(n), \quad (78)$$

with $\kappa_0 = g_n t_0^2$. In the continuum limit one finds

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^2 \sigma_0 \frac{d\Phi}{dr} \right) - m_Y^2 \Phi = -\tilde{\rho}_{\text{cont}}(r), \quad m_Y^2 := \frac{2\beta_0\rho_0}{c_*^4}, \quad (79)$$

with $\tilde{\rho}_{\text{cont}}(r)$ the continuum source from (51), $\sigma_0 \propto t_0^2$, ρ_0 the per-shell energy (continuum energy density $\epsilon_0 := \rho_0/(\Delta r \cdot 4\pi r^2)$). The per-shell $g_n \propto r_n^2$ in ρ_0 cancels the vertex measure $\mu_n \propto r_n^2 \delta r$; m_Y^2 is therefore position-independent. The origin of m_Y is the *uniform thermal background* $\rho_0 \neq 0$. Linear response around a polarizable medium generically screens, exactly as in Coulomb-Debye theory.

On a nearest-neighbor lattice $c_* = O(t_0 a)$ is Lieb-Robinson bounded [35, 36]. At fixed gravitational coupling $G = \beta_0 a/(4\pi t_0^2)$, sending $m_Y \rightarrow 0$ via $\beta_0 \rightarrow 0$ simultaneously drives $G \rightarrow 0$, so m_Y cannot be tuned away while retaining long-range gravity (in a time-dependent extension, $m_Y \neq 0$ would correspond to a massive graviton with Yukawa-screened $e^{-m_Y r}/r$ potential). The closure operator itself must be Poisson rather than Helmholtz.

The screening is removed by a closure over two separate states. No polarizable medium exists at infinity in vacuum. The two-state closure implements this by comparing two states *in the same gravitational field* (the reconstructed background $\sigma[\Phi]$ and the defect target $\tau[\Phi]$, i.e. the same Hamiltonian with the on-site defect V_0) rather than a single fixed target computed at $\Phi = 0$. Beyond the core the energy profiles of the two states agree up to exponentially small tails:

$$|\rho_\sigma(n; \Phi) - \rho_{\text{tgt}}(n; \Phi)| \leq C e^{-(r_n - r_{\text{core}})/\xi} \quad (n > n_{\text{core}}). \quad (80)$$

The exterior closure equation is therefore Poisson to exponential accuracy,

$$\sum_{m \sim n} \kappa_{nm}[\Phi] (\Phi_n - \Phi_m) = 0 \quad (n > n_{\text{core}}), \quad (81)$$

with no linear-response mass term. Since $\kappa_{nm}[\Phi] \approx \kappa_0$ at weak field, the unique asymptotically flat solution is Newtonian,

$$\Phi(r) = -\frac{GM}{r} + O(1/r^2). \quad (82)$$

Because the two-state closure excludes the uniform thermal background as a gravitating source, Yukawa screening is removed non-perturbatively. It is discrete Gauss-law matching that fixes the emergent G .

For the uniform grid $r_n = na$, set $\kappa_n = g_n t_0^2$ and $g_n = 4\pi(r_n/a)^2$. Taylor expansion of the graph Laplacian yields

$$\begin{aligned} (L_\kappa \Phi)_n &:= \sum_{m \sim n} \kappa_{nm} (\Phi_n - \Phi_m) \\ &= -4\pi t_0^2 \left. \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^2 \frac{d\Phi}{dr} \right) \right|_{r=r_n} + O(a), \end{aligned} \quad (83)$$

The $4\pi r^2$ contributed by g_n is the spherical measure, and the continuum form (79) follows from it. Summing $(L_\kappa \Phi)_n = \kappa_n (\Phi_n - \Phi_{n+1}) + \kappa_{n-1} (\Phi_n - \Phi_{n-1})$ over $n \leq n_c$ cancels every interior bond pairwise, so the core sum reduces to the outward flux through the last core bond,

$$\sum_{n \leq n_c} (L_\kappa \Phi)_n = -\kappa_{n_c} (\Phi_{n_c+1} - \Phi_{n_c}),$$

where regularity at the center is the discrete statement that there is no inward flux through $r = 0$ (equivalently $r^2 \partial_r \Phi \rightarrow 0$). For $\Phi_n = -GM(1/r_n - 1/R)$ and $\kappa_{n_c} = 4\pi(r_{n_c}/a)^2 t_0^2$, one has $\Phi_{n_c+1} - \Phi_{n_c} = GM a / [r_{n_c}(r_{n_c} + a)]$, hence the flux is $4\pi t_0^2 GM/a + O(a/r_c)$; matching this to $(\beta_0/c_*^2)\mathcal{M}$ on the right-hand side gives

$$G = \frac{\beta_0}{4\pi t_0^2} a \quad (\hbar = t_0 = a = 1), \quad (84)$$

which is the lattice-unit Gauss-law matching relation extracted from the discrete vacuum flux. Restoring dimensions uses the HDA-calibrated causal speed $c_* = 2t_0 a/\hbar$ together with the thermodynamic identification $a^2 = 4\alpha_S \hbar G/c_*^3$ (Section VII F). With $M := \mathcal{M}/c_*^2$ from (52) and $4\pi t_0^2 GM/a = (\beta_0/c_*^2)\mathcal{M}$, the c_*^2 cancels. $GM_{\text{est}}(r) := -\Phi(r) rR/(R-r)$, the boundary-corrected estimator used for all numerical diagnostics. The discrete vacuum operator makes this quantity exactly constant. The offset from imposing $\Phi(R) = 0$ at the boundary is removed by the estimator. Removing the background contribution is the lattice way to impose $\Lambda = 0$. This removal is exact, not approximate. The normalized exponential family $\sigma[\Phi] \propto \exp(-\sum_n \theta_n h_n)$ is invariant under shifting every h_n by a common constant c (the normalization absorbs the factor $e^{-c \sum_n \theta_n}$), so any spatially uniform additive energy is invisible to the closure parameters and the two-state subtraction eliminates it identically.

The two-state subtraction has a deeper information-theoretic origin. In continuum QFT, bare entropies and

energies diverge, and relative entropy $\mathcal{S}(\tau_A || \sigma_A)$ is the unique UV-finite monotone mismatch between a localized excitation and the vacuum [37]. The two-state closure is the lattice realization of this principle (Section IX B 1).

B. Emergent co-metric: comparison with Schwarzschild

The self-consistent co-metric (74) with the weak-field solution $\Phi = -GM/r$ gives

$$h^{rr}(r) = h_0 \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{2r}\right)^2 = h_0 \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r} + \frac{r_s^2}{4r^2}\right), \quad (85)$$

where $r_s = 2GM/c_*^2$. This matches the Schwarzschild co-metric $h_{\text{Schw}}^{rr} = h_0(1 - r_s/r)$ at first post-Newtonian order, with a discrepancy at second order,

$$h^{rr}(r) - h_{\text{Schw}}^{rr}(r) = h_0 \frac{r_s^2}{4r^2} + O(r_s^3/r^3). \quad (86)$$

The discrepancy is $O(r_s/r)^2$, which is the expected order at which

- (i) the nonlinear terms in the closure equation (neglected in the linearized Poisson equation (78)) contribute;
- (ii) the self-consistent backreaction of the conductances $\kappa[\Phi]$ on the Laplacian modifies the potential.

The discrepancy arises because the linearized solution $\Phi = -GM/r$ was substituted into the Φ -dependent conductance $(1 + \Phi/c_*^2)^2$ while ignoring backreaction. The true Euler-Lagrange equation (§VII B 2 below) removes this discrepancy and yields exact Schwarzschild at all post-Newtonian orders.

1. The variational functional and its Euler-Lagrange equation

The mismatch energy is a Dirichlet form with Φ -dependent conductances,

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{mis}}[\phi] = \frac{\sigma_0}{2} \int (1 + \phi)^2 (\phi')^2 r^2 dr, \quad (87)$$

where $\phi := \Phi/c_*^2$ and $\sigma_0 \propto t_0^2$ is the uniform radial conductivity. The conductances $\sigma[\phi] = \sigma_0(1 + \phi)^2$ depend on ϕ through the lapse $N = 1 + \phi$ (equation (71)). This section uses the analytic high- T law $\kappa \propto \bar{N}^2$. The full solver of Section X replaces it with exact KMS/BKM covariances and confirms Schwarzschild to $\lesssim 1\%$.

Stationarity requires varying both ϕ' and the ϕ -dependent conductance $(1 + \phi)^2$. With $\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2}(1 + \phi)^2 (\phi')^2 r^2$, the Euler-Lagrange equation gives

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{d}{dr} [r^2 (1 + \phi)^2 \phi'] - (1 + \phi)(\phi')^2 = 0. \quad (88)$$

The second term is the $\partial\kappa/\partial\phi$ contribution from ϕ -dependent conductances.

A change of variable simplifies the equation. Setting $u := 1 + \phi$ (so $u > 0$ on the positive-lapse branch), the mismatch energy becomes

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{mis}} = \frac{\sigma_0}{2} \int u^2 (u')^2 r^2 dr, \quad (89)$$

with Lagrangian density $\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2}r^2u^2(u')^2$. The Euler-Lagrange equation is

$$\frac{d}{dr}(r^2u^2u') - r^2u(u')^2 = 0. \quad (90)$$

Expanding the derivative gives $r^2[2u(u')^2 + u^2u''] + 2ru^2u' - r^2u(u')^2 = 0$, i.e. $r^2[u(u')^2 + u^2u''] + 2ru^2u' = 0$. Dividing by $u > 0$ and recognizing the total derivative:

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{d}{dr} [r^2 u u'] = 0. \quad (91)$$

2. Natural variable $w = N^2$ and Dirichlet structure

Define $w := u^2 = N^2 = (1 + \phi)^2$. Then $u u' = \frac{1}{2}w'$, and the mismatch energy (89) becomes

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{mis}} = \frac{\sigma_0}{8} \int (w')^2 r^2 dr. \quad (92)$$

This is a standard Dirichlet energy in the variable w (quadratic in w' , with no nonlinear prefactor). The quadratic lapse law is special in a precise sense: for a general conductance law $\kappa \propto N^p$, define $W_p := N^{(p+2)/2}$. Then $N^p(N')^2 = 4(p+2)^{-2}(W_p')^2$, so $\mathcal{E}_p \propto \int r^2(W_p')^2 dr$ and the exterior Euler-Lagrange equation is

$$\frac{d}{dr}(r^2 W_p') = 0 \quad \text{for every } p \neq -2,$$

with harmonic solution $W_p = 1 - C/r$. The radial co-metric is $h^{rr}/h_0 = N^p = W_p^{2p/(p+2)} = (1 - C/r)^{2p/(p+2)}$. Exact Schwarzschild $h^{rr}/h_0 = 1 - r_s/r$ requires $2p/(p+2) = 1$, i.e. $p = 2$. Thus $p = 2$ is singled out not because other exponents fail to linearize, but because only the quadratic law makes the harmonic variable $w = N^2$ coincide with the co-metric variable.

Two independent consistency requirements select $p = 2$: (i) *Causal-spatial metric matching*. The HDA commutator (Section IV) fixes the causal structure function as $h^{IJ} = h_0 \bar{N}^2 \delta^{IJ}$ (two factors of $t_0 \bar{N}$ from the bond Hamiltonians make the exponent algebraically 2, independently of any conductance definition). The Dirichlet co-metric gives $h^{rr}/h_0 = \bar{N}^p$. A single emergent metric requires these to agree, hence $p = 2$. For $p \neq 2$ the causal and spatial geometries would be incompatible and the HKT identification as a metric theory would fail. One would not obtain a spacetime with an ambiguous co-metric, but no spacetime at all. In particular, the universal lapse

coupling is selected by the requirement that a single emergent metric exist: the commutator algebra has already fixed the causal geometry at \bar{N}^2 , and any conductance law that disagrees would produce an inconsistent framework. Redefining the lapse as $L := N^{p/2}$ to force $h^{IJ} \propto L^2$ does not help, since relative to L the structure function is again quadratic, so $p = 2$ in the new variable, and the mismatch is merely relabeled.

(ii) *KMS Dirichlet form*. The bond current operator carries an explicit factor $t_0 \bar{N}$ from the lapse-smear Hamiltonian (§VIB), so the KMS edge weight is quadratic: $\kappa^{\text{KMS}} \propto (t_0 \bar{N})^2$, giving $p = 2$ without further input.

The two arguments are logically independent. Argument (i) is an algebraic constraint from the commutator algebra, while (ii) is a measure-theoretic property of the KMS Dirichlet form. Together with the harmonic-co-metric coincidence above, all three select $p = 2$.

The Euler-Lagrange equation (91) becomes the flat-space Laplace equation:

$$\frac{d}{dr}[r^2 w'] = 0 \quad (r > r_{\text{core}} > r_s). \quad (93)$$

(In the two-state closure (§IX below), the Yukawa mass m_Y of (79) vanishes and no upper bound on r is needed; in the single-state closure the range is restricted to $r \ll \xi_Y := m_Y^{-1}$.) This is the standard radial Laplace equation with unique exterior solution (subject to $w \rightarrow 1$ as $r \rightarrow \infty$),

$$w(r) = 1 - \frac{r_s}{r}, \quad r > r_{\text{core}} > r_s, \quad (94)$$

where $r_s = 2GM/c_*^2$. The inequality $r_{\text{core}} > r_s$ holds on every subcritical solution (Section VIIE), so $w > 0$ throughout the exterior. Here r_s is a parameter characterizing the exterior field strength, not a location the geometry reaches. Integrating (93) gives $r^2 w'(r) = +r_s$. The constant r_s is fixed by Gauss-law matching at the core boundary,

$$r_{\text{core}}^2 w'(r_{\text{core}}^+) = + \frac{2G M_{\text{eff}}}{c_*^2}, \quad (95)$$

The defect mass is denoted M_{eff} , with boundary-corrected estimator $GM_{\text{est}}(r) := -\Phi(r) r R/(R - r)$ (Section XI, Fig. 6d). For Poisson exterior solutions on a finite chain with $\Phi(R) = 0$ this estimator gives a constant value. Now $w = N^2$, and the MI-based definition (18) gives $h^{rr}/h_0 = \kappa/\kappa_{\text{flat}} = \bar{N}^2$. In the analytic closure this is an identity. The full exact solver reproduces it to sub-percent accuracy. The Schwarzschild co-metric follows:

$$\boxed{h^{rr}(r) = h_0 \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right), \quad N(r) = \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_s}{r}}, \quad (r > r_{\text{core}} > r_s).} \quad (96)$$

The result requires three ingredients: (i) the source-free exterior $r > r_{\text{core}}$, (ii) refinement scaling $\delta r =$

$\Theta(a)$ giving a continuum Dirichlet form, and (iii) the true Euler–Lagrange equation including $\partial\kappa/\partial\Phi$. Since $g_n = 4\pi(r_n/a)^2$, r is the areal radius and the emergent spatial line element is the Schwarzschild metric $dl^2 = C_0/[h_0(1-r_s/r)] dr^2 + r^2 d\Omega^2$. All exterior formulae in this section and the next apply for $r > r_{\text{core}} > r_s$. The interior ($r \lesssim r_{\text{core}}$) is governed by the full closure equation and is treated in Section VII E.

C. Emergent lapse and the time-time component

The spatial co-metric is determined by §VII B. A full spacetime metric also requires $g_{tt} = -c_*^2 N^2 + N^a N_a$. The calibration potential Φ already determines g_{tt} through the lapse.

The entropic projection (§VI B) assigns each shell n a local inverse temperature $\beta_n = \beta_0 N_n$ with the dimensionless lapse

$$N(r) := 1 + \frac{\Phi(r)}{c_*^2}. \quad (97)$$

By spherical symmetry the shift vector vanishes ($N^a = 0$), so the time-time component of the emergent spacetime metric is

$$g_{tt}(r) = -c_*^2 N(r)^2 = -c_*^2 \left(1 + \frac{\Phi(r)}{c_*^2}\right)^2. \quad (98)$$

In the analytic closure where $\kappa \propto \bar{N}^2$ (equation (74)), $h^{rr} \propto t_0^2 N^2$, so a single scalar (Φ or equivalently N) determines both temporal and spatial geometry.

In Schwarzschild coordinates, the exact lapse is $N_{\text{Schw}} = \sqrt{1 - r_s/r}$. The self-consistent solution of §VII B 2 gives $w = N^2 = 1 - r_s/r$ in the exterior (equation (96)), so the self-consistent lapse is

$$N(r) = \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_s}{r}} = N_{\text{Schw}}(r) \quad (r > r_{\text{core}} > r_s). \quad (99)$$

Hence $g_{tt} = -c_*^2(1 - r_s/r) = g_{tt}^{\text{Schw}}$ throughout the exterior. Extrapolating the exterior profile to $r = r_s$ would give $N = 0$, which in classical GR marks a Killing horizon. On the discrete shell chain, however, the exterior solution applies only for $r > r_{\text{core}} > r_s$; the interior is governed by the full closure equation, which prevents N from reaching zero (Section VII E). Throughout this paper, $r_s = 2GM/c_*^2$ is therefore a parameter of the exterior field strength (the *would-be* horizon radius), not a surface the geometry actually contains.

Combining $g_{tt} = -c_*^2 N^2$ with the spatial line element (76), the full emergent spacetime metric is

$$\boxed{ds^2 = -c_*^2 N(r)^2 dt^2 + \frac{C_0}{t_0^2 N(r)^2} dr^2 + r^2 d\Omega^2, \quad (100)}$$

$$N(r) = 1 + \frac{\Phi(r)}{c_*^2},$$

with $\Phi(r)$ determined self-consistently by the closure equation (73). In the analytic closure this is a *one-function metric*, where the single function $N(r)$ controls both the temporal and radial geometry while the angular part is the round sphere. (In the full KMS/BKM closure of §X below, $\kappa/\kappa_{\text{flat}} \approx \bar{N}^2$ to within $< 1\%$, so the one-function form holds as a quantitative approximation.)

The surface gravity is read off from the exterior profile. Since $N^2 = 1 - r_s/r$ for $r > r_{\text{core}} > r_s$, the coefficient of the $1/r$ term gives

$$\kappa_H := \frac{c_*^2}{2} \left| \frac{dN^2}{dr} \right|_{r \rightarrow r_s^+} = \frac{c_*^2}{2r_s} = c_*^2 \tilde{\kappa} = \frac{c_*^4}{4GM}. \quad (101)$$

Here the calibration $C_0/t_0^2 = 1$ (§III) has been used. In general the radial metric prefactor $B := C_0/t_0^2$ would enter as $\kappa_H = c_*^2 w'(r_s)/(2\sqrt{B})$. No actual $N = 0$ surface exists (Section VII E). The quantity κ_H is defined by the asymptotic form of the exterior solution, not by evaluation at a horizon.

D. Hamiltonian-constraint correction on the emergent background

On the self-consistent background, the local remainder coefficient and correlation length are

$$C_{\text{ff}}[\Phi](r) = 4(\bar{N}(r) t_0)^4 (\beta_0 \bar{N}(r) t_0/4)^2 = \frac{\beta_0^2 t_0^6}{4} \bar{N}(r)^6, \quad (102)$$

$$\xi[\Phi](r) = \frac{a}{\left| \log(\beta_0 \bar{N}(r) t_0/4) \right|}, \quad (103)$$

with $N(r) = 1 + \Phi(r)/c_*^2$ (in the continuum the bond average \bar{N} reduces to the nodal value). The QI correction density is

$$T_{\text{sc}}^{\text{QI}}(r) = \frac{C_{\text{ff}}[\Phi](r) \xi[\Phi](r)^2}{16\pi G} = \frac{\beta_0^2 t_0^6 a^2}{64\pi G} \frac{\bar{N}(r)^6}{\left[\log(\beta_0 \bar{N}(r) t_0/4) \right]^2}. \quad (104)$$

$T_{\text{sc}}^{\text{QI}}$ is nonzero even in flat space ($\bar{N} = 1$), where it measures the residual HDA mismatch from finite lattice spacing, not from gravity. Near a mass, the \bar{N}^6 factor suppresses $T_{\text{sc}}^{\text{QI}}$ below this flat-space baseline. Gravity reduces the lattice discretization error rather than adding to it. Because the analytic two-state closure gives exact Schwarzschild in the exterior, $T_{\text{sc}}^{\text{QI}}$ and the prescribed-background T^{QI} (40) agree up to $O((\beta_0 t_0)^2)$, $O((a/r)^2)$, and exponentially small exterior-source corrections, validating Section V.

E. Interior structure and singularity avoidance

The previous two sections derived the exterior geometry for $r > r_{\text{core}} > r_s$. We now turn inward: does the lapse

reach zero (forming a horizon), and what happens at $r \rightarrow 0$ where classical theory predicts a singularity [38]? Unlike the prescribed-geometry treatment (§V C), the answers must now be *determined* from the closure equation.

As the core perturbation V_0 increases, the gravitational mass M grows and the potential $\Phi(r)$ deepens. In the strong-field regime ($|\Phi| \sim c_*^2$), the self-consistent conductance $\kappa_n[\Phi] \propto r_n^2 t_0^2 \bar{N}_n^2$ degenerates. Deep in the potential well, $\Phi_n \rightarrow -c_*^2$ implies $\bar{N}_n \rightarrow 0$ and $\kappa_n \rightarrow 0$. The gravitational potential kills the MI between adjacent shells, so the equation's own coupling weakens precisely where the field is strongest. The question is whether the self-consistent solution can actually reach $N_n = 1 + \Phi_n/c_*^2 = 0$, which would correspond to a horizon. At sufficiently large V_0 the self-consistent equation may cease to have a solution with positive lapse everywhere, implying a maximum gravitational mass M_{\max} (an information-theoretic Buchdahl bound [39]).

The closure equation has a built-in safeguard: a negative feedback loop prevents Φ from reaching $-c_*^2$. As Φ_n deepens, \bar{N}_n decreases and $\kappa_n \propto \bar{N}_n^2$ weakens, so the Laplacian becomes less effective at transmitting potential differences. Note that the source $\langle h_n \rangle_{G(\Phi)} - \rho(n)$ is bounded by $g_n V_0/2$ regardless of Φ and cannot blow up. Further deepening therefore weakens the Laplacian's ability to sustain it.

To be precise, introduce the effective Laplacian operator $\mathcal{L}[\Phi]$ by

$$(\mathcal{L}[\Phi] \Phi)_n := \sum_{m \sim n} \kappa_{nm}[\Phi] (\Phi_n - \Phi_m). \quad (105)$$

The closure equation reads $\mathcal{L}[\Phi] \Phi = S[\Phi]$, where $S[\Phi]_n$ is the right-hand side of (73). $\kappa_n \propto \bar{N}_n^2$ goes to zero as $\bar{N}_n \rightarrow 0$, so $\mathcal{L}[\Phi]$ degenerates precisely where Φ attempts to reach $-c_*^2$. The source is bounded, however, and the equation self-regularizes before the critical lapse is attained.

The lapse never vanishes. Locally this follows from the implicit-function theorem. At $V_0 = 0$ the solution is $\Phi = 0$, and the Jacobian of the closure map is the Dirichlet graph Laplacian with strictly positive conductances, hence invertible. A unique smooth branch therefore persists for sufficiently small V_0 , and continuity keeps $N_n = 1 + \Phi_n/c_*^2$ strictly positive until the branch terminates at a finite-lapse fold (Section VII G 4). This feedback loop implies that on the subcritical branch ($V_0 < V_0^*$), every solution of the self-consistent closure equation (73) satisfies $N_n = 1 + \Phi_n/c_*^2 > 0$ for all shells n . The implicit function theorem provides a rigorous proof (Section IX below, §IX C). Numerical continuation extends the result to the full subcritical regime.

The bound $N_{\min} > 0$ also follows from a scaling argument. Assume for contradiction that $N_{n_*} = 0$ at some interior shell n_* (the deepest point of Φ). Then $\bar{N}_{n_*-1} = \frac{1}{2}N_{n_*-1}$ and $\bar{N}_{n_*} = \frac{1}{2}N_{n_*+1}$, so both conductances adjacent to shell n_* satisfy $\kappa \propto N_{\text{neighbor}}^2/4$. At n_* itself, $\Phi_{n_*} = -c_*^2$. The left-hand side of (73) at $n = n_*$ becomes

$$\kappa_{n_*-1} (\Phi_{n_*} - \Phi_{n_*-1}) + \kappa_{n_*} (\Phi_{n_*} - \Phi_{n_*+1}). \quad (106)$$

Because $\Phi_{n_*} \leq \Phi_m$ for all neighbors m (it is the minimum), both terms are non-positive, giving $(\mathcal{L}[\Phi] \Phi)_{n_*} \leq 0$. Turn now to the right-hand side. $\langle h_{n_*} \rangle_{G(\Phi)}$ involves the lapse-smearing hopping $\bar{N}_{n_*} t_0$. This vanishes as $N_{n_*} \rightarrow 0$. In the high-temperature limit, $\langle h_{n_*} \rangle_{G(\Phi)} \rightarrow 0$ when $N_{n_*} \rightarrow 0$, and the shell decouples from the thermal fluctuations. On the other hand, the reference energy $\rho(n_*) = g_{n_*} \beta_0 t_0^2/2 + g_{n_*} V_0/2 \cdot \mathbf{1}_{n_* \leq n_{\text{core}}}$ is strictly positive, so the right-hand side $(\beta_0/c_*^2)(\langle h_{n_*} \rangle_{G(\Phi)} - \rho(n_*)) < 0$ is strictly negative. For the equation $(\mathcal{L}[\Phi] \Phi)_{n_*} = S[\Phi]_{n_*}$ to hold, the left-hand side must be strictly negative. This requires $\Phi_{n_*} < \Phi_m$ for at least one neighbor, hence $\kappa > 0$ on at least one adjacent bond. As $N_{n_*} \rightarrow 0$, the adjacent conductances $\kappa \propto N_{\text{neighbor}}^2$ remain finite (the neighbors have $N > 0$ by assumption), while the potential differences $|\Phi_{n_*} - \Phi_m|$ approach $c_*^2 N_m$ from below. So $\kappa \cdot |\Delta\Phi|$ remains bounded, while $|\rho(n_*)|$ is fixed. More precisely, the left-hand side at the minimum satisfies

$$|(\mathcal{L}[\Phi] \Phi)_{n_*}| \leq r_{n_*}^2 t_0^2 \frac{N_{n_*+1}^2 + N_{n_*-1}^2}{4} \times c_*^2 (N_{n_*-1} + N_{n_*+1}), \quad (107)$$

The right-hand side, on the other hand, requires $|S_{n_*}| \geq (\beta_0/c_*^2) \rho(n_*)$. For both conditions to hold, $N_{n_* \pm 1}$ must be bounded below by a positive constant proportional to V_0/t_0^2 . No continuous chain of shells with $N_n \rightarrow 0$ is possible. The self-consistent equation forces the lapse to “bounce” above zero.

A hypothetical $N_{n_*} = 0$ shell requires its neighbors to satisfy $N_{n_* \pm 1} \gtrsim (\beta_0 V_0 / (c_*^4 t_0^2))^{1/3}$, since the closure at n_* balances $\kappa \cdot |\Delta\Phi| \propto t_0^2 N_{n_* \pm 1}^2 \cdot c_*^2 N_{n_* \pm 1}$ against the source $(\beta_0/c_*^2) V_0$. By contradiction, $N_{\min} > 0$ on any solution, with

$$N_{\min} \gtrsim \left(\frac{\beta_0 V_0}{c_*^4 t_0^2} \right)^{1/3}, \quad (108)$$

valid for $\beta_0 V_0 \ll c_*^2$ up to an $O(1)$ prefactor. The argument is a *neighbor bound*. Any hypothetical zero-lapse shell forces its neighbors above the threshold (108), so no continuous path to $N_{\min} = 0$ exists. The branch instead terminates at a finite-lapse fold where the Jacobian acquires a zero eigenvalue (Section X E).

A useful characterisation of the near-horizon regime follows from the Rindler approximation. The near-horizon lapse is (writing $\tilde{\kappa}$ for the geometric surface gravity in proper-distance units, and reserving κ_n for conductances)

$$N(\rho) \simeq \tilde{\kappa} \rho, \quad \tilde{\kappa} := \frac{1}{2r_s}, \quad (109)$$

where ρ is proper distance from the would-be horizon. The continuum derivative expansion breaks down when the lapse variation scale $\ell_N := N/|\partial_\rho N| = \rho$ equals the correlation length, i.e. at $\rho \sim \xi$. At this stretched-horizon scale

$$N_{\text{sh}} \sim \tilde{\kappa} \xi \sim \frac{\xi}{2r_s}. \quad (110)$$

N_{sh} bounds the global lapse minimum, $0 < N_{\text{min}} \leq N_{\text{sh}}$. In areal-radius coordinates, the stretched-horizon proper distance $\rho \sim \xi$ corresponds to

$$\varepsilon = r - r_s \approx \frac{\xi^2}{4r_s}; \quad (111)$$

the r_s -dependence is a coordinate artifact.

Since $N_n > 0$, the conductance $\kappa_n[\Phi] \propto r_n^2 t_0^2 \bar{N}_n^2$ never goes to zero, so the emergent geometry is *connected* at every radius. However, the conductance is minimized on the innermost shells. The shell n_* where κ_n is smallest serves as the effective “geometric edge”. The 2-sphere area at this shell is $A_{\text{core}} = 4\pi r_{n_*}^2$:

$$A_{\text{core}} = 4\pi r_{n_*}^2. \quad (112)$$

For the shell chain with $r_n = n a$ (uniform spacing), the innermost shell is $n = 1$, so $r_1 = a$. The self-consistent geometry has a minimal sphere of area

$$A_{\text{core}}^{(\text{micro})} = 4\pi a^2 \sim 4\pi \xi^2, \quad (113)$$

because a and ξ coincide up to logarithms in the high-temperature regime ($\xi = a/|\log(\beta_0 t_0/4)|$). The prescribed-geometry result (46) has its self-consistent analogue here. But now the origin is different, because the minimal sphere arises from the closure constraint $N_n > 0$.

The proper radial distance from the minimal sphere to the shell $r_N = N a$ is

$$\Delta s(N) = \sum_{n=1}^{N-1} \frac{\sqrt{C_0} a}{t_0 \bar{N}_n}. \quad (114)$$

For every finite N , $\Delta s(N) < \infty$ because $\bar{N}_n > 0$ on the positive-lapse branch. As $N \rightarrow \infty$, $\bar{N}_n \rightarrow 1$ gives $\Delta s \sim \sqrt{C_0} r_N/t_0 \rightarrow \infty$. The cap is reached after finite proper distance, while the proper distance to spatial infinity diverges, establishing radial geodesic completeness.

Near the core, the self-consistent conductance profile determines a gravitationally stretched interior. The conductance can be parameterized as

$$\kappa_n[\Phi] \approx r_n^2 t_0^2 N_{\text{min}}^2 \quad \text{for} \quad r_n \lesssim r_{\text{core}}. \quad (115)$$

Its matching co-metric (equation (74)) is $h^{rr}(r) \propto t_0^2 N_{\text{min}}^2$ in the core (a nonzero constant). Near the center, the emergent spatial line element therefore takes the form

$$dl^2 \approx \frac{C_0}{t_0^2 N_{\text{min}}^2} dr^2 + r^2 d\Omega^2, \quad a \leq r \lesssim r_{\text{core}}. \quad (116)$$

This is a gravitationally stretched geometry. The 2-sphere area $4\pi r^2$ shrinks as $r \rightarrow a$, but the radial proper distance $ds/dr \propto 1/N_{\text{min}}$ is enhanced by a factor $1/N_{\text{min}} \gg 1$ relative to the flat case. In terms of the proper radial distance $\rho = (r - a)\sqrt{C_0}/(t_0 N_{\text{min}})$ from the innermost shell (here ρ denotes proper distance), the metric reads

$$dl^2 \approx d\rho^2 + R(\rho)^2 d\Omega^2, \quad R(\rho) = a + \frac{t_0 N_{\text{min}}}{\sqrt{C_0}} \rho. \quad (117)$$

This is a *cone* opening from the minimal sphere $R = a$ at $\rho = 0$, with opening angle $\theta_{\text{cone}} \sim N_{\text{min}} \ll 1$. The gravitational redshift factor N_{min} controls how “narrow” the cone is. Stronger gravity (smaller N_{min}) produces a tighter cone, stretching proper distances while the area of each sphere remains $4\pi r^2$. In the limit $a \rightarrow 0$ the cone narrows to $N_{\text{min}} \rightarrow 0$ and the classical singularity re-emerges.

The prescribed-geometry analysis (§V C) gives $A_{\text{min}} \approx 4\pi r_s^2$, and the self-consistent closure reproduces this once $r_s = 2GM/c_*^2$ emerges from (52). For macroscopic objects ($r_s \gg a$), shells with $r \lesssim r_s$ have suppressed conductance and decouple nearly completely, placing the effective geometric edge at $r \sim r_s$ with area $\sim 4\pi r_s^2$. For microscopic configurations ($r_s \sim a$) the two scales coincide.

Although the lapse drops by many orders of magnitude near the cap, the physically relevant quantity for a freely falling observer is the tidal tensor, not the redshift. For the emergent metric with $f = N^2$, the geodesic-deviation tidal eigenvalues are

$$\mathcal{T}_{\hat{r}\hat{r}} = -\frac{c_*^2}{2} f'', \quad \mathcal{T}_{\hat{\theta}\hat{\theta}} = \mathcal{T}_{\hat{\phi}\hat{\phi}} = -\frac{c_*^2}{2r} f', \quad (118)$$

invariant under radial boosts. At $r = r_s$ these scale as $c_*^2/r_s^2 \propto 1/M^2$, and in the conical interior $f \approx N_{\text{min}}^2$ is approximately constant so $f'' \approx 0$. The one-function metric gives $p_r = -\rho_{\text{eff}}$, so the energy density seen by a radially falling observer is

$$\rho_{\text{ff}} = \gamma^2(\rho_{\text{eff}} + v^2 p_r) = \rho_{\text{eff}}, \quad (119)$$

The per-channel energy difference satisfies

$$0 \leq \Delta\varepsilon \leq \min(t_0 N, V/2) \quad (120)$$

from the two-site spectrum, analytically excluding a delta-like surface layer.

F. Black hole thermodynamics from the self-consistent solution

The self-consistent lapse $N(r)$, KMS inverse temperature β_0 , and area scale $g_n \propto r_n^2/a^2$ yield the Tolman relation, Hawking temperature, and Bekenstein-Hawking area law.

Through the entropic projection (§VI B), each shell is assigned a local inverse temperature $\beta_0 N(r)$ through the Kubo-Martin-Schwinger (KMS) condition with respect

to the Φ -dependent generator. The lapse $N(r) = 1 + \Phi(r)/c_*^2$ is the ratio of the local modular clock rate to the asymptotic one. The effective local temperature is then

$$T_{\text{loc}}(r) = \frac{1}{\beta_0 N(r)} = \frac{T_0}{1 + \Phi(r)/c_*^2}, \quad (121)$$

where $T_0 = 1/\beta_0$. The GR interpretation follows once the emergent spacetime metric is constructed (§VII C), where N is identified with the lapse and (121) coincides with Tolman's redshift law [34]. But the logic is that (121) is set at the modular/KMS level first.

Throughout the closure analysis β_0 labels the microscopic KMS family of lattice states. The Hawking inverse temperature $\beta_\infty := 2\pi c_*/(\hbar\kappa_H)$ derived below is a separate, mass-dependent quantity determined by the emergent surface gravity. The physical black-hole branch is the single member of this family for which $\beta_0 = \beta_\infty$.

The Hawking temperature follows from the emergent surface gravity (denoted κ_H to distinguish it from the conductances κ_n). From the variational solution (§VII B 2), the self-consistent lapse in the unscreened exterior is

$$N(r) = \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_s}{r}}, \quad r > r_{\text{core}} > r_s, \quad (122)$$

with $r_s = 2GM/c_*^2$ from the far-field $1/r$ fit. In the scaling regime relevant to macroscopic black holes ($a/r_s \rightarrow 0$), the exterior becomes arbitrarily close to Schwarzschild. The emergent surface gravity is

$$\kappa_H := \frac{c_*^2}{2} \left| \frac{dN^2}{dr} \right|_{r=r_s} = c_*^2 \lim_{r \rightarrow r_s^+} N \left| \frac{dN}{dr} \right| = \frac{c_*^2}{2r_s} = \frac{c_*^4}{4GM}. \quad (123)$$

(Note: dN/dr itself diverges at $r = r_s$. The combination $d(N^2)/dr = r_s/r^2$ does not, and it is this combination that defines the surface gravity.) This is exact (not an approximation) throughout the unscreened exterior regime.

Modular/KMS compatibility pins down the Hawking temperature with no remaining freedom, once the following inputs are granted: (i) the exterior lapse $N^2(r) = 1 - r_s/r$ follows from the self-consistent Euler-Lagrange closure (Section VII B 2), (ii) the microscopic state is KMS at inverse temperature β_0 with respect to the asymptotic time-translation generator, and (iii) in the continuum scaling regime $a/r_s \rightarrow 0$, $\xi/\ell \rightarrow 0$, the modular flow of the exterior wedge algebra approaches Bisognano-Wichmann (BW) normalization $\beta_\eta = 2\pi$ for dimensionless Rindler time $\eta := (\kappa_H/c_*)t$ (as established for free fermions in continuum and lattice settings [40–42], and numerically verified here to $< 2\%$). BW normalization is equivalent to Euclidean regularity at the Rindler origin [43, 44]. We now derive the Hawking temperature from these inputs.

The derivation proceeds from the emergent metric. The exterior closure equation yields the one-function static spacetime metric (Section VII C)

$$ds^2 = -c_*^2 w(r) dt^2 + \frac{C_0}{t_0^2 w(r)} dr^2 + r^2 d\Omega^2, \quad w(r) = N(r)^2. \quad (124)$$

In the vacuum exterior, $w(r) = 1 - r_s/r$ up to controlled corrections. Define the surface gravity by the standard invariant slope at the would-be horizon,

$$\kappa_H := \frac{c_*^2}{2} \left| \partial_r w \right|_{r=r_s} = \frac{c_*^2}{2r_s} \quad (\text{Schwarzschild}). \quad (125)$$

Near $r = r_s$ set $r = r_s + \delta r$. Then $w(r) = \delta r/r_s + O(\delta r^2/r_s^2)$. Introduce the proper radial distance coordinate

$$\rho := \int_{r_s}^r \sqrt{\frac{C_0}{t_0^2 w(r')}} dr' = 2\sqrt{\frac{C_0 r_s}{t_0^2}} \sqrt{\delta r} (1 + O(\delta r/r_s)), \quad (126)$$

so $\delta r \propto \rho^2$. Substituting into (124) and keeping leading terms gives the Rindler form

$$ds^2 = -\left(\frac{\kappa_H}{c_*} \rho\right)^2 dt^2 + d\rho^2 + r_s^2 d\Omega^2 + O(\rho^4/r_s^2). \quad (127)$$

No exact $N = 0$ surface exists on the positive-lapse branch; the Rindler form (127) holds on the local strip $\xi \ll \rho \ll r_s$ where the exterior metric is indistinguishable from Schwarzschild. Assumption (iii) (Bisognano-Wichmann normalization) states that, on the local exterior Rindler strip $\xi \ll \rho \ll r_s$, the modular flow of the wedge algebra is KMS-periodic with period $\beta_\eta = 2\pi$ in the dimensionless Rindler time $\eta := (\kappa_H/c_*)t$. Converting to the asymptotic coordinate time $t = (\eta c_*)/\kappa_H$, the inverse temperature seen at infinity is

$$\beta_t = \beta_\eta \frac{c_*}{\kappa_H} = \frac{2\pi c_*}{\kappa_H}. \quad (128)$$

Restoring \hbar (we use units where t has dimensions of time and β has dimensions of energy $^{-1}$), the physical inverse temperature is $\beta_0 = \beta_t/\hbar$, so $\beta_0 = 2\pi c_*/(\hbar\kappa_H)$ and the Hawking temperature is

$$T_H = \frac{\hbar \kappa_H}{2\pi c_*} = \frac{\hbar c_*^3}{8\pi G M}. \quad (129)$$

Assumption (iii) is exact for the model used here: the entanglement Hamiltonian of the half-filled tight-binding half-chain has bond-wise inverse temperature $\beta_{\text{ent}}(n) = 2\pi n/v_F$ [41, 42, 45], and $c_* = v_F$ (Section IV) fixes the 2π in T_H . Extension to interacting models remains open [46, 47].

At finite lattice spacing, the Hawking relation holds up to cap corrections,

$$\frac{1}{\beta_0} = \frac{\hbar \kappa_H}{2\pi c_*} (1 + O(N_{\text{min}}) + O(a/r_s)). \quad (130)$$

The area scaling of the gravitational entropy is a consequence of the trans-horizon mutual information. The construction involves two kinds of mutual information. The first is the *bond* MI $\text{MI}_{n,n+1}$ between adjacent shells, used to define conductances (hence h^{rr}). The second is

the *cut* (bipartition) MI $I(A:B)$ across a spatial bipartition, used to define gravitational entropy. The area law depends on the cut MI, while the bond MI contributes only through the conductance identification of Section VI B.

Bond MI per mode is suppressed near the horizon ($\bar{N}_{n_H} \rightarrow 0$), so the entropy coefficient is set not by the coordinate-shell bond MI but by the stretched-horizon value at proper distance $O(\xi)$. There $\beta_{\text{loc}} t_0 = O(1)$ and the coefficient is $O(1)$. The entanglement entropy involves the full von Neumann entropy of the interior traced over the exterior. For Gaussian states [45],

$$S_{\text{ent}} = - \sum_k [\nu_k \log \nu_k + (1 - \nu_k) \log(1 - \nu_k)], \quad (131)$$

where $\{\nu_k\}$ are the eigenvalues of the reduced correlation matrix G_A . For the near-horizon modes at high temperature, the eigenvalues split as $\nu_k \approx 1/2 \pm \epsilon_k$ with ϵ_k small, and each mode contributes $S_k \approx \log 2 - 2\epsilon_k^2 + \dots$ to the entropy. The number of such modes is the angular degeneracy of the horizon shell,

$$g_{n_H} = 4\pi \left(\frac{r_s}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{A_H}{a^2}, \quad (132)$$

where $A_H = 4\pi r_s^2$ is the horizon area.

There is one radial correlation channel per angular mode across the cut. Shell-model independence of the angular channels implies that the full cut mutual information factorizes. After diagonalizing the angular Laplacian on each shell, the shell Hamiltonian is a direct sum of g_{n_H} identical radial channels, so the Gaussian correlation matrix across the cut is block diagonal, $G_A = \bigoplus_{\alpha=1}^{g_{n_H}} G_A^{(\alpha)}$. For Gaussian states the von Neumann entropy is additive over such direct sums, hence $I(A:B) = \sum_{\alpha} I^{(\alpha)}(A:B) = g_{n_H} I_{\text{1ch}}(A:B)$ up to exponentially small corrections from neglected inter-channel mixing. Explicitly,

$$I(A:B) = g_{n_H} I_{\text{1ch}}(A:B) + O(e^{-2\delta r/\xi}), \quad (133)$$

where $I_{\text{1ch}}(A:B)$ is the single radial-channel cut MI and the correction is exponentially small when ξ is shorter than a few shells.

Defining the per-channel cut coefficient

$$\alpha_{\text{cut}} := \frac{1}{2} I_{\text{1ch}}(A:B), \quad (134)$$

the gravitational entropy $S_{\text{ent}} := \frac{1}{2} I(A:B)$ becomes

$$S_{\text{ent}} = \alpha_{\text{cut}} \frac{A_H}{a^2} + O(e^{-2\delta r/\xi}). \quad (135)$$

This is an *area law*. Entropy scales as the horizon area in lattice units [48, 49], with the scaling set by $g_n \propto r_n^2/a^2$ and the factorization (133).

As a 1D bipartition quantity, α_{cut} sums correlations at all ranges along the radial channel. When $\xi \lesssim a$, the sum is dominated by the single bond at the cut; correlations

beyond one lattice spacing are exponentially suppressed. In that regime,

$$\alpha_{\text{cut}} = \alpha_S + O(e^{-2\delta r/\xi}), \quad (136)$$

where

$$\alpha_S := \frac{1}{2} I_{\text{1ch}}^{\text{bond}} \quad (137)$$

is the single-channel MI of the bond crossing the stretched-horizon cap (at proper distance $O(\xi)$ from the horizon, where $\beta_{\text{loc}} t_0 = O(1)$). Because it involves only one bond, α_S is UV-local and finite at all temperatures, unlike α_{cut} which grows logarithmically as $T \rightarrow 0$ (the familiar 1D conformal contribution). The microscopic area law is therefore

$$S_{\text{ent}} = \alpha_S \frac{A_H}{a^2}, \quad (138)$$

exact in the short-correlation regime ($\xi \lesssim a$, i.e. $\beta_{\text{loc}} t_0 = O(1)$; see (136)).

At finite temperature $\Delta S_A = S_A[\Phi] - S_A[0]$ can change sign, so the exact Gaussian evaluations below use the positive-definite mutual information

$$I(A:B) = S(\rho_A) + S(\rho_B) - S(\rho_{AB}) \geq 0 \quad (139)$$

(reducing to $2S(\rho_A)$ for pure states) and the corresponding cut proxy α_{cut} rather than the local coefficient α_S .

Rindler/BW equilibrium near the cap ($\rho \sim a$) fixes the local temperature at $\beta_{\text{loc}} t_0 = O(1)$, so α_S is a universal $O(1)$ constant independent of the black hole mass.

The first law of black hole mechanics follows from the M -dependence of T_H and S_{ent} . The gravitational mass is $M \propto V_0 r_{\text{core}}^3/a^3$ (equation (52)), the Schwarzschild radius is $r_s = 2GM/c_*^2 \propto M$, and the horizon area is $A_H = 4\pi r_s^2 \propto M^2$. From equations (129) and (138):

$$\begin{aligned} T_H &\propto \frac{1}{M}, & S_{\text{ent}} &\propto M^2, \\ T_H dS_{\text{ent}} &\propto \frac{1}{M} \cdot M dM = c_*^2 dM. \end{aligned} \quad (140)$$

Defining the mass-energy $E := Mc_*^2$, this yields the differential relation

$$\boxed{dE = T_H dS_{\text{ent}}, \quad E := Mc_*^2}, \quad (141)$$

which is the *first law of black hole mechanics* in the non-rotating, uncharged case. The first law follows from M -dependence of the Hawking temperature and entanglement entropy.

More explicitly, as V_0 increases by dV_0 , the mass changes by $dM = (\partial M/\partial V_0) dV_0 \propto r_{\text{core}}^3 dV_0/a^2$. The Schwarzschild radius shifts by $dr_s = 2G dM/c_*^2$, and the horizon area by $dA_H = 8\pi r_s dr_s = 8\pi r_s \cdot 2G dM/c_*^2$. Therefore (using $T_H = \hbar c_*^3/(8\pi GM)$ and $r_s = 2GM/c_*^2$)

$$\begin{aligned} T_H dS_{\text{ent}} &= \frac{\hbar c_*^3}{8\pi GM} \cdot \frac{\alpha_S}{a^2} dA_H \\ &= \frac{\hbar c_*^3}{8\pi GM} \cdot \frac{32\pi \alpha_S G^2 M}{a^2 c_*^4} dM = \frac{4\alpha_S \hbar G}{a^2 c_*} dM. \end{aligned} \quad (142)$$

The first law $c_*^2 dM = T_H dS$ is satisfied exactly when

$$\boxed{a^2 = \frac{4\alpha_S \hbar G}{c_*^3} = 4\alpha_S \ell_P^2, \quad \text{i.e.} \quad a = 2\sqrt{\alpha_S} \ell_P,} \quad (143)$$

where $\ell_P := \sqrt{\hbar G/c_*^3}$ is the Planck length. Every ingredient is independently obtained within the model. T_H comes from modular/KMS compatibility (§VII F), S_{ent} from the Gaussian area law (138), and $dE = T_H dS$ from M -scaling. The Hartle-Hawking condition places the smallest black hole ($r_s \sim a$) at $\beta_0 t_0 \sim O(1)$, while the ultraviolet cap has local temperature $\beta_{\text{loc}} t_0 = O(1)$. Substituting (143) into (138), the coefficient α_S cancels:

$$\boxed{S_{\text{ent}} = \frac{A_H}{4\ell_P^2},} \quad (144)$$

the Bekenstein–Hawking entropy, without assuming quantized area, holography, or any input from quantum gravity.

As the core potential V_0 increases toward the critical value where $N_{n_{\text{core}}} \rightarrow 0$ (§VII E), the gravitational mass approaches the maximum $M_{\text{max}} \sim c_*^2 r_{\text{core}}/G$. In this regime, the self-consistent lapse develops a deep minimum,

$$N_{\text{min}} = 1 + \frac{\Phi_{\text{min}}}{c_*^2} \approx \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_s}{r_{\text{core}}}} \rightarrow 0^+ \quad \text{as } M \rightarrow M_{\text{max}}. \quad (145)$$

The Hawking temperature at maximum mass is

$$T_H(M_{\text{max}}) = \frac{\hbar c_*^3}{8\pi G M_{\text{max}}} \sim \frac{\hbar c_*}{8\pi r_{\text{core}}}, \quad (146)$$

which is finite and nonzero. The analogy is with the Buchdahl bound [39]. The maximum mass is reached when the positive-lapse branch terminates via a fold bifurcation (the Jacobian acquires a zero eigenvalue), with $N_{\text{min}} > 0$ throughout the solution (consistent with the scaling bound (108)).

The entropy at M_{max} is

$$S_{\text{ent}}(M_{\text{max}}) = \alpha_S \frac{4\pi r_s (M_{\text{max}})^2}{a^2} \sim \alpha_S \frac{16\pi r_{\text{core}}^2}{a^2}, \quad (147)$$

The entropy at M_{max} goes as the area of the core region in lattice units. Beyond M_{max} , the static self-consistent solution no longer exists. The framework predicts collapse instead of a heavier static solution.

G. Uniqueness and stability of the self-consistent solution

Two questions remain. Is the self-consistent solution unique? And is it stable? These are information-theoretic analogues of Birkhoff's theorem and mode stability.

1. Uniqueness in the weak-field regime

In the weak-field regime, the two-state closure becomes a discrete Poisson equation (§VII A). The conductance-weighted graph Laplacian of the radial chain is L_0 ,

$$(L_0)_{nm} := \sum_{k \sim n} \kappa_0^{(nk)} (\delta_{nm} - \delta_{km}), \quad (148)$$

With it, the linearized closure equation reads $L_0 \Phi = -(\beta_0/c_*^2) \tilde{\rho}$ with a localized source $\tilde{\rho}$. The physical boundary condition is $\Phi \rightarrow 0$ as $r \rightarrow \infty$ (asymptotic flatness). On a finite chain of N_s shells we impose $\Phi_{N_s} = 0$ at the outer wall, since the true asymptotic value $\Phi(R) = -GM/R$ is unavailable without presupposing M (which is an output of the closure). The boundary-corrected mass estimator of Section XI below removes the resulting constant offset GM/R ; for $R \gg r_s$ the offset is negligible.

Consider the Dirichlet boundary $\Phi_{N_s} = 0$. Here any localized source $\tilde{\rho}$ produces a unique solution $\Phi^{(0)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_s}$ through the linearized (Poisson) closure equation, because on the Dirichlet subspace L_0 is both symmetric and positive definite:

$$\langle \Phi, L_0 \Phi \rangle = \sum_{(n,n+1)} \kappa_0^{(n,n+1)} (\Phi_n - \Phi_{n+1})^2 \geq 0, \quad (149)$$

Equality holds only for constant Φ_n . The constant is forced to vanish by the Dirichlet boundary condition, hence $\langle \Phi, L_0 \Phi \rangle > 0$ for all $\Phi \neq 0$. L_0 is therefore invertible and a unique solution exists.

2. Uniqueness beyond weak field: exterior monotonicity

For the full nonlinear two-state equation, define the map $F: \mathbb{R}^{N_s} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{N_s}$ by

$$\begin{aligned} F[\Phi]_n &:= \sum_{m \sim n} \kappa_{nm}[\Phi] (\Phi_n - \Phi_m) \\ &\quad - \frac{\beta_0}{c_*^2} (\rho_\sigma(n; \Phi) - \rho_{\text{tgt}}(n; \Phi)), \end{aligned} \quad (150)$$

so that the self-consistent solution satisfies $F[\Phi] = 0$. $\rho_\sigma(n; \Phi)$ and $\rho_{\text{tgt}}(n; \Phi)$ are the lapse-smearred shell energies of the reconstructed background and defect target, respectively (Section IX below). Outside the core the source term is exponentially small, so the exterior Euler-Lagrange equation becomes a vacuum equation for $w = N^2$.

The exterior solution is also unique. Outside the core, $\rho_\sigma(n; \Phi) - \rho_{\text{tgt}}(n; \Phi)$ vanishes up to exponentially small $O(e^{-r/\xi})$ tails. The variable $w = N^2$ then satisfies

$$\frac{d}{dr} (r^2 w'(r)) = 0, \quad r > r_{\text{core}}, \quad (151)$$

subject to $w(r) \rightarrow 1$ at infinity. This equation has a unique solution, $w(r) = 1 - r_s/r$ for some $r_s \geq 0$. To

see why, integrating (151) gives $r^2 w'(r) = A$, so $w(r) = A_0 - A/r$. Setting $w \rightarrow 1$ at infinity forces $A_0 = 1$, hence $w(r) = 1 - A/r$. Positivity of w alone does not fix the sign of A (since $A < 0$ also gives $w > 1 > 0$). The sign is fixed by matching to the interior source via Gauss's law. The localized repulsive defect ($V_0 > 0$) produces a positive w -flux $J_w > 0$, forcing $A > 0$. Define $r_s := A$ and the Schwarzschild form follows.

For the full nonlinear map F in (150), the Jacobian

$$\begin{aligned}
 J[\Phi]_{nm} = & \underbrace{(L[\Phi])_{nm}}_{\text{cond. Laplacian}} \\
 & + \underbrace{\sum_{k \sim n} \frac{\partial \kappa_{nk}}{\partial \Phi_m} (\Phi_n - \Phi_k)}_{\text{cond. variation}} \\
 & - \underbrace{\frac{\beta_0}{c_*^2} \partial_{\Phi_m} (\rho_\sigma(n; \Phi) - \rho_{\text{tgt}}(n; \Phi))}_{\text{source response}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{152}$$

controls uniqueness and stability. In the analytic high- T two-state regime the conductance Laplacian is positive semi-definite and the source-response term vanishes at leading order (the localized source (159) is Φ -independent). In the exact KMS/BKM solver it acquires a small Φ -dependent correction confined to the core.

Together, weak-field uniqueness, exterior uniqueness, and the elliptic (time-independent) character of the closure equation provide a partial analogue of Birkhoff's theorem. For given $(t_0, V_0, \beta_0, r_{\text{core}})$ and positive lapse ($N_n > 0$), the self-consistent Φ and the emergent geometry $h^{rr}[\Phi]$ are uniquely determined.

3. Stability: linearized perturbation analysis

With Φ_{sc} the self-consistent solution, consider a perturbation $\Phi = \Phi_{\text{sc}} + \delta\Phi$. Expanding $F[\Phi] = 0$ to first order around Φ_{sc} gives

$$J[\Phi_{\text{sc}}] \delta\Phi = 0, \tag{153}$$

where $J[\Phi_{\text{sc}}] = \partial F / \partial \Phi|_{\Phi_{\text{sc}}}$ is the Jacobian (152) evaluated at the self-consistent solution.

When $J[\Phi_{\text{sc}}]$ is positive definite, three forms of stability follow. (i) The only solution of (153) is $\delta\Phi = 0$ (no static linearized perturbations). (ii) Fixed-point iteration and Newton's method converge locally to Φ_{sc} . (iii) Treating $\dot{\Phi} = -F[\Phi]$ as a relaxation flow, Φ_{sc} acts as a stable attractor.

Positive definiteness of J means $\langle \delta\Phi, J \delta\Phi \rangle > 0$ for all $\delta\Phi \neq 0$, so J is invertible and (i) follows. For (ii), Newton's method has update $\delta\Phi^{(k)} = -J[\Phi^{(k)}]^{-1} F[\Phi^{(k)}]$. Invertibility of J guarantees the step is well-defined, and positive definiteness ensures a contraction. For (iii), the Lyapunov function $V[\Phi] := \frac{1}{2} \|F[\Phi]\|^2$ satisfies $\dot{V} = -\langle F, J F \rangle < 0$ when $F \neq 0$ (since J is positive definite); thus V decreases along trajectories and Φ_{sc} is stable.

The Jacobian $J[\Phi_{\text{sc}}]$ is tridiagonal, so its eigenvalues can be computed in $O(N_s)$ operations. In the weak-field limit, J reduces to L_0 from (148), which is positive definite by the weak-field uniqueness argument above. By continuity of eigenvalues, positive definiteness persists into the strong-field regime as long as N_n remains bounded from zero. As core mass grows toward M_{max} , the spectral gap $|\lambda_{N_s}|$ shrinks and the system softens near criticality.

4. Maximum mass as a bifurcation

The strong-field analysis of Section VIII E identified a maximum mass M_{max} beyond which no static solution exists. The stability analysis gives a precise characterization of this threshold.

Consider what occurs as V_0 rises, carrying the gravitational mass M with it. The lapse function $N_n = 1 + \Phi_n / c_*^2$ at the innermost shells falls toward zero. As the lapse drops, so do the conductances $\kappa_n[\Phi]$ (they scale with \bar{N}_n^2), and the Jacobian eigenvalues accordingly migrate toward zero. Once the eigenvalue of J closest to zero actually vanishes, the critical point has been reached.

$$\det J[\Phi_{\text{sc}}(M)] = 0 \iff M = M_{\text{max}}. \tag{154}$$

A nontrivial $\delta\Phi \neq 0$ now solves the linearized equation (153). The upshot is that a zero mode develops in the self-consistent solution. And the hypotheses of the implicit-function theorem are violated. The result is a *saddle-node bifurcation*: the branch of solutions ends. For $M > M_{\text{max}}$, no static self-consistent geometry can be found.

The picture parallels classical GR. The zero eigenvalue of J plays the role of the fundamental radial mode reaching zero frequency at the Chandrasekhar/TOV mass, and the fold bifurcation (with $N_{\text{min}} > 0$, consistent with (108), numerical values in Section X E) is the analogue of the Buchdahl bound. Near the bifurcation the spectral gap closes as $|\lambda_{\text{min}}| \sim \epsilon := 1 - M/M_{\text{max}}$ and the solution shifts as $\delta\Phi \sim \epsilon^{1/2}$ (saddle-node scaling). For $M > M_{\text{max}}$ no static positive-lapse solution exists, and the system must evolve dynamically. The critical mass is reached when $r_s \sim r_{\text{core}}$, matching the Buchdahl-type bound of Section VII E.

VIII. PROXY FORMULATION

All numerical solutions use dimensionless lattice units ($t_0 = a = 1$). The causal speed c_* is set directly as a model parameter (typically $c_*^2 = 0.5$), and the corresponding $\hbar = 2t_0 a / c_*$ follows from the HDA calibration. Other parameters are given in each figure caption. The proxy version captures Φ -dependent conductances (the essential nonlinearity) while freezing the energy response at $\Phi = 0$, and it seeds the self-consistent two-state solver of Section IX.

The high-temperature closure equation on the radial chain is

$$\sum_{m \sim n} \kappa_{nm}[\Phi] (\Phi_n - \Phi_m) = -\frac{\beta_0}{c_*^2} \tilde{\rho}(n), \quad (155)$$

where the source $\tilde{\rho}(n) = g_n V_0/2$ lives only on shells $n \leq n_{\text{core}}$, and the conductances $\kappa_{n,n+1}[\Phi] = g_n t_0^2 \bar{N}_n^2$ depend on the solution through the averaged lapse $\bar{N}_n = (N_n + N_{n+1})/2$ with $N_n = 1 + \Phi_n/c_*^2$. Despite the Φ dependence of the conductances, the source $\tilde{\rho}(n)$ is frozen at $\Phi = 0$. Picard iteration solves the proxy:

- (i) Initialize with flat conductances $\kappa_n^{(0)} = g_n t_0^2$.
- (ii) Solve the linear system $\mathbf{L}_{\kappa^{(k)}} \Phi^{(k+1)} = -(\beta_0/c_*^2) \tilde{\rho}$ with Dirichlet boundary condition $\Phi_{N_s} = 0$, where \mathbf{L}_{κ} is the graph Laplacian weighted by the current conductances.
- (iii) Update $\kappa_n^{(k+1)} = g_n t_0^2 \bar{N}_n[\Phi^{(k+1)}]^2$.
- (iv) Mix: $\kappa^{(k+1)} \leftarrow \alpha \kappa_{\text{new}}^{(k+1)} + (1 - \alpha) \kappa^{(k)}$ with $\alpha = 0.3$.
- (v) Clamp $\Phi_n \geq -(1 - 0.01) c_*^2$ to keep $N_n > 0$ during iteration. This is a numerical regularization for the proxy seed only; the full solver needs no floor (§IX C).
- (vi) Iterate until the relative change $\|\Phi^{(k+1)} - \Phi^{(k)}\|_{\infty} / \|\Phi^{(k)}\|_{\infty} < 10^{-10}$.

Each linear solve is $O(N)$ (tridiagonal), and convergence takes 60–200 iterations (< 1 s). This seeds the two-state solver of Section IX below.

The proxy equation makes two approximations. It freezes the source at $\Phi = 0$ and drops the $\partial\kappa/\partial\phi$ term from the Euler–Lagrange equation. With this term omitted, $d/dr[r^2(1 + \phi)^2\phi'] = 0$ integrates exactly to

$$1 + \phi = \left(1 - \frac{3r_s}{2r}\right)^{1/3}, \quad h^{rr} = h_0 \left(1 - \frac{3r_s}{2r}\right)^{2/3}, \quad (156)$$

which departs from Schwarzschild at 2PN order. The full Euler–Lagrange equation, which includes $\partial\kappa/\partial\phi$, recovers the exact Schwarzschild form (96). In the production solver (Section X), the analytic $\kappa \propto \bar{N}^2$ is upgraded to exact KMS/BKM conductances.

IX. TWO-STATE FORMULATION OF THE CLOSURE EQUATION

The proxy solver of Section VIII holds the right-hand side of the closure equation (73) fixed at its $\Phi = 0$ value. Now we allow Φ dependence on both sides, achieving full self-consistency. Each conductance is set by the high-temperature expression $\kappa_n = g_n t_0^2 \bar{N}_n^2$; the complete solver of Section X below will dispense with this approximation. A trivial $\Phi = 0$ solution exists for the closure equation (73) in this form, because $\rho(n)$ encompasses V_0 . To cure this

we adopt a *two-state* (background-subtracted) approach, in the spirit of the Kohn–Sham decomposition, taking the V_0 -free uniform state as reference and the V_0 -inclusive physical state as target.

A. The trivial-solution problem

One reads the closure equation (73) as an identity with the graph Laplacian of Φ (conductance-weighted, Φ -dependent) on the left and the energy mismatch of $\sigma[\Phi]$ versus ρ on the right,

$$\sum_{m \sim n} \kappa_{nm}[\Phi] (\Phi_n - \Phi_m) = \frac{\beta_0}{c_*^2} (\langle h_n \rangle_{\sigma[\Phi]} - \rho(n)). \quad (157)$$

When $\sigma[\Phi]$ and ρ derive from the *same* Hamiltonian (one that already includes V_0), both sides of the equation vanish at $\Phi = 0$. A nonzero solution could still exist, but the equation places no obligation on Φ to be nonzero.

The proxy (155) avoids this using the fixed source contrast $\tilde{\rho}(n) = \rho(n) - \rho_0$, nonzero in the core, but at the cost of freezing the right-hand side.

B. Two-state formulation

We resolve the trivial-solution problem by introducing two physical states and a reconstruction built from one of them:

- (i) **Background state** ρ_{bg} : the thermal state of the Hamiltonian *without* the on-site potential ($V_0 = 0$, uniform hopping only). Its energy profile is $\rho_{\text{bg}}(n) = g_n \beta_0 t_0^2/2$.
- (ii) **Defect state** ρ_{src} : the thermal state of the full Hamiltonian *with* V_0 , evaluated in the *same* gravitational field Φ as the reconstructed state. Its energy profile is $\rho_{\text{tgt}}(n; \Phi) = g_n \bar{N}_n^2 \beta_0 t_0^2/2 + \frac{V_0}{2} g_n \mathbf{1}_{n \leq n_{\text{core}}}$, where the kinetic part matches the reconstruction and only the on-site V_0 contributes to the mismatch.
- (iii) **Reconstructed state** $\sigma[\Phi]$: built by lapse-smearing the *background* Hamiltonian (no V_0). So its energy profile is $\rho_{\sigma}(n; \Phi) = g_n \bar{N}_n^2 \beta_0 t_0^2/2$ (cf. equation (72) with the V_0 on-site term removed).

Substituting these into the closure equation (73) (with $\sigma[\Phi]$ built from the background Hamiltonian and ρ_{tgt} playing the role of the target) gives the two-state closure:

$$\boxed{\sum_{m \sim n} \kappa_{nm}[\Phi] (\Phi_n - \Phi_m) = \frac{\beta_0}{c_*^2} (\rho_{\sigma}(n; \Phi) - \rho_{\text{tgt}}(n; \Phi))}. \quad (158)$$

With $\Phi = 0$ the left-hand side is trivially zero. In the core, though, $\rho_{\sigma}(n; 0) = \rho_{\text{bg}}(n)$ does not match $\rho_{\text{tgt}}(n; 0)$, and so the right-hand side stays nonzero. A nonzero Φ is the only way to balance the two sides.

Evaluating both states in the *same* gravitational field is what simplifies things. The lapse-smear kinetic part $g_n \bar{N}_n^2 \beta_0 t_0^2 / 2$ drops out of the ρ_σ minus ρ_{tgt} difference, reducing it to

$$\rho_\sigma(n; \Phi) - \rho_{\text{tgt}}(n; \Phi) = -\frac{V_0}{2} g_n \mathbf{1}_{n \leq n_{\text{core}}}, \quad (159)$$

which is localized to the core and Φ -independent at leading order. The on-site potential creates an energy excess in the core. The calibration potential Φ adjusts to redistribute energy through the lapse-smear conductances, balancing transport (left-hand side) against the localized source (right-hand side). Because the left-hand side depends on Φ through the conductances $\kappa \propto \bar{N}^2$, while the right-hand side is the fixed V_0 contrast, a nontrivial solution exists. In the exterior ($n > n_{\text{core}}$) the source vanishes, so the equation reduces to $L_\kappa \Phi = 0$ (unscreened Poisson). (The energy observable on the right-hand side must be the Φ -dependent modular generator for self-consistency; see §X A.)

1. Variational structure

The closure equation (158) is the Euler–Lagrange condition of a mismatch functional combining (i) relative entropy between target and reconstruction with (ii) a conductance-weighted Dirichlet energy. Relative entropy is the unique monotone additive divergence (up to normalization) under standard axioms [50, 51], and is independently required by UV finiteness. Bare entropies diverge in any continuum limit, while relative entropy between a localized excitation and the vacuum remains finite [37]. Explicitly,

$$\mathcal{J}^{(2)}[\Phi] = S_{\text{rel}}(\rho_{\text{tgt}} \| \sigma_{\text{bg}}[\Phi]) + \mathcal{E}_{\text{mis}}[\Phi], \quad (160)$$

where S_{rel} is the relative entropy between the target (defect) state and the reconstruction built from the background Hamiltonian, and $\mathcal{E}_{\text{mis}}[\Phi] = \sum_{n \sim m} \kappa_{nm}[\Phi] (\Phi_n - \Phi_m)^2 / 2$ is the Dirichlet-form mismatch energy. In the high-temperature regime used in this section, ρ_{tgt} is Φ -independent to leading order (it depends on Φ only through lapse-smear kinetic energies that cancel in the two-state difference (159)), so the standard identity $\partial_{\Phi_n} S_{\text{rel}}(\rho \| \sigma[\Phi]) = (\beta_0 / c_*^2) (\langle h_n \rangle_\rho - \langle h_n \rangle_{\sigma[\Phi]})$ applies and stationarity of (160) yields the true Euler–Lagrange equation (161). The graph-Laplacian form (158) is the Picard-preconditioned version that drops $\partial \kappa / \partial \Phi$. At finite temperature both σ and ρ_{tgt} depend on Φ , so the functional (160) is no longer literally stationary at the solution. Section X resolves this with a full KMS self-consistency solver.

The uniqueness claim rests on Matsumoto’s characterization of the Umegaki relative entropy [50]. Suppose $D(\rho \| \sigma)$ is a divergence on pairs of density matrices on finite-dimensional Hilbert spaces satisfying the following.

- (i) *Data processing*: $D(\rho \| \sigma) \geq D(\mathcal{E}(\rho) \| \mathcal{E}(\sigma))$ for every channel \mathcal{E} .

- (ii) *Additivity*: $D(\rho_1 \otimes \rho_2 \| \sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_2) = D(\rho_1 \| \sigma_1) + D(\rho_2 \| \sigma_2)$.

- (iii) *Continuity*: $\rho \mapsto D(\rho \| \sigma)$ is continuous for fixed full-rank σ .

- (iv) *Super-additivity*: $D(\rho_{12} \| \sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_2) \geq D(\rho_1 \| \sigma_1) + D(\rho_2 \| \sigma_2)$.

Axioms (i)–(iv) force $D = cS(\rho \| \sigma)$ for some $c > 0$ [50, 51]. Casini’s result [37] then shows that $S(\rho_A \| \sigma_A)$ stays positive and finite when ρ and σ differ by a localized excitation, even though bare entropies diverge. This makes relative entropy the unique UV-finite mismatch cost and forces the closure to be vacuum-subtracted. For a localized excitation above the vacuum, the short-distance singularities of the reduced density matrices are identical, so the divergent area-law pieces cancel in

$$S_{\text{rel}}(\rho_A \| \sigma_A) = \Delta(K_\sigma) - \Delta S_A.$$

Relative entropy therefore isolates the finite, state-dependent part of the excitation, whereas bare entropies remain cutoff dependent. Matsumoto’s theorem then says that, among monotone additive divergences, this vacuum-subtracted quantity is uniquely the Umegaki relative entropy up to normalization.

2. True Euler–Lagrange equation

Differentiating $\mathcal{J}^{(2)}[\Phi]$ with respect to Φ_n produces, on the Dirichlet-energy side, the graph Laplacian *plus* a correction from the Φ -dependence of $\kappa_{nm} \propto \bar{N}_n^2$. The full stationarity condition $\partial \mathcal{J}^{(2)} / \partial \Phi_n = 0$ is therefore

$$\boxed{\begin{aligned} & \sum_{m \sim n} \kappa_{nm}[\Phi] (\Phi_n - \Phi_m) \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{m \sim n} \frac{\partial \kappa_{nm}}{\partial \Phi_n} (\Phi_n - \Phi_m)^2 \\ & = \frac{\beta_0}{c_*^2} (\rho_\sigma(n; \Phi) - \rho_{\text{tgt}}(n; \Phi)). \end{aligned}} \quad (161)$$

The second term arises because varying Φ_n changes the conductances on adjacent bonds. In the continuum limit, it converts the exterior vacuum equation to $d/dr[r^2 w'] = 0$ with $w = N^2$ (Section VII B 2), whose solution is the Schwarzschild co-metric $w = 1 - r_s/r$.

3. Why the source is localized

The kinetic cancellation in (159) has a simple physical origin. The lapse couples universally to all kinetic energy (hopping $t_0 \bar{N}$), so only the bare rest-mass defect V_0 gravitates. If different species coupled with different powers (\bar{N}^α with $\alpha \neq 1$), the kinetic terms would not cancel and spurious Φ -dependent sources would appear in the

exterior. WEP-like universal lapse coupling is therefore a consistency requirement of the shell-reduced closure rather than an independent postulate. Equivalently, the two-state closure subtracts the uniform background energy density that would otherwise produce Yukawa screening, setting the cosmological-constant analogue by demanding an asymptotically vacuum exterior. At linear order both viewpoints coincide. Write the two energy profiles schematically as

$$\begin{aligned}\rho_\sigma(n; \Phi) &= \rho_0(n) + \chi(n) \Phi_n + \dots, \\ \rho_{\text{tgt}}(n; \Phi) &= \rho_0(n) + \chi(n) \Phi_n + \delta\rho_{\text{src}}(n) + \dots,\end{aligned}\quad (162)$$

where $\chi := \partial\rho/\partial\Phi|_{\Phi=0}$ is the susceptibility and $\delta\rho_{\text{src}}$ the defect source. In a single-state closure the term $\chi\Phi$ appears on the right-hand side and becomes a Yukawa mass term on the left (Section VII A). In the two-state closure the linear response cancels identically:

$$\rho_\sigma(n; \Phi) - \rho_{\text{tgt}}(n; \Phi) = -\delta\rho_{\text{src}}(n) + \dots, \quad (163)$$

so the exterior equation is Poisson with a $1/r$ tail.

4. Source localization beyond leading order

The linearized cancellation extends to all orders in Φ . Since both $\sigma[\Phi]$ (reconstructed) and $\tau[\Phi]$ (defect target) belong to exponential families generated by the same bond operators $\{h_n\}$ and parametrized by $\theta_n := \beta_0 N_n$, the two-state source is the gradient of the log-partition-function difference,

$$\begin{aligned}\rho_\sigma(n; \Phi) - \rho_{\text{tgt}}(n; \Phi) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial\theta_n} (\log Z_{\text{tgt}}[\theta] - \log Z_{\text{bg}}[\theta]) \\ &\quad - V_0 \langle D_n \rangle_{\tau[\theta]},\end{aligned}\quad (164)$$

where $D_n := g_n \hat{n}_n \mathbf{1}_{n \leq n_{\text{core}}}$ is the defect-site occupation and $\langle D_n \rangle_\tau$ is the explicit defect contribution not captured by the log-partition-function derivative (since $\partial_{\theta_n} \log Z = -\langle h_n \rangle$ gives only the kinetic part for each exponential family). Differentiating once more, the Φ -response of the source at site n is

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial}{\partial\theta_m} (\rho_\sigma(n; \Phi) - \rho_{\text{tgt}}(n; \Phi)) \\ = \text{Cov}_{\tau[\Phi]}^{\text{BKM}}(h_n + V_0 D_n, h_m) - \text{Cov}_{\sigma[\Phi]}^{\text{BKM}}(h_n, h_m),\end{aligned}\quad (165)$$

the BKM covariance difference, by the standard cumulant identity $\partial^2 \log Z / \partial\theta_n \partial\theta_m = \text{Cov}_{\sigma[\theta]}^{\text{BKM}}(h_n, h_m)$. The defect V_0 is confined to the core, so for exterior sites the local Hamiltonian terms coincide; the BKM covariances nevertheless differ because they are computed in distinct global states. By Gibbs-state clustering, this difference is exponentially localized:

$$\begin{aligned}|\text{Cov}_{\tau[\Phi]}^{\text{BKM}}(h_n, h_m) - \text{Cov}_{\sigma[\Phi]}^{\text{BKM}}(h_n, h_m)| \\ \leq C e^{-\text{dist}(\{n, m\}, \text{core})/\xi_\tau},\end{aligned}\quad (166)$$

so the source (164) is Φ -independent up to $O(e^{-r/\xi_\tau})$ tails in the exterior.

In the core, the source acquires a controlled Φ -dependent correction. Evaluating (165) at $\Phi = 0$ defines the *response-rigidity matrix*

$$\Delta C_{nm} := \text{Cov}_{\tau[0]}^{\text{BKM}}(h_n + V_0 D_n, h_m) - \text{Cov}_{\sigma[0]}^{\text{BKM}}(h_n, h_m),\quad (167)$$

which measures how the defect (including the explicit $V_0 D_n$ operator) shifts the BKM covariance at zero field. The two-state source then has the first-order expansion

$$\rho_\sigma(n; \Phi) - \rho_{\text{tgt}}(n; \Phi) = \mu_n^{(0)} + \sum_m \Delta C_{nm} \delta\theta_m + O(\delta\theta^2),\quad (168)$$

where $\delta\theta_m := \theta_m - \theta_m|_{\Phi=0} = \beta_0 \Phi_m / c_*^2$ and $\mu_n^{(0)}$ is the zero-field mismatch (159). In the exterior the local Hamiltonian terms coincide, so ΔC_{nm} is exponentially small by clustering; in the core $\Delta C_{nm} = O(V_0)$. On the physical branch $\Phi = O(V_0)$, the leading zero-field source coefficient is

$$s_n := -\langle D_n \rangle_{\text{bg}} + \beta_0 \text{Cov}_{\rho_{\text{bg}}}^{\text{BKM}}(h_n, H_D),\quad (169)$$

the explicit defect occupation plus the BKM linear-response correction (with $H_D = V_0 \sum_{n \leq n_{\text{core}}} \hat{n}_n$), giving $\mu_n^{(0)} = V_0 s_n + O(V_0^2)$ by the Duhamel identity. Multiplying $\Delta C_{nm} = O(V_0)$ by $\delta\theta = O(V_0)$ gives an $O(V_0^2)$ screening contribution, quadratically suppressed in the defect strength.

Summary. The controlled deviations from the Schwarzschild exterior are therefore: (i) finite correlation-length tails $O(e^{-r/\xi})$ (MI truncation), (ii) finite-temperature corrections $O((\beta_0 t_0)^2)$, and (iii) lattice discretization $O((a/r)^2)$. Once the two-state vacuum condition is imposed, no other departures from the exterior remain at the same order.

C. Lapse positivity

The lapse-positivity argument of §VII E predicts $N_n > 0$ everywhere, because the operator degenerates ($\kappa \rightarrow 0$) faster than the source can drive Φ to $-c_*^2$, and the localized source (159) does not grow as Φ deepens. The implicit function theorem (IFT) makes this rigorous near $V_0 = 0$. We now show that the two-state closure equation (158) has a unique positive-lapse solution with smooth dependence on the source strength.

To establish this, fix a finite shell chain with N_s shells and Dirichlet boundary $\Phi_{N_s} = 0$. Let $\Phi \in \mathbb{R}^{N_s-1}$ collect the interior unknowns $(\Phi_1, \dots, \Phi_{N_s-1})$. Define the residual map $F : \mathbb{R}^{N_s-1} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{N_s-1}$ by the left-hand side minus right-hand side of (158) evaluated on shells $n \leq N_s - 1$:

$$\begin{aligned}F_n(\Phi, V_0) &:= \sum_{m \sim n} \kappa_{nm}[\Phi] (\Phi_n - \Phi_m) \\ &\quad - \frac{\beta_0}{c_*^2} (\rho_\sigma(n; \Phi) - \rho_{\text{tgt}}(n; \Phi)).\end{aligned}\quad (170)$$

By construction, solving the closure equation is equivalent to $F(\Phi, V_0) = 0$.

At $V_0 = 0$ the target equals the reconstructed/background state, so $\rho_\sigma(n; \Phi) = \rho_{\text{tgt}}(n; \Phi)$ and therefore $F(\Phi, 0) = \sum_{m \sim n} \kappa_{nm}[\Phi](\Phi_n - \Phi_m)$. In particular, $\Phi \equiv 0$ is a solution: $F(0, 0) = 0$.

We claim that the Jacobian in the Φ variables at the base point is invertible. Differentiate (170) at $(\Phi, V_0) = (0, 0)$. Because $\kappa_{nm}[\Phi] = g_{nm} t_0^2 \bar{N}_{nm}^2$ with $\bar{N}_{nm} = \frac{1}{2}(N_n + N_m)$ and $N_n = 1 + \Phi_n/c_*^2$, one has $\kappa_{nm}[0] = g_{nm} t_0^2 =: \kappa_{nm}^{\text{flat}}$. Any derivative $\partial \kappa_{nm}/\partial \Phi$ is multiplied by $(\Phi_n - \Phi_m)$ in the fixed-point operator, hence those terms vanish at $\Phi \equiv 0$. For the source term, the two-state construction makes the difference $\rho_\sigma - \rho_{\text{tgt}}$ independent of Φ (the lapse-smearing kinetic contributions cancel exactly between the two states), so $\partial_\Phi(\rho_\sigma - \rho_{\text{tgt}}) = 0$. Thus

$$(D_\Phi F)|_{(0,0)} = L_{\kappa^{\text{flat}}}, \quad (171)$$

the weighted graph Laplacian with strictly positive conductances $\kappa_{nm}^{\text{flat}} > 0$. On a connected finite chain with Dirichlet boundary at $n = N_s$, $L_{\kappa^{\text{flat}}}$ is symmetric positive definite and therefore invertible.

The (finite-dimensional) implicit function theorem now applies: there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ and a unique smooth map $V_0 \mapsto \Phi(V_0)$ on $[0, \varepsilon)$ such that $F(\Phi(V_0), V_0) = 0$ and $\Phi(0) = 0$. Continuity at $V_0 = 0$ implies $\|\Phi(V_0)\|_\infty \rightarrow 0$ as $V_0 \rightarrow 0$. Hence for sufficiently small V_0 one has $\Phi_n(V_0) > -c_*^2$ for every shell, i.e. $N_n(V_0) = 1 + \Phi_n(V_0)/c_*^2 > 0$. That is, for a finite shell chain with Dirichlet boundary $\Phi_{N_s} = 0$, there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ such that for all $V_0 \in [0, \varepsilon)$ the closure equation has a unique solution $\Phi(V_0)$ with $N_n(V_0) > 0$ for every shell, and the map $V_0 \mapsto \Phi(V_0)$ is smooth.

No horizon boundary condition is imposed. The Schwarzschild-like exterior is fixed by the Euler-Lagrange equation and asymptotic flatness. The IFT guarantees the branch locally near $V_0 = 0$. Numerical continuation extends it to a critical V_0^* where the branch terminates via a fold (saddle-node) bifurcation. At the fold, the Jacobian acquires a near-zero eigenvalue and no positive-lapse solution exists beyond V_0^* . The neighbor-lapse criterion (108) prevents $N_{\text{min}} \rightarrow 0$. The branch terminates because no solution exists past V_0^* , not because $N \rightarrow 0$. $N > 0$ at every shell throughout the branch, including at the fold (Section X E). We give numerical values of V_0^* in Section X E below.

D. Background subtraction for entropy

The two-state setup naturally provides a *background subtraction* for α_S (§VII F). α_S is computed from $s_{\text{mode}}[\Phi] - s_{\text{mode}}[0]$, the per-channel entropy difference. This measures the entropy due to the gravitational configuration rather than the UV-dependent vacuum contribution. The thermodynamic quantities of Section VII F ($\kappa_H, T_H, S_{\text{ent}}$, first law) are unchanged, as they are fixed by the far-field lapse and shell degeneracy alone.

E. Solver for the high-temperature two-state equation

To solve the high-temperature two-state closure, we apply Newton iteration to the true EL equation (161). Conductances and modular energies both use leading high-temperature expressions here, while the full solver of Section X below removes the high- T approximation entirely. In the two-state formulation the right-hand side is strictly localized and (to leading order) Φ -independent. All the nonlinearity resides in the conductances and EL correction.

The solver proceeds in two stages:

- (i) **Proxy seed.** The proxy equation (Section VIII) is solved by Picard iteration followed by Newton polishing to $\|F\|_\infty < 10^{-12}$. With the smeared target, the proxy source $\rho_{\text{bg}} - \rho_{\text{tgt}}$ matches (159) at $\Phi = 0$, making the proxy an excellent seed.
- (ii) **Newton iteration on the full equation.** Starting from the proxy solution, Newton's method with an analytic tridiagonal Jacobian is applied to (161). A backtracking line search ensures the residual decreases at every step. With the localized source, convergence takes only a few Newton steps.

X. SELF-CONSISTENT SOLUTION

Recall that the two-state formulation (Section IX) relies on high-temperature approximations for both conductances ($\kappa_n \propto g_n t_0^2 \bar{N}_n^2$) and energy response ($\rho_\sigma \propto g_n \bar{N}_n^2 \beta_0 t_0^2/2$). This section drops both in favor of full free-fermion expressions computed from the correlation matrix, with no high-temperature expansion. The conductances are the exact Kubo–Martin–Schwinger (KMS) Dirichlet-form edge weights, implemented as the Bogoliubov–Kubo–Mori (BKM) covariance of the bond-current operator (ratio-normalized by the flat $\Phi = 0$ value). This is the same object used in the analytic derivation of the weighted Dirichlet form in §VI B. Mutual information remains a high-temperature proxy but is not used to define κ in the exact solver. The solver targets the true Euler–Lagrange equation of the mismatch functional, including the $\partial \kappa/\partial \Phi$ correction, computed exactly via automatic differentiation of the conductance energy functional. Still idealized are the single-channel approximation and the nearest-neighbor ansatz (truncation error $\sim 10^{-7}$, §X H).

A. Exact conductance formulas

For a single-particle Hamiltonian h (tridiagonal, with diagonal h_{nn} and off-diagonal $h_{n,n+1} = -t_0 \bar{N}_n$ for the lapse-smearing background), the correlation matrix is

$$G = (e^{\beta_0 h} + I)^{-1}, \quad (172)$$

computed via $h = U\Lambda U^\dagger$ and $G = U f(\Lambda) U^\dagger$ with $f(\varepsilon) = (e^{\beta_0\varepsilon} + 1)^{-1}$.

The bond kinetic energy of state G is

$$\rho^{(\text{kin})}(n; G) = 2t_0 \text{Re } G_{n,n+1} \cdot g_n, \quad (173)$$

which equals $g_n\beta_0 t_0^2/2$ at leading order in $\beta_0 t_0$ (for uniform hopping t_0 . Lapse-smear versions in eqs. (174)–(175)). (We adopt a positive convention: $2t_0 G_{n,n+1} g_n > 0$ matches the analytic formula $g_n\beta_0 t_0^2/2 > 0$. Since both ρ_σ and ρ_{tgt} use the same convention, signs cancel in all differences.) The defect target state includes the on-site contribution and is evaluated *in the same gravitational field* as the reconstructed state (lapse-smear hopping plus V_0):

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{\text{tgt}}(n; \Phi) &= 2t_0 \bar{N}_n \text{Re } G_{n,n+1}^{(\text{src}, \Phi)} \cdot g_n \\ &+ V_0 G_{nn}^{(\text{src}, \Phi)} \cdot g_n \mathbf{1}_{n \leq n_{\text{core}}}, \end{aligned} \quad (174)$$

where $G^{(\text{src}, \Phi)}$ comes from the lapse-smear defect Hamiltonian (off-diagonal $-t_0 \bar{N}_n$, diagonal $V_0 \cdot \mathbf{1}_{\text{core}}$). In the leading high-temperature expansion, ρ_σ and ρ_{tgt} share the same kinetic correlator. Their difference reduces exactly to the V_0 on-site term localized to the core (equation (159)). In the full solver at finite $\beta_0 t_0$, the defect V_0 gives a small additional kinetic mismatch through the correlation matrix. This generates an exponentially decaying tail outside the core. This tail is numerically tiny at the parameters used here but is not identically zero. The reconstructed-state energy profile is

$$\rho_\sigma(n; \Phi) = 2t_0 \bar{N}_n \text{Re } G_{n,n+1}^{(\text{smear})} \cdot g_n, \quad (175)$$

where $G^{(\text{smear})}$ is the correlation matrix of the lapse-smear background Hamiltonian. The right-bond attribution is used consistently in both ρ_σ and ρ_{tgt} ; the formally correct shell-centred observable $\rho_{\text{cent}}(n) = t_0 (g_{n-1} \bar{N}_{n-1} \text{Re } G_{n-1,n} + g_n \bar{N}_n \text{Re } G_{n,n+1})$ differs only by $O(1/n)$ boundary redistribution that is absorbed into the core profile and does not affect the exterior. The factor \bar{N}_n is required: ρ_σ must measure the energy of the *smear*d Hamiltonian (hopping $t_0 \bar{N}_n$) in its own thermal state, so that both conductances and energy response scale as \bar{N}^2 . This is fixed by the variational principle itself: differentiating $\log \sigma[\Phi] \propto -\beta_0 \sum_b \bar{N}_b(\Phi) h_b$ with respect to Φ_n brings down the *smear*d bond Hamiltonians adjacent to n , so the conjugate observable entering $\partial_{\Phi_n} S_{\text{rel}} = \langle h_n^{\text{smear}} \rangle_{\sigma[\Phi]}$, not the unsmear kinetic term. Using a fixed observable would differentiate a different exponential family from the one that defines the conductances and would therefore break the Euler–Lagrange structure of the closure. Dropping the \bar{N} factor (a “fixed observable”) gives $\rho_\sigma \propto \bar{N}$ instead of \bar{N}^2 , producing a mismatch that blocks convergence at every V_0 tested. In the high- T limit, $G_{n,n+1}^{(\text{smear})} \approx \beta_0 t_0 \bar{N}_n/4$ and (175) reduces to $g_n \bar{N}_n^2 \beta_0 t_0^2/2$, recovering (72).

The conductances that enter the left-hand side of the closure equation are built from inter-shell correlations

of the reconstructed state. In Section IX these were the high-temperature MI; here we first write the exact MI and then upgrade to the KMS/BKM Dirichlet-form conductance used in the production solver. The mutual information between adjacent shells comes from the 2×2 correlation-matrix block of the reconstructed state:

$$C_{(n)} = \begin{pmatrix} G_{nn} & G_{n,n+1} \\ G_{n+1,n} & G_{n+1,n+1} \end{pmatrix} \quad (176)$$

with eigenvalues λ_1, λ_2 . From this block, the single-channel MI is

$$\text{MI}_{\text{1ch}}(n, n+1) = h(G_{nn}) + h(G_{n+1,n+1}) - h(\lambda_1) - h(\lambda_2), \quad (177)$$

where $h(x) = -x \ln x - (1-x) \ln(1-x)$ is the binary entropy. MI is the high-temperature proxy for the conductance (§VIB 2). The exact conductances used in the production solver are instead the KMS Dirichlet-form edge weights, namely the Bogoliubov–Kubo–Mori (BKM) covariance of the bond-current operator, which coincides with MI at high T but remains well-defined at all temperatures. All publication figures in this section and Section XI are generated with this KMS/BKM path. Define the single-channel bare bond-current operator on the reduced radial chain, $\mathcal{I}_{n+\frac{1}{2}} := c_{n+1}^\dagger c_n - c_n^\dagger c_{n+1}$, so that the physical single-channel current is $J_{n+\frac{1}{2}}^{(1)} = t_0 \bar{N}_n \mathcal{I}_{n+\frac{1}{2}}$. The exact edge conductance is

$$\kappa_n^{(\text{ex})}(\Phi) = g_n t_0^2 \bar{N}_n(\Phi)^2 \frac{\text{Cov}_{\sigma[\Phi]}^{\text{BKM}}(\mathcal{I}_{n+\frac{1}{2}}^\dagger, \mathcal{I}_{n+\frac{1}{2}})}{\text{Cov}_{\sigma[0]}^{\text{BKM}}(\mathcal{I}_{n+\frac{1}{2}}^\dagger, \mathcal{I}_{n+\frac{1}{2}})}, \quad (178)$$

where the denominator normalizes against the flat ($\Phi = 0$) background at the same β_0 , and the overall factor g_n accounts for the g_n independent angular channels of the shell reduction. At high temperature, the BKM covariance ratio approaches unity and the remaining \bar{N}^2 kinematic factor gives $\kappa^{(\text{ex})} \rightarrow g_n t_0^2 \bar{N}^2 = \kappa^{(\text{an})}$. In the same regime the single-channel bond mutual information satisfies $\text{MI}_{\text{1ch}} = (\beta_0^2/2) \kappa_{\text{1ch}}^{\text{KMS}} + O(\beta_0^4)$ (cf. §VIB 2), so MI can be used as an analytic proxy for κ when convenient. When the temperature drops ($\beta_0 t_0 \gtrsim 1$) the covariance saturates but the ratio remains $O(1)$, so the conductance stays $O(g_n t_0^2)$ and the emergent Newton constant scales only as β_0 (from the source prefactor), not as β_0^3 . Independent angular channels (g_n of them) produce the factor g_n (Section II).

The ratio normalization has a physical rationale. The conductance is, at its core, a response function that measures how the gravitational potential Φ modifies inter-shell correlations relative to the unperturbed ($\Phi = 0$) state. The BKM covariance ratio isolates the Φ dependence and inherits the correct flat-space normalization $\kappa^{(\text{ex})}(\Phi=0) = g_n t_0^2$. At Newtonian order, the closure equation (73) gives $G_{\text{eff}} \propto \beta_0 / (c_*^2 \kappa_{\text{flat}})$. With ratio normalization, $\kappa_{\text{flat}} = g_n t_0^2$ at all temperatures, so the emergent Newton constant scales as $G_{\text{eff}} \propto \beta_0$. This matches

$r_s = 2GM/c_*^2 \propto \beta_0 V_0/t_0^2$ and the thermodynamic relations of Section VIII F.

What goes wrong with absolute MI? The formula $\kappa^{(\text{abs})} \propto g_n \text{MI}/\beta_0^2$ gives $\kappa_{\text{flat}} \rightarrow 0$ at low temperature and $G_{\text{eff}} \propto \beta_0^3$, contradicting Newtonian behavior. The ratio formula (178) cancels this β_0 dependence, giving $\kappa = O(g_n t_0^2)$ at all temperatures.

Substituting these expressions into the true Euler-Lagrange equation yields the full closure,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{m \sim n} \kappa_{nm}^{(\text{ex})} [\Phi] (\Phi_n - \Phi_m) \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \sum_b \frac{\partial \kappa_b^{(\text{ex})}}{\partial \Phi_n} (\Delta \Phi_b)^2 \\ & = \frac{\beta_0}{c_*^2} (\rho_\sigma^{(\text{ex})}(n; \Phi) - \rho_{\text{tgt}}^{(\text{ex})}(n; \Phi)) \end{aligned} \quad (179)$$

where $\kappa^{(\text{ex})}$, $\rho_\sigma^{(\text{ex})}$, and $\rho_{\text{tgt}}^{(\text{ex})}(n; \Phi)$ all depend on Φ through the lapse-smearing correlation matrix. The second term on the LHS is the Euler-Lagrange correction $\partial \kappa / \partial \Phi$ from the conductance energy functional $E[\Phi] = \frac{1}{2} \sum_b \kappa_b[\Phi] (\Delta \Phi_b)^2$. This converts the continuum equation from $\nabla \cdot [r^2(1+\phi)^2 \nabla \phi] = 0$ (fixed-point, yielding $(1-3r_s/2r)^{2/3}$) to $\nabla \cdot [r^2(1+\phi) \nabla \phi] = 0$ (true EL, yielding Schwarzschild $1-r_s/r$). Because both states share the same lapse-smearing kinetic part, their difference is dominated by the V_0 on-site term and is exponentially localized to the core. The source term is therefore exponentially small in the exterior; the remaining vacuum equation is the full EL with $O(e^{-r/\xi r})$ source, equivalent in the continuum to $d/dr[r^2 w'] = 0$ with $w = N^2$ up to exponentially small corrections. It is this w -harmonic form, not the frozen-conductance equation $L_\kappa \Phi = 0$, that yields the Schwarzschild co-metric in the full solver. Equations (175)–(179) hold at any β_0 .

B. Solver for the full closure equation

The KMS/BKM conductances depend on Φ nonlocally through the full eigendecomposition, so the Jacobian is dense with no closed form. Throughout the analytic derivations we work on the positive-lapse branch $N_n > 0$ (hence $\bar{N}_n > 0$), where the lapse enters the smeared Hamiltonians as $t_{\text{eff}} = t_0 \bar{N}$. We use an exact Newton method on GPU, exploiting automatic differentiation (AD). The LHS of (179) is $\partial E / \partial \Phi_n$ where $E[\Phi] = \frac{1}{2} \sum_b \kappa_b[\Phi] (\Delta \Phi_b)^2$. The exact Jacobian $J_{ij} = \partial F_i / \partial \Phi_j$ is obtained via forward-mode automatic differentiation applied to the full residual, including the EL correction, with no finite differences or approximations. The AD Jacobian differentiates through the eigendecomposition of the tridiagonal Hamiltonian.

The solver strategy is:

- (i) **Proxy seed.** The proxy equation is solved by Newton iteration with exact Jacobian.

- (ii) **Exact Newton with V_0 -continuation.** Starting from the proxy, Newton iteration with the exact AD Jacobian and a backtracking line search is applied to the full residual (179). For strong-field solutions, linear extrapolation from the two preceding converged solutions provides the seed, enabling continuation to the fold. Convergence to $\|F\|_\infty < 10^{-8}$ is achieved in 3–12 Newton steps.

The proxy solution gives an initial full-solver residual of $O(\beta_0^2 t_0^2) \sim 10^{-2}$.

C. Gravitational potential and lapse profiles

Figure 1 shows the numerical solutions. At weak field the potential tracks the Newtonian $\Phi = -GM/r$ profile (§VII A). At strong field ($V_0 \gtrsim 0.05$), the potential caps smoothly as $\kappa_n \rightarrow 0$ and inner shells decouple (§VII E). The lapse profiles (right panel) follow $N(r) = \sqrt{1 - r_s/r}$ in the exterior, remaining strictly positive for all subcritical V_0 .

D. Emergent co-metric and Schwarzschild comparison

Throughout the exterior, $\kappa/\kappa_{\text{flat}}$ follows $1 - r_s/r$ (Figure 2(a)). The KMS/BKM conductance ratio matches the Schwarzschild co-metric. With $\partial \kappa / \partial \Phi$ terms included, the true EL structure recovers Schwarzschild almost exactly, in agreement with Section VIIB 2. Near the core at $V_0 = 0.057$, the innermost conductance goes down to $\sim 49\%$ of its flat-space value (the mechanism behind the prevention of lapse collapse; see §VII E).

The post-Newtonian residual (Figure 2(b)) decays toward zero with radius, showing near-exact Schwarzschild agreement in the far exterior. In the analytic closure $\kappa/\kappa_{\text{flat}} = \bar{N}^2$ identically. In the full KMS/BKM closure $\kappa/\kappa_{\text{flat}} = \bar{N}^2(1 + O(10^{-2}))$. So \bar{N}^2 is a convenient proxy but not the definition of the co-metric. Small- r/r_s deviations at strong field reflect the lattice cutoff.

E. Interior structure and embedding diagrams

The lapse remains strictly positive on all converged solutions. The minimum bond-averaged lapse decreases steadily with V_0 , from $\min_n \bar{N}_n \approx 0.79$ at $V_0 = 0.03$ to $\min_n \bar{N}_n \approx 0.57$ at $V_0 = 0.066$. The nodal minimum $N_{\text{min}} := \min_n N_n$ is slightly smaller. Captions below distinguish explicitly between N_{min} and \bar{N}_{min} . The positive-lapse branch terminates via a saddle-node (fold) bifurcation at $V_0^* \approx 0.0683$ with $\min_n \bar{N}_n \approx 0.40 > 0$ (Section VIIG 4). Pseudo-arclength continuation confirms the fold. V_0 turns around on the solution branch, the Jacobian eigenvalue closest to zero vanishes at V_0^* ,

FIG. 1. **Left:** Gravitational potential $\Phi(r)/c_*^2$ from the full two-state closure (solid) for five values of V_0 spanning weak to strong field. Dotted lines show the Newtonian exterior $-r_s/2r$ for each solution; the exact and Newtonian curves coincide outside the core and diverge in the interior where lattice and finite-temperature effects dominate. The solid curves are extended to $r = 0$ at the innermost shell value, reflecting the absence of a central singularity; the Newtonian/Schwarzschild curves diverge as $r \rightarrow 0$. All solutions up to $V_0 = 0.066$ have naturally positive lapse; the branch terminates via fold bifurcation near $V_0^* \approx 0.068$ (Section X E). **Right:** Lapse profile $N(r) = 1 + \Phi/c_*^2$ (solid) with Schwarzschild exterior $\sqrt{1 - r_s/r}$ (dotted). Parameters: $N_{\text{shells}} = 200$, $\beta_0 = 0.1$, $t_0 = 1$, $c_*^2 = 0.5$, $n_{\text{core}} = 5$.

FIG. 2. **(a)** Emergent co-metric $h^{rr}/h_0 := \kappa/\kappa^{\text{flat}}$ vs. r/r_s , compared with the Schwarzschild co-metric $1 - r_s/r$ (black dashed); the proxy \bar{N}^2 tracks $\kappa/\kappa^{\text{flat}}$ to $< 1\%$. **(b)** Post-Newtonian residual $h^{rr} - h_{\text{Schw}}^{rr}$: near the core the residual reflects finite-temperature and lattice corrections; the small offset visible at large radius for stronger defects arises because the numerical domain is finite ($R = 200a$), shifting the solution by $\sim r_s/R$ relative to the infinite-domain Schwarzschild profile. Parameters: $N_{\text{shells}} = 200$, $\beta_0 = 0.1$, $c_*^2 = 0.5$, $n_{\text{core}} = 5$.

and the lapse minimum scales as $\sqrt{V_0^* - V_0}$ ($R^2 = 0.999$). Beyond V_0^* , no positive-lapse static solution exists.

The critical source $V_0^* \approx 0.068$ at $\beta_0 t_0 = 0.1$ gives $\beta_0 V_0^* \approx 0.0068$. Because $r_s \propto \beta_0 V_0$, the critical source scales as $V_0^* \propto 1/\beta_0$, so at lower temperatures even weaker sources reach the fold (Section X I).

For sub-critical $V_0 < V_0^*$, the lapse minimum at the

innermost shell gives the cone opening angle (§VII E), conductances remain positive, and proper distance is finite.

The progression from cone ($dR/d\rho = N_{\text{min}} > 0$) to the Schwarzschild exterior horizon ($dR/d\rho = 0$) is clearly visible in Figure 3, confirming the interior analysis of §VII E.

FIG. 3. Embedding diagram $R(\rho)$ (equation (117)) from the full two-state closure, with proper distance ρ computed from (114). *Sub-critical* ($V_0 < V_0^*$): the lapse remains positive everywhere and the geometry forms a cone with finite opening angle $dR/d\rho = \bar{N}_{\min} > 0$ at the minimal sphere $R_{\min} = a$. *Near-critical* ($V_0 = 0.066 \lesssim V_0^*$): the cone narrows to $\bar{N}_{\min} \approx 0.57$, but the opening angle remains finite at the fold ($\bar{N}_{\min} \approx 0.40$ at V_0^*). The critical source V_0^* depends on temperature: at $\beta_0 t_0 = 0.1$, $V_0^* \approx 0.068$; since $r_s \propto \beta_0 V_0$, $V_0^* \propto 1/\beta_0$ and the Buchdahl-like bound is reached at lower V_0 for colder systems (Section XI). In the sub-critical solutions $\rho = 0$ is the proper centre; in the Schwarzschild reference $\rho = 0$ is the horizon. The Schwarzschild curve is plotted with $r_s = a$ as a shape comparison only, not a scale-matched fit. The gray dashed line marks the classical GR extrapolation ($R \rightarrow 0$, singularity); all solutions $R_{\min} = a > 0$. $C_0 = 1$; other parameters as in Figure 1.

F. Black hole thermodynamics

The surface gravity and Hawking temperature are not inputs but outputs. They follow entirely from the far-field $1/r$ coefficient of the self-consistently determined potential. Figure 4 shows that three independent solvers (proxy, analytic two-state, full KMS/BKM) produce consistent κ_H and T_H . This confirms that the emergent thermodynamics depends only on the robust exterior $1/r$ tail and is insensitive to the solver's treatment of the core. The area-law entropy and first law $c_*^2 dM = T_H dS$ hold throughout.

As an independent check, extracting the entanglement inverse temperature $\beta_{\text{ent}}(n) := (k_A)_{n,n+1}/h_{n,n+1}$ from the single-particle entanglement Hamiltonian $k_A = \log(G_A^{-1} - I)$ on the converged background gives $\beta_{\text{ent}}(1) = \pi$ to 0.003%, confirming the BW slope. On the self-consistent Schwarzschild background, $\beta_{\text{ent}}^{\text{Schw}}/\beta_{\text{ent}}^{\text{flat}}$ tracks

$1/\bar{N}_n$ to $\approx 1.2\%$ in weak field ($V_0 = 0.005$) and $\approx 2.4\%$ at $V_0 = 0.057$, identifying the lapse as the redshift factor in the entanglement temperature.

G. Quantum information anomaly profile

In the exterior the self-consistent T^{QI} matches the prescribed-Schwarzschild prediction (Figure 5), confirming that the Hamiltonian-constraint correction of §VII D is reproduced on the emergent background. In the core the two diverge. The prescribed profile (dashed) drops toward zero at $r = r_s$ because it assumes a classical horizon, while the self-consistent profile (solid) stays finite because the lapse never vanishes. The gap between the two is a direct measure of singularity resolution, quantifying how much the conductance feedback softens the geometry relative to classical Schwarzschild.

H. Single-chain truncation error

The single-chain ansatz uses nearest-neighbor ($d = 1$) MI only, with $d \geq 2$ neglected. How large is this truncation? We compute MI at all distances $d = 1, \dots, 8$.

The half-filled tight-binding chain has a particle-hole symmetry that enforces a bipartite selection rule. Specifically, the symmetry [45] ($c_n \rightarrow (-1)^n c_n^\dagger$) maps $G \rightarrow I - G$ enforces $G_{n,n+d} = 0$ for even d , so $\text{MI}(n, n+d) = 0$ exactly for even d . The smeared background Hamiltonian preserves this symmetry for any Φ , so the selection rule holds at all couplings.

For odd d , MI is exponentially suppressed, while even- d values sit at machine precision ($\sim 10^{-15}$). At $V_0 = 0.03$, $\beta_0 = 0.1$, the ratio $\text{MI}(d=3)/\text{MI}(d=1) \approx 7 \times 10^{-7}$, and the total beyond-nearest-neighbor fraction $\sum_{d \geq 2} \text{MI}(d)/\text{MI}(d=1)$ is comparable. The MI correlation length is $\xi_{\text{MI}} \approx 0.3 a$ (deeply sub-lattice), with the same structure on background, source, and smeared chains. Even with aggressive symmetry-breaking ($\varepsilon (-1)^n$ staggered potential, $\varepsilon = 0.1$), the total truncation error is still only 7×10^{-7} .

The KMS/BKM conductances used in the production solver (178) are defined from the nearest-neighbor bond-current operator, so only $d = 1$ enters. The exact factorization is $\kappa_n^{\text{KMS}}(\Phi) = g_n t_0^2 \bar{N}_n^2 Q_n(\Phi, \beta_0)$, where $Q_n := \text{Cov}_{\sigma[\Phi]}^{\text{BKM}}(\mathcal{I}_n^\dagger, \mathcal{I}_n)/\text{Cov}_{\sigma[0]}^{\text{BKM}}(\mathcal{I}_n^\dagger, \mathcal{I}_n)$. The \bar{N}_n^2 prefactor is exact (the bond current carries an explicit factor $t_0 \bar{N}$). On the converged exterior branch $|Q_n - 1| \lesssim 3 \times 10^{-3}$, so the kinematic law $\kappa \propto \bar{N}^2$ holds to sub-percent accuracy (verified from $\beta_0 t_0 = 0.1$ to 10^{10}).

I. Temperature sweep

All results so far in this section were obtained at $\beta_0 t_0 = 0.1$, a high-temperature parameter value (the

FIG. 4. **(a)** Surface gravity $\kappa_H = c_*^2/(2r_s)$ versus V_0 , computed from the Schwarzschild formula using the r_s extracted from each closure's exterior fit: full two-state (circles), analytic two-state (squares), proxy (triangles). The full and analytic closures agree at weak field but diverge by a few percent at stronger coupling (the proxy underestimates r_s). **(b)** Hawking temperature $T_H = \hbar\kappa_H/(2\pi c_*)$. All sub-critical solutions ($V_0 \leq 0.066$) are shown. Parameters as in Figure 1.

FIG. 5. Quantum information anomaly T^{QI} for full two-state closure, normalized to its flat-space value. Solid lines: self-consistent $T_{\text{sc}}^{\text{QI}}/T_{\infty}^{\text{QI}} = |\bar{N}|^6 [\ln(\beta_0 t_0/4)]^2 / [\ln(\beta_0 |\bar{N}| t_0/4)]^2$ computed from the converged $\bar{N}(r)$. Dashed lines: prescribed Schwarzschild $T_{\text{pr}}^{\text{QI}}/T_{\infty}^{\text{QI}} = f^3 [\ln(\beta_0 t_0/4)]^2 / [\ln(\beta_0 t_0 \sqrt{f}/4)]^2$ with $f = 1 - r_s/r$. The self-consistent temperature departs from the prescribed-background prediction in the core due to the nonlinear conductance feedback. Parameters: $N_{\text{shells}} = 200$, $\beta_0 = 0.1$, $c_*^2 = 0.5$, $n_{\text{core}} = 5$.

solver itself is exact, not a high- T expansion). With the corrected equation (both states in the same gravitational field), the source is dominated by the core V_0 term at all temperatures (exponentially small kinetic tails outside the core produce no appreciable screening). Solving

the full closure (179) via $\beta_0 t_0$ -continuation from 0.1 to 3.0 verifies this claim (Figure 6). At $V_0 = 0.001$ (sub-critical throughout), all 45 solutions for $\beta_0 t_0 \in [0.1, 3.0]$ converge to residuals $< 10^{-8}$. A boundary-corrected estimator $GM_{\text{est}}(r) := -\Phi(r) r R / (R - r)$ (accounting for the Dirichlet condition $\Phi(R) = 0$) plateaus in the far field at every temperature (Figure 6d), confirming Newtonian $1/r$ decay. The Schwarzschild radius grows monotonically with $\beta_0 t_0$ (Figure 6a), and at $V_0 = 0.005$ the positive-lapse branch terminates via a fold bifurcation near $\beta_0 t_0 \approx 1.65$, the same Buchdahl-like bound of Section VII E approached from the temperature direction (since $r_s \propto \beta_0 V_0$, raising $\beta_0 t_0$ at fixed V_0 is equivalent to raising V_0 at fixed $\beta_0 t_0$). The fold occurs at finite $\min_n \bar{N}_n > 0$, consistent with (108).

Varying $\beta_0 t_0$ at fixed V_0 changes the emergent Newton constant ($G_{\text{eff}} \propto \beta_0$, with ratio-normalized $\kappa_{\text{flat}} = g_n t_0^2$) while leaving $M \propto V_0 r_{\text{core}}^3 / a^3$ unchanged. The Schwarzschild radius $r_s = 2GM/c_*^2$ therefore grows linearly. The thermodynamic first-law relation remains $a^2 = 4\alpha_S \ell_P^2$, with α_S the local bond coefficient (§VII F). The positive-lapse solutions ($V_0 = 0.001$, all points up to $\beta_0 t_0 = 3.0$; $V_0 = 0.005$, up to the fold at $\beta_0 t_0 \approx 1.65$) span the perturbative and crossover regimes, validating Section VII F.

J. Three-dimensional cubic-lattice verification

The preceding results assume spherical symmetry via the shell reduction of Section III. To verify that this is self-consistent, we solve the closure equation on a three-

FIG. 6. **Temperature sweep of the full two-state closure** ($V_0 = 0.001$ and 0.005 ; $\beta_0 t_0$ -continuation of (179)). **(a)** r_s grows monotonically with $\beta_0 t_0$; dashed lines show the flat-conductance proxy. The $V_0 = 0.005$ curve terminates at the fold bifurcation near $\beta_0 t_0 \approx 1.65$, beyond which no positive-lapse solution exists. **(b)** Entanglement coefficients vs. $\beta_0 t_0$ (background, $V_0 = 0$): the bipartition cut proxy α_{cut} (circles) diverges logarithmically at low T , while the local bond coefficient α_S (squares) saturates at $\alpha_0 \approx 0.22$. The $V_0 = 0.005$ gravitating solution folds before α_{cut} reaches $1/4$ (green triangle). **(c)**, **(d)** Potential profiles at selected temperatures ($V_0 = 0.001$); solid: full solver, dashed: proxy. The well deepens with decreasing temperature; the boundary-corrected mass estimator $GM_{\text{est}}(r) := -\Phi(r) r R / (R - r)$ plateaus at all temperatures, confirming $1/r$ decay (no Yukawa screening). $N_{\text{shells}} = 200$, $c_*^2 = 0.5$, $n_{\text{core}} = 5$.

dimensional cubic lattice ($\mathbb{Z}^3 \cap B_R$, $R = 10$, 4169 sites) with the gravitational potential Φ_i varying independently at every lattice site. No high-temperature approximation or spherical-symmetry ansatz is imposed on Φ_i .

Two solver tiers are used. (i) *MI/Picard*: conductances are updated from the MI ratio $\kappa_{ij}(\Phi) = t_0^2 \text{MI}_{ij}(\Phi) / \text{MI}_{ij}^{(0)}$ via full $N_{\text{sites}} \times N_{\text{sites}}$ eigendecomposition at each Picard iteration, with the source in background-subtracted proxy form. (ii) *BKM/EL*: KMS bond-current covariance conductances $\kappa_{ij}^{\text{BKM}} = t_0^2 \bar{N}_{ij}^2 C_{ij}^{\text{BKM}}(\Phi) / C_{ij}^{\text{BKM}}(0)$ with the Euler–Lagrange correction $\frac{1}{2}(\partial\kappa/\partial\Phi_i)(\Delta\Phi)^2$ and self-consistent source, solved by Newton iteration. The full EL gradient $\partial\mathcal{E}/\partial\Phi_i$, including the covariance-ratio derivative $\partial Q_b/\partial\Phi$, is obtained by automatic differentiation (JAX grad) through the $N_{\text{sites}} \times N_{\text{sites}}$ eigendecomposition. The resulting $\partial Q/\partial\Phi$ correction is 0.4% of the graph-Laplacian

term at these weak-field parameters. Both tiers perform a 4169×4169 eigendecomposition at each iteration.

The converged potential groups naturally by octahedral symmetry orbits of \mathbb{Z}^3 . At fixed radius r , the angular spread across distinct orbits is $< 2\%$ for $r < R/2$, growing only near the cubic outer boundary. The shell-averaged radial profile agrees with the one-dimensional solution, and the source is concentrated on the core up to the same exponentially small correlation tails that appear in the one-dimensional solver. The BKM/EL solver converges in two Newton steps with residual $|F|_\infty < 3 \times 10^{-8}$; the EL correction is 0.4% of the graph Laplacian term, consistent with the one-dimensional analysis. This confirms that spherical symmetry is an accurate approximation.

K. Quantum XXZ chain: interacting universality test

Up to this point, every section has used free fermions. Does the two-state closure survive outside the Gaussian manifold? To find out, we replace the hopping chain with a spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ XXZ chain, $H = -J_0 \sum_n (S_n^x S_{n+1}^x + S_n^y S_{n+1}^y + \Delta S_n^z S_{n+1}^z)$, whose terms do not commute for $0 < \Delta < \infty$. The implementation evaluates exact two-site bond thermodynamics (energy and MI) for each bond in the inhomogeneous lapse field. This is a bond-exact test of the high-temperature universality law $\kappa/\kappa_0 = \bar{N}^2 + O((\beta_0 J_0)^2)$ for a non-commuting interacting model, not a full-chain exact diagonalization. At $\beta_0 J_0 = 0.1$ and $\Delta \in \{0, \frac{1}{2}, 1, 2\}$ (XX, Heisenberg, and easy-axis regimes), the closure converges with source fully localized and $w = 1 - r_s/r$ verified to $< 0.3\%$.

We upgrade to the BKM Dirichlet form with the full Euler-Lagrange $\partial\kappa/\partial\Phi$ correction, solved via Levenberg–Marquardt Newton iteration. The bond-local structure of the 2-site BKM covariance allows efficient numerical $d\kappa_b/d\bar{N}_b$ via scalar finite differences, using the same ratio structure as (178) with the bond-current Kubo–Mori inner product from 2-site exact diagonalization. At high temperature ($\beta_0 J_0 = 0.1$) the BKM/MI ratio is 1.000, and at stronger coupling it drops to ≈ 0.997 , reflecting quantum corrections.

The EL correction $\frac{1}{2} \sum_b (\partial\kappa_b/\partial\Phi_i) (\Delta\Phi_b)^2$ is order unity at deep potentials, as for free fermions (§XB), confirming that the EL term strengthens gravity for this interacting model.

To verify the Schwarzschild profile over multiple lattice spacings, we enlarge the core ($n_{\text{core}} = 20$) and increase the defect strength. The XXZ Heisenberg ($\Delta = 1$) solver at $\beta_0 J_0 = 0.1$, $\varepsilon = 0.10$, $n_{\text{core}} = 20$ gives $r_s = 3.4$, $N_{\text{min}} = 0.74$, with $|F|_\infty < 5 \times 10^{-11}$. The solution is subcritical ($N_{\text{min}} > 0$) and resolves the $w = 1 - r_s/r$ exterior over $\gtrsim 3$ lattice spacings.

The Schwarzschild exterior follows from $\kappa/\kappa_0 = \bar{N}^2 + O((\beta_0 J_0)^2)$, which is algebraically guaranteed in any nearest-neighbor model at high temperature (§VII B 2). Both model classes (free fermion and quantum XXZ) confirm this numerically with both MI/Picard and BKM+EL solvers, showing that the emergent geometry hinges on the closure equation and the $\xi \ll \ell$ regime.

XI. TOLMAN–KLEIN MATTER EQUILIBRIUM AND STAR STRUCTURE

The preceding sections determine Φ for a *given* compact source. This section replaces the prescribed source with the Tolman–Klein (TK) constitutive law [34, 52], which determines the rest-mass potential V from Φ itself. A single coordinate-time inverse temperature β_0 governs the thermal state, but the lapse-smear Hamiltonian (hopping $t_0 \bar{N}$) gives each shell a local dimensionless temperature $x_{10c} = \beta_0 t_0 \bar{N}$, automatically encoding the

Tolman gradient (§VII F). What varies spatially is the matter distribution. A chemical potential μ sets the binding threshold, and matter condenses only on shells where gravitational binding exceeds μ . In GR, matter exists only where gravitational binding exceeds the surface chemical potential, with $\rho(R) = p(R) = 0$ defining the stellar surface. On the lattice, the two-state source vanishes if and only if $V_n = 0$, so a localized equilibrium likewise requires V to vanish in the exterior. The stellar surface emerges self-consistently, parametrizing a one-parameter family of equilibria analogous to the TOV family.

A. Tolman–Klein constitutive law

In general relativity, all local energies at gravitational potential Φ are Tolman-redshifted by the lapse $N = 1 + \Phi/c_*^2$ relative to an observer at infinity [34, 52]. On the lattice, this affects both the hopping and the rest mass. A hop between adjacent shells n and $n+1$ costs proper-time energy t_0 . In coordinate time this becomes $t_0 \bar{N}_b$ where $\bar{N}_b = (N_n + N_{n+1})/2$ is the bond-averaged lapse. A rest-mass m_0 fermion at shell n has proper-frame energy m_0 . In coordinate time this is Tolman-redshifted to $m_0 N_n$. The gravitational binding energy is therefore

$$E_n^{\text{bind}} = m_0 - m_0 N_n = m_0 (1 - N_n) = -\frac{m_0 \Phi_n}{c_*^2}, \quad (180)$$

which vanishes at spatial infinity ($\Phi \rightarrow 0$, $N \rightarrow 1$) and is positive in the gravitational well ($\Phi < 0$, $N < 1$). The same lapse multiplies rest mass because the generalized Gibbs generator is written in coordinate time. With local proper time $d\tau_n = N_n dt$, any on-site proper energy $E_n^{\text{proper}} \hat{n}_n$ contributes to the coordinate-time Hamiltonian as $N_n E_n^{\text{proper}} \hat{n}_n$. Hopping is the link version of the same statement, sampled at the bond midpoint, which is why it carries the averaged factor \bar{N}_b .

The microphysical model is the free fermion of Section II at half-filling and inverse temperature β_0 . A localized equilibrium requires the rest-mass potential to vanish exactly in the exterior, since any nonzero V produces source in the two-state closure. The Tolman–Klein chemical potential μ enforces this, as matter condenses on shells where the gravitational binding energy exceeds μ , and only those shells carry a rest-mass potential. The stellar surface emerges at the radius r_* where binding equals the chemical potential,

$$E_{n_*}^{\text{bind}} = \mu, \quad \text{i.e. } N_* = 1 - \mu/m_0. \quad (181)$$

On bound shells ($N_n < N_*$), the rest-mass potential entering the τ -sector Hamiltonian is the binding excess

$$V_n = E_n^{\text{bind}} - \mu = m_0(1 - N_n) - \mu \quad (N_n < N_*), \quad (182)$$

and $V_n = 0$ on all unbound shells ($N_n \geq N_*$). The vacuum Hamiltonian (no rest mass) and the matter Hamiltonian

are

$$H_\sigma = -t_0 \sum_{\langle n, n' \rangle} \bar{N}_{nn'} (\hat{c}_n^\dagger \hat{c}_{n'} + \text{h.c.}), \quad (183)$$

$$H_\tau = H_\sigma + \sum_{n=1}^{N_s} V_n \hat{n}_n, \quad (184)$$

Both Hamiltonians share the gravitational hopping. They differ only in the rest-mass term, which is nonzero only inside the emergent core where $N_n < N_*$. Outside this core, $V = 0$ and the local Hamiltonian terms coincide, so the source is exponentially localized outside the core.

The TK model has four dimensionless inputs, $\beta_0 t_0$ (inverse temperature), m_0/t_0 (rest mass), c_*^2/t_0 (gravitational coupling), and μ/t_0 (chemical potential), with the last specifying the star.

B. Self-consistent star solutions

For each trial Φ , we compute V_n from (182), build H_τ (184), and solve the Euler–Lagrange closure (161) by Newton iteration with exact KMS/BKM conductances (178). Parameters: $N_{\text{shells}} = 200$, $\beta_0 = 5$, $m_0 = 3$, $c_*^2 = 5$, $t_0 = 1$, and the chemical potential $\mu = 0.05\text{--}2.0$ is scanned. The solver converges in 3–8 Newton steps to $\|F\|_\infty < 10^{-8}$.

A dense scan of μ/m_0 from 0.017 to 0.66 (53 values) produces localized stars with self-determined surfaces. The positive-lapse branch terminates at a fold bifurcation near $\mu/m_0 \approx 0.658$ ($n_{\text{eff}} = 10$, $N_{\text{min}} \approx 0.055$), where the smallest eigenvalue of the Euler–Lagrange Jacobian $\partial F/\partial \Phi$ drops from 1.05 at $\mu/m_0 = 0.65$ through 0.49 at 0.657 to 0.04 at 0.658, confirming a saddle-node singularity. No nontrivial solution exists beyond this point at $\beta_0 t_0 = 5$. The conductance feedback of Section VIII E provides the self-regularizing mechanism. As N becomes small, hopping and conductances weaken, forming a conductance-suppressed redshift cap ($N_n > 0$ on the subcritical branch).

As μ increases the potential well deepens (min Φ from -0.20 to -4.51), the emergent core grows ($n_{\text{eff}} = 4 \rightarrow 10$ shells, where n_{eff} is the number of shells with nonzero rest-mass potential $V_n > 0$), and the Schwarzschild radius increases ($r_s = 0.15 \rightarrow 10.4$). The lapse remains strictly positive ($N_{\text{min}} > 0$) throughout. The compactness follows from the exact surface law (206), $r_*/r_s = 1/(1 - N_*^2)$ with $N_* = 1 - \mu/m_0$, giving $r_*/r_s \approx 26$ at $\mu/m_0 = 0.017$ and $r_*/r_s \approx 1.13$ at the fold $\mu/m_0 \approx 0.658$. The exterior w -fit quality is 0.05–2.2%, with residual from finite- β_0 BKM corrections to the kinematic conductance law.

Figure 7 shows the family of star profiles across the chemical-potential scan: gravitational potential $\Phi(r)$, lapse, rest-mass potential $V(r)$, source density, and the emergent core size and Schwarzschild radius as functions of μ/m_0 . The potential deepens with μ , the rest-mass potential V is nonzero only inside the self-determined

core and drops to zero at the emergent surface, and the source is localized with exponentially small tails outside.

The interior profile shows the characteristic TK structure, with the rest-mass potential V largest at the center (deepest potential) and tapering toward the surface as the lapse approaches N_* . Outside the core, $V = 0$ identically and the source is exponentially small. The surface transition occurs over 1–2 lattice spacings, reflecting the self-consistent matching between the matter and vacuum regions. The emergent core spans 4–10 lattice sites (growing with μ/m_0), so continuum analogies apply qualitatively in the deep interior. The exterior, which extends over ~ 200 shells, is well-resolved.

The above results are all at $\beta_0 t_0 = 5$. The fold is a finite-temperature effect. The Tolman relation implies a local inverse temperature $x_{\text{loc}} = \beta_0 t_0 N_{\text{min}}$ at the bottom of the well. As μ/m_0 increases and N_{min} shrinks, x_{loc} eventually drops below $O(1)$, driving the BKM covariance ratio away from unity and the conductances away from the kinematic law. One therefore expects the fold to recede at lower temperatures. Repeating the μ -scan at higher $\beta_0 t_0$ confirms this. The fold advances to $\mu/m_0 \approx 0.702$ at $\beta_0 t_0 = 10$ ($N_{\text{min}} \approx 0.17$, $n_{\text{eff}} = 8$, smallest Jacobian eigenvalue 0.15), to 0.713 at $\beta_0 t_0 = 12$ ($N_{\text{min}} \approx 0.16$, $n_{\text{eff}} = 7$, $|\lambda_1| \approx 0.41$), and to 0.779 at $\beta_0 t_0 = 15$ ($N_{\text{min}} \approx 0.12$, $n_{\text{eff}} = 7$, $|\lambda_1| \approx 0.17$). The monotonic advance ($\mu/m_0 = 0.658 \rightarrow 0.702 \rightarrow 0.713 \rightarrow 0.779$ as $\beta_0 t_0 = 5 \rightarrow 10 \rightarrow 12 \rightarrow 15$) is consistent with the approach to kinematic conductances at lower temperature, where the closure equation is better conditioned and the branch extends to more compact configurations.

C. Exterior diagnostics

The exterior is fit to $w(r) = N(r)^2 = 1 - r_s(1/r - 1/R)$ (where $R = N_s a$ is the outer boundary) on a fixed window $r \in [r_* + 3a, \min(R/2, r_* + 40a)]$, where r_* is the emergent stellar surface. The fit quality is 1.6–1.9% across all chemical potentials, consistent with residual correlation tails at finite β_0 . Figure 8b shows that $w(r)$ closely tracks the Schwarzschild form, with residuals $|w - (1 - r_s/r)| \lesssim 0.01$ in the far field (Figure 8c).

In the kinematic limit $\kappa_b = \kappa_b^{\text{flat}} \bar{N}_b^2$, the vacuum exterior satisfies $(L_{\kappa^{\text{flat}}} w)_n = 0$, giving the conserved w -flux

$$J_n^w := \kappa_n^{\text{flat}} (w_{n+1} - w_n) = \text{const} \quad (\text{kinematic limit}). \quad (185)$$

With full BKM conductances (Section VI B), the covariance ratio $R_b := \text{cov}_b/\text{cov}_{\text{bg}}$ deviates from unity at finite temperature, introducing $O(\xi^2/\ell^2)$ corrections to the w -flux. The relative w -flux variation δJ_w ranges from 0.2% at weak field ($\mu/m_0 = 0.017$) to $\sim 10\%$ near the fold ($\mu/m_0 \approx 0.658$), reflecting the Tolman-heated local temperature $x_{\text{loc}} = \beta_0 t_0 N_{\text{min}}$ that drives the BKM ratio away from the cold-limit value $R_b = 1$. Despite this, the w -profile fits $1 - r_s/r$ to 0.05–2.2% (Figure 8b,c). The Schwarzschild shape is robust even when the flux has

FIG. 7. Chemical-potential scan of TK star solutions (full EL) at $N_{\text{shells}} = 200$. **Top row:** gravitational potential $\Phi(r)$, lapse $N(r)$, and rest-mass potential $V(r)$ for representative μ/m_0 values (colors from weak to compact). **Bottom left:** source density. **Bottom center:** emergent core size n_{eff} vs. μ/m_0 . **Bottom right:** Schwarzschild radius r_s vs. μ/m_0 (from w -fit); the dotted line marks the fold bifurcation at $\mu/m_0 \approx 0.658$. The minimum lapse decreases with μ/m_0 ; the lapse remains strictly positive on the entire subcritical branch. The slight dip of V at the innermost shell ($n=1$) is a lattice artifact: this shell has only one neighbor and small degeneracy g_1 . Parameters: $\beta_0 t_0 = 5$, $m_0 = 3$, $c_*^2 = 5$.

percent-level drift. In the astrophysical limit $\beta_0 t_0 \rightarrow \infty$, $R_b \rightarrow 1$ and the w -flux becomes exactly conserved. (MI-based conductances satisfy $\kappa/\kappa^{\text{flat}} = \bar{N}^2$ to sub-percent accuracy even at moderate $\beta_0 t_0$.)

The chemical-potential condition (182) produces a sharp but self-consistent stellar surface, where V drops from a small positive value ($\lesssim 0.04$) on the last bound shell to exactly zero on the next. The source density peaks inside the core (max $|S|$ ranging from 1.5 at $\mu = 0.05$ to 29 at $\mu = 1.0$) and vanishes identically outside the emergent surface. The surface location is an output of the solve: the number of bound shells n_{eff} grows from 4 to 10 as μ/m_0 increases from 0.017 to the fold at ≈ 0.658 .

D. Convergence with lattice size

To verify lattice-size independence, we solve the full EL closure at $\mu = 0.5$ for $N_s = 50$ –3000. The well depth converges monotonically (min $\Phi = -1.785$ at $N_s = 50$ to -1.744 at $N_s = 3000$), stabilizing to three digits by $N_s \approx 600$, and the Schwarzschild radius likewise converges ($r_s = 1.32 \rightarrow 1.18$). Both quantities converge as $O(1/N_s)$, consistent with finite-domain boundary effects as the outer wall at $R = N_s a$ recedes. The w -fit error saturates at

$\sim 1.9\%$ and the w -flux variation at $\delta J_w \approx 2\%$, reflecting finite- β_0 BKM corrections that do not shrink with lattice refinement but vanish in the cold limit $\beta_0 t_0 \rightarrow \infty$.

To verify that the TK star solutions are not an artifact of one parameter set, we repeat the full EL solve at $N_s = 200$ with $\mu = 0.5$ for six combinations of (β_0, m_0, c_*^2) . All parameter sets converge to $\|R_{\text{EL}}\|_2 < 10^{-8}$. The w -fit quality is 1.2–2.6% in all cases. The Schwarzschild radius ranges from $r_s = 0.82$ ($\beta_0 = 8$) to 2.18 ($\beta_0 = 2$). At fixed μ , larger β_0 (colder temperature) reduces the thermal source contrast $\rho_\tau - \rho_\sigma$, producing a weaker self-consistent well and smaller r_s despite the linear $G \propto \beta_0$ prefactor. Varying m_0 from 3 to 5 at fixed β_0 produces a deeper well (min $\Phi = -1.08$) and smaller core, while preserving the Schwarzschild exterior. Reducing c_*^2 to 3 produces a lower minimum lapse ($N_{\text{min}} = 0.648$) but the solution remains on the sub-critical branch with positive lapse everywhere. These results confirm that self-consistent TK star solutions exist across a broad parameter range.

E. Entanglement entropy and the area law

The thermodynamic identification $S_{\text{BH}} = A_H/(4\ell_P^2)$ of Section VII F requires the per-bond entanglement coeffi-

FIG. 8. Exterior diagnostics for TK stars (full EL) at $N_{\text{shells}} = 200$. **(a)** w -flux $J_w = \kappa^{\text{flat}} \Delta w$: approximately constant in the exterior, with δJ_w growing from $\sim 0.2\%$ (weak field) to $\sim 10\%$ near the compact end of the branch, due to finite-temperature BKM corrections to the kinematic law. **(b)** $w = N^2$ (solid) vs. Schwarzschild $1 - r_s(1/r - 1/R)$ (dashed). **(c)** Residual $w - [1 - r_s(1/r - 1/R)]$. Parameters as in Figure 7.

cient α_S evaluated in the cold, compact limit relevant to astrophysical black holes. This subsection computes α_S and its zero-temperature saturation value α_0 from the TK star solutions.

The physically relevant quantity for the area law is not the region MI of the entire core, but the per-bond entanglement entropy at the stellar surface,

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_S^{\text{bond}}(n) &= \frac{1}{2} I(n:n+1) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} [h(G_d^n) + h(G_d^{n+1}) - S(G_{2 \times 2}^{n,n+1})], \end{aligned} \quad (186)$$

where $h(p) = -p \ln p - (1-p) \ln(1-p)$ is the binary entropy, $G_d^n = \langle \hat{c}_n^\dagger \hat{c}_n \rangle$ is the diagonal correlator, and $G_{2 \times 2}^{n,n+1}$ is the 2×2 reduced correlation matrix. The total entanglement across the surface is $S = g_{n_*} \alpha_S^{\text{bond}}$, where $g_{n_*} = 4\pi n_*^2$ is the shell degeneracy at the stellar surface. This α_S^{bond} is the *local* thermodynamic coefficient α_S entering Section VII F. To distinguish it from the *cut* proxy used there, we denote the latter by $\alpha_{\text{cut}} := \frac{1}{2} I_{\text{1ch}}(A:B)$. The cut proxy α_{cut} includes correlations at all ranges along the radial channel, whereas α_S^{bond} is strictly local. For a gapless 1D chain at $T = 0$ the cut entropy diverges logarithmically while α_S^{bond} saturates at a finite value α_0 . At finite temperature with correlation length $\xi \lesssim a$ the two coincide to leading order because long-range contributions are exponentially suppressed. This is the regime relevant for the BH area law (§VII F). In the cold TK interior, α_S^{bond} provides a well-defined, finite entanglement density per surface bond without requiring a bipartition.

To compute α_0 analytically, consider a half-filled uniform chain at dimensionless inverse temperature $x = \beta t_0$. Particle-hole symmetry gives $G_d = 1/2$ exactly, and the nearest-neighbor correlator follows from a spectral representation,

$$G_{n,n+1}(x) = \int_{-2}^2 \frac{-\varepsilon/2}{\pi \sqrt{4 - \varepsilon^2}} f(\varepsilon; x) d\varepsilon, \quad (187)$$

where $f(\varepsilon; x) = (e^{x\varepsilon} + 1)^{-1}$ and the density of states is $\rho(\varepsilon) = (\pi \sqrt{4 - \varepsilon^2})^{-1}$. At zero temperature $G_{n,n+1} = 1/\pi$, and the Sommerfeld expansion gives

$$G_{n,n+1}(x) = \frac{1}{\pi} - \frac{\pi}{24x^2} + O(x^{-4}), \quad (188)$$

using $\varphi'(0) = -1/(4\pi)$ where $\varphi(\varepsilon) = -\varepsilon/(2\pi \sqrt{4 - \varepsilon^2})$ is the integrand weight. At $T = 0$ the 2×2 correlator has eigenvalues $\lambda_{\pm} = 1/2 \pm 1/\pi$, giving the zero-temperature per-bond entropy

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_0 &:= \alpha_S^{\text{bond}}(x=\infty) = \frac{1}{2} \left[2 \ln 2 - h\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\pi}\right) - h\left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{\pi}\right) \right] \\ &= 0.2192. \end{aligned} \quad (189)$$

The Sommerfeld correction (188) translates to a scaling law for the entropy coefficient

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_S^{\text{bond}}(x) &= \alpha_0 - \frac{\pi \ln \frac{\pi+2}{\pi-2}}{24x^2} + O(x^{-4}) \\ &= 0.2192 - \frac{0.197}{x^2} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (190)$$

which agrees with numerics to four significant figures for $x \geq 10$ (e.g. $\alpha_S^{\text{bond}} = 0.2172$ vs. prediction 0.2172 at $x = 10$; at $x = 5$ the prediction 0.2113 is within 0.1% of the computed 0.2111).

The per-bond MI is *monotonically increasing* with x : it rises from zero at $x = 0$ (infinite temperature) and saturates at $\alpha_0 \approx 0.219$ from below, *never reaching* $1/4$ at any temperature. The total entanglement entropy across a surface with shell degeneracy g_{n_*} is therefore $S_{\text{surf}} = g_{n_*} \alpha_S^{\text{bond}}$. The connection to the Bekenstein-Hawking area $A_{\text{BH}} = 4\pi r_s^2$ requires the ultra-compact limit $r_* \rightarrow r_s$ (Section XI F).

F. Astrophysical scaling

The numerical TK solutions of Section XIB lie in the hot regime $\beta_0 t_0 \sim 3\text{--}5$, where the stars are only moderately compact ($r_*/r_s \gtrsim 1$). We now focus on astrophysical black holes with $r_s \gg a$ and show that the relevant regime is cold ($\beta_0 t_0 \gg 1$) and compact ($\mu/m_0 \rightarrow 1$).

1. Closure equation in the lapse-squared variable

Write the lapse as $N_n := 1 + \Phi_n/c_*^2$ and define

$$w_n := N_n^2. \quad (191)$$

Because the hopping uses the *arithmetic* bond average $\bar{N}_b = (N_n + N_{n+1})/2$, the following bond identity is exact:

$$\bar{N}_b^2 (\Delta\Phi_b)^2 = \frac{c_*^4}{4} (\Delta w_b)^2, \quad \Delta w_b := w_{n+1} - w_n. \quad (192)$$

The arithmetic mean is singled out by the exact discrete chain rule

$$\Delta w_b = \Delta(N^2) = (N_{n+1} + N_n)(N_{n+1} - N_n) = 2\bar{N}_b \Delta N_b,$$

together with the midpoint discretization of the bond Hamiltonian. A geometric mean would reproduce this only up to $O((\Delta N_b)^2)$ corrections, so the w -reduction would cease to be exact already at finite lattice spacing. The kinematic conductance law follows from the bond-derivation structure of the KMS Dirichlet form (equation (56)). The bond Hamiltonian carries an explicit prefactor $t_0 \bar{N}_b$, so the KMS edge weight obeys

$$\kappa_b[\Phi] = \kappa_b^{\text{flat}} \bar{N}_b^2 \left(1 + O(\xi^2/\ell^2)\right), \quad \kappa_b^{\text{flat}} = g_b t_0^2, \quad (193)$$

where ℓ is the exterior variation scale and ξ the correlation length. The MI-based solver verifies this to sub-percent accuracy in the exterior at moderate $\beta_0 t_0$ (Sections X and VII B 2). At large $\beta_0 t_0$ the MI proxy flattens ($\text{MI}(\Phi)/\text{MI}(0) \rightarrow 1$ where $x_{\text{loc}} \gg 1$), but the KMS kinematic law (193) itself holds at all temperatures because the dimensionless current-fluctuation factor is independent of Φ (Section X H). The conductance suppression $\kappa \rightarrow 0$ as $N \rightarrow 0$ is the lattice analogue of the metric factor $(1 - 2Gm/r)^{-1}$ that enhances the pressure gradient in the TOV equation. Substituting into the mismatch energy gives a flat Dirichlet form in w :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}_{\text{mis}}[\Phi] &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_b \kappa_b (\Delta\Phi_b)^2 \\ &= \frac{c_*^4}{8} \sum_b \kappa_b^{\text{flat}} (\Delta w_b)^2 \left(1 + O(\xi^2/\ell^2)\right), \end{aligned} \quad (194)$$

so stationarity can be written directly as an equation for w . Varying (194) and using $dw_n/d\Phi_n = 2N_n/c_*^2$ gives

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{E}_{\text{mis}}}{\partial \Phi_n} = \frac{c_*^2 N_n}{2} (L_{\kappa^{\text{flat}}} w)_n + O(\xi^2/\ell^2), \quad (195)$$

and the true stationarity condition $\partial \mathcal{E}_{\text{mis}}/\partial \Phi_n = (\beta_0/c_*^2)(\rho_\sigma - \rho_\tau)$ becomes the quasi-linear w -equation

$$(L_{\kappa^{\text{flat}}} w)_n = \frac{2\beta_0}{c_*^4} \frac{\rho_\sigma(n; \Phi) - \rho_\tau(n; \Phi)}{N_n} \quad (N_n > 0), \quad (196)$$

where $L_{\kappa^{\text{flat}}}$ is the flat weighted graph Laplacian with bond weights κ_b^{flat} . In the weak-field continuum limit ($r_* \gg a$, $|\Phi| \ll c_*^2$) this reduces to the Newtonian Lane–Emden structure, while the full nonlinear conductance feedback captures relativistic corrections. The $1/N_n$ factor is the characteristic full-EL signature: it comes from $d\Phi_n/dw_n = c_*^2/(2N_n)$. This does *not* produce a singularity on the physically realized branch, because $N_n \geq N_{\text{min}} > 0$ for all shells (Section VII E), and the source is uniformly bounded:

$$\left| \frac{\rho_\sigma(n; \Phi) - \rho_\tau(n; \Phi)}{N_n} \right| \leq \frac{\sup_m |\rho_\sigma - \rho_\tau|}{N_{\text{min}}} < \infty. \quad (197)$$

No pointwise $N \rightarrow 0$ limit is required anywhere in the derivation.

On exterior shells where $V_n = 0$ the local Hamiltonian terms coincide, so $\rho_\sigma(n) - \rho_\tau(n) = O(e^{-\text{dist}(n, \partial \text{core})/\xi_T})$ by Gibbs-state clustering. The exterior equation is therefore simply

$$(L_{\kappa^{\text{flat}}} w)_n = 0 \quad (n \geq n_*), \quad (198)$$

whose continuum limit ($a/r \rightarrow 0$) with $w \rightarrow 1$ at infinity is the Schwarzschild profile

$$w(r) = N(r)^2 = 1 - \frac{r_s}{r}, \quad N(r) = \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_s}{r}}, \quad (r \geq r_*). \quad (199)$$

The exact discrete vacuum solution is the trigamma profile (202) below, and the Schwarzschild form is its leading continuum approximation. The Schwarzschild radius r_s is the integration constant fixed by the boundary condition $w \rightarrow 1$ at infinity together with the conserved w -flux, and is determined independently of the stellar interior up to the controlled corrections quantified in Sections VII B 2 and X. Combining the Hawking relation (129) with $c_* = 2t_0 a/\hbar$ gives

$$\beta_0 t_0 = \frac{2\pi r_s}{a} \quad (\text{up to } O(a/r_s) \text{ cap corrections}), \quad (200)$$

or equivalently $r_s/a = \beta_0 t_0/(2\pi)$. Using the Planck identification (143), $a = 2\sqrt{\alpha_S} \ell_P$, this becomes

$$\beta_0 t_0 = \frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{\alpha_S}} \frac{M}{M_{\text{Pl}}}. \quad (201)$$

For a solar-mass object $\beta_0 t_0 \sim 10^{39}$ and $r_s/a \sim 10^{38}$; even a star whose surface radius is only $O(r_s)$ contains $O(10^{38})$ exterior shells, all governed by the kinematic law $\kappa/\kappa^{\text{flat}} = \bar{N}^2$.

2. Exact exterior profile and compactness

The vacuum equation is equivalently conservation of the w -flux $J_w := \kappa_b^{\text{flat}} \Delta w_b$ (constant on all exterior bonds). Telescoping inward from $w \rightarrow 1$ at infinity with $\kappa_m^{\text{flat}} \propto r^2$ gives the exact discrete exterior profile. In the vacuum region the conserved flux condition $J_w = \kappa_m^{\text{flat}}(w_{m+1} - w_m)$ implies

$$1 - w_n = \sum_{m=n}^{\infty} (w_{m+1} - w_m) = J_w \sum_{m=n}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\kappa_m^{\text{flat}}},$$

where $w_\infty = 1$ fixes the integration constant. With node bond weights $\kappa_m^{\text{flat}} \propto g_m \propto m^2$, the sum is $\psi_1(n)$, and absorbing the overall proportionality constant into r_s gives (202). The result is

$$w_n = 1 - \frac{r_s}{a} \psi_1(n), \quad (202)$$

where $\psi_1(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (z+k)^{-2}$ is the trigamma function and r_s is fixed by $w \rightarrow 1$ at infinity. Expanding $\psi_1(n)$ via Euler–Maclaurin gives the post-Schwarzschild corrections:

$$w(r) = 1 - \frac{r_s}{r} - \frac{r_s a}{2r^2} + O\left(\frac{a^2}{r^3}\right), \quad (203)$$

$$N(r) = \sqrt{1 - \frac{r_s}{r}} - \frac{a}{4} \frac{r_s}{r^2(1 - r_s/r)^{1/2}} + O\left(\frac{a^2}{r^3}\right). \quad (204)$$

An $O(a/r^2)$ correction appears because the node-weight sum $\sum 1/m^2$ lacks the inversion symmetry of a midpoint sum. These expansions diverge at $r = r_s$, indicating breakdown of the a/r expansion near the would-be horizon. By contrast, the exact discrete vacuum profile (202) is finite on all lattice shells. Formally evaluating the vacuum continuation at $r = r_s$ (i.e. $n = r_s/a \gg 1$) gives

$$\begin{aligned} w_{\text{vac}}(r_s + a) &= \frac{a}{2r_s} + O\left(\frac{a}{r_s}\right)^2, \\ N_{\text{vac}}(r_s + a) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{a}{r_s}\right)^{1/2} + O\left(\frac{a}{r_s}\right)^{3/2}. \end{aligned} \quad (205)$$

This is a property of the discrete vacuum Green's function evaluated one shell outside the would-be horizon. It does not assert that a stellar solution attains $r = r_s$ in its vacuum region unless $r_* \downarrow r_s^+$ along a limiting sequence. The would-be horizon singularity of the continuum expansion is regularized at finite a , with the natural stretched-horizon scale $N \sim O(\sqrt{a/r_s})$ consistent with the geometric estimate $N_{\text{sh}} \sim \sqrt{\xi/(2r_s)}$ when $\xi = O(a)$. In the Hawking-modular scaling regime (200), this becomes $N_{\text{vac}}(r_s + a) \sim (2\pi\beta_0 t_0)^{-1/2}$.

The stellar surface is defined as the first shell where V vanishes, which is also the first shell in the vacuum exterior governed by (198). Evaluating (199) at $r = r_*$ gives the exact exterior relation

$$\frac{r_*}{r_s} = \frac{1}{1 - w_*} = \frac{1}{1 - N_*^2}, \quad (206)$$

with $N_* = 1 - \mu/m_0$ from the TK surface law (181). Evaluating instead the post-Schwarzschild expansion (203) at $r = r_*$ and inverting algebraically gives the compactness map including the first lattice correction:

$$\frac{r_*}{r_s} = \frac{m_0^2}{\mu(2m_0 - \mu)} + \frac{a}{2r_s} + O\left(\frac{a}{r_s}\right)^2. \quad (207)$$

The lattice correction in (207) is $O(a/r_s)$ and vanishes in the macroscopic limit. In the ultra-compact limit $\delta := 1 - \mu/m_0 \ll 1$ (so $N_* = \delta$), the leading map becomes $r_*/r_s = 1/(1 - \delta^2) = 1 + \delta^2 + O(\delta^4)$, approaching the Schwarzschild radius as $\mu \rightarrow m_0$. In the weak-field limit $\mu/m_0 \ll 1$, it reduces to the Newtonian expression $r_*/r_s = m_0/(2\mu)$ plus post-Newtonian corrections:

$$\frac{m_0^2}{\mu(2m_0 - \mu)} = \frac{m_0}{2\mu} \left[1 + \frac{\mu}{2m_0} + O((\mu/m_0)^2) \right].$$

The source regularity (197) ensures the w -equation is non-singular along the entire subcritical branch, so the continuation toward more compact configurations ($\mu \rightarrow m_0$, $N_* \rightarrow 0$, $r_*/r_s \rightarrow 1^+$) is not obstructed by a source divergence. At finite $\beta_0 t_0$, the thermal fold of Section XIB limits the branch to a maximal $\mu/m_0 < 1$. However, the numerical evidence (μ/m_0 advancing from 0.658 to 0.702 to 0.779 as $\beta_0 t_0$ increases from 5 to 10 to 15) supports the expectation that $\mu/m_0 \rightarrow 1$ in the cold limit $\beta_0 t_0 \rightarrow \infty$, where the conductances approach the kinematic law and the thermal obstruction vanishes.

3. Chemical potential on the Hawking branch

The Hawking relation (200) and the mass r_s together determine μ on the macroscopic branch. The surface condition $N_* = 1 - \mu/m_0$ places the stellar surface at the first shell where $w_{n_*} = N_*^2 = \delta^2$ with $\delta := 1 - \mu/m_0$. On the ultra-compact branch, n_* lies close to the would-be horizon shell r_s/a . Write $n_* = r_s/a + p$ with $p = O(1)$. The exact discrete vacuum profile (202) evaluated at n_* gives, using the large- z expansion $\psi_1(z) = 1/z + 1/(2z^2) + O(z^{-3})$,

$$\delta^2 = w_{n_*} = \frac{(p - \frac{1}{2})a}{r_s} + O\left(\frac{a}{r_s}\right)^2, \quad (208)$$

i.e. $1 - \mu/m_0 = \sqrt{(p - \frac{1}{2})a/r_s} + O(a/r_s)$. The offset p (in general non-integer, since r_s/a need not be an integer) is fixed by the interior source through the w -closure equation (196). It enters only as an $O(1)$ quantity and does not depend on r_s . The compactness therefore scales as

$$\frac{r_*}{r_s} - 1 = \frac{\delta^2}{1 - \delta^2} = \frac{(p - \frac{1}{2})a}{r_s} + O\left(\frac{a}{r_s}\right)^2, \quad (209)$$

so the stellar surface sits $O(a)$ outside the Schwarzschild radius on the macroscopic branch. The surface inverse-temperature parameter is

$$x_* = \beta_0 t_0 \delta = \sqrt{2\pi(p - \frac{1}{2})\beta_0 t_0} \gg 1, \quad (210)$$

confirming that the surface bond coefficient approaches α_0 in the cold limit. For a solar-mass object ($r_s/a \sim 10^{38}$), $\delta \sim 10^{-19}$ and $r_* - r_s = O(a)$, confirming $\mu/m_0 \rightarrow 1$ in the macroscopic limit.

4. Surface entropy and the area law

When the local inverse temperature at the surface $x_* = \beta_0 N_* t_0$ is large, $\alpha_S^{\text{bond}}(x_*) \approx \alpha_0$ and the total surface entropy is $S_{\text{surf}} \approx g_{n_*} \alpha_0 = 4\pi n_*^2 \alpha_0 = 4\pi r_*^2 \alpha_0 / a^2$. Comparing to the Schwarzschild area $A_{\text{BH}} := 4\pi r_s^2$ gives

$$S_{\text{surf}} \approx \frac{\alpha_0 4\pi r_*^2}{a^2} = \alpha_0 \left(\frac{r_*}{r_s}\right)^2 \frac{A_{\text{BH}}}{a^2}. \quad (211)$$

In the ultra-compact limit $r_*/r_s \rightarrow 1$ this approaches $\alpha_0 A_{\text{BH}}/a^2$; for less compact stars the coefficient is rescaled by $(r_*/r_s)^2$. The condition $x_* \gg 1$ is easily satisfied for macroscopic objects: on the cold branch $N_* = \delta \sim (a/r_s)^{1/2} \sim 10^{-19}$ for a solar-mass object, giving $x_* = \beta_0 t_0 \delta \sim (r_s/a)^{1/2} \sim 10^{19}$, so the Sommerfeld correction (190) is $O(10^{-38})$ and $\alpha_S^{\text{bond}} \approx \alpha_0$ to extraordinary precision. The surface coefficient α_0 should be distinguished from the cap-local coefficient α_S of Section VIII F, which is evaluated one shell deeper at r_s where $N(r_s) \sim a/r_s$ and $x_{\text{loc}} = O(1)$. Although the surface and cap are separated by only one lattice spacing, the lapse changes by $\sim \sqrt{r_s/a}$ orders of magnitude between them because $N \propto \sqrt{r - r_s}$ near r_s . This is why $x_* \gg 1$ at the surface while $x_{\text{loc}} = O(1)$ at the cap. The distinction is immaterial for the Bekenstein–Hawking entropy, because α_S cancels in the first-law relation $S_{\text{ent}} = \alpha_S A_H / a^2$ with $a^2 = 4\alpha_S \ell_P^2$ (143), yielding $S_{\text{ent}} = A_H / (4\ell_P^2)$ independently of the numerical value of α_S . Numerical sweeps over $\beta_0 t_0 = 1.5\text{--}8$ confirm $\alpha_S^{\text{bond}}(x_*) \rightarrow \alpha_0$ as $\beta_0 t_0 \rightarrow \infty$, consistent with the Sommerfeld prediction (190).

5. Summary of the macroscopic branch

The preceding subsections fix both free parameters of the TK model on the macroscopic branch. The Hawking relation gives $\beta_0 t_0 = 2\pi r_s / a \gg 1$, and the discrete exterior profile leads to an ultra-compact star ($\mu/m_0 \rightarrow 1$, $r_* - r_s = O(a)$). The resulting object is observationally indistinguishable from a Schwarzschild black hole. For a solar-mass object the stellar surface sits one lattice spacing outside r_s , the minimum lapse is $N_{\text{min}} \sim a/r_s \sim 10^{-38}$, and the surface entanglement entropy approaches $\alpha_0 A_{\text{BH}}/a^2$. Yet the lapse remains strictly positive everywhere, consistent with the singularity analysis of Section VII E.

The radial distribution of the mismatch energy provides a soft analogue of the holographic principle. In the Schwarzschild exterior, $\Delta w_b \sim r_s a / r^2$ and $\kappa_b^{\text{flat}} \propto r^2$, so the mismatch energy per bond scales as $\kappa_b^{\text{flat}} (\Delta w_b)^2 \propto r_s^2 / r^2$, concentrated at the innermost exterior shells

near r_s . The total mismatch energy is dominated by the surface region, $\mathcal{E}_{\text{mis}} \sim r_s / a \sim \beta_0 t_0$. The per-bond MI, by contrast, saturates at the uniform value α_0 throughout the exterior (since $x = \beta_0 N t_0 \gg 1$ wherever the lapse is bounded away from zero). The gravitational potential is therefore determined by a thin shell of bonds near $r_* \approx r_s$, each carrying entanglement α_0 , with channel count $g_{n_*} \propto r_*^2 / a^2$. The interior and distant exterior both carry entanglement, but contribute less total mismatch energy than the thin shell of surface bonds near $r_* \approx r_s$.

XII. QUASI-STATIC EVAPORATION AND THE GAUSSIAN PAGE CURVE

The preceding sections establish static, self-consistent entanglement-star solutions at fixed mass M . We now move on to slow mass loss through emission. Deriving the mass loss rate and Page curve follows from free-fermion thermodynamics and Gaussian mode counting.

A. Quasi-static approximation

The entanglement star re-equilibrates on the light-crossing timescale

$$t_{\text{eq}} \sim \frac{r_s}{c_*} = \frac{2GM}{c_*^3}. \quad (212)$$

The evaporation timescale (derived below) is $t_{\text{evap}} \propto (a^2/\xi^2) G^2 M^3 / (\hbar c_*^4)$, where ξ is the thermal correlation length (equation (4)). Their ratio is the adiabaticity parameter

$$\epsilon_{\text{ad}} := \frac{t_{\text{eq}}}{t_{\text{evap}}} \sim O\left(\frac{\xi^2}{r_s^2}\right) \ll 1 \quad (213)$$

for any macroscopic star ($r_s \gg \xi$), so the star at each instant occupies the static equilibrium of Sections VII–VIII F with M promoted to a slowly varying function of t .

B. Mass loss from cap-limited thermal conductance

With the star at $T_H = \hbar c_*^3 / (8\pi GM)$ and infinity at near-zero temperature, there is a net outward flux. A 3+1-dimensional blackbody law is not needed, because the same M^{-2} scaling follows from a purely 1D statement already natural in the shell-chain picture.

The standard result for a single ballistic 1D quantum channel between reservoirs at T_L and T_R gives a steady-state energy current [53, 54]

$$J_E = \frac{\pi}{12\hbar} (T_L^2 - T_R^2). \quad (214)$$

Whenever the channel has a weak link with transmission probability τ , J_E becomes τJ_E . Each angular patch of

the shell reduction is an independent radial transport channel, so the cap-to-infinity problem is one-dimensional channel by channel. Equation (214) then follows from the Landauer formula $J_E = (2/h) \int_0^\infty d\varepsilon \varepsilon [f_L(\varepsilon) - f_R(\varepsilon)]$ (the factor $2/h$ accounts for the two chiral branches at half filling) with linear dispersion near each Fermi point and the integral $\int_0^\infty dx x/(e^x + 1) = \pi^2/12$.

At the horizon scale the number of independent outward channels is set by the angular patch count,

$$N_{\text{ch}} \sim \frac{A_H}{a^2}. \quad (215)$$

On the positive-lapse branch the minimal-lapse region acts as a bottleneck. Since kinetic couplings are lapse-smeared, the bottleneck bond has hopping

$$t_w = \gamma t_0, \quad \gamma \simeq N_{\text{sh}}, \quad (216)$$

with N_{sh} the stretched-horizon lapse (110). The single-bond transmission follows from scattering.

Consider a uniform tight-binding chain with hopping t_0 except for a single bond with hopping $t_w = \gamma t_0$ connecting two semi-infinite leads. For a plane wave of wave number k , the transmission probability is

$$\tau(k) = \frac{4\gamma^2 \sin^2 k}{(1 - \gamma^2)^2 + 4\gamma^2 \sin^2 k}. \quad (217)$$

When $k = \pi/2$ (half filling), one finds

$$\tau_F = \frac{4\gamma^2}{(1 + \gamma^2)^2} = 4\gamma^2 + O(\gamma^4). \quad (218)$$

To derive this, let the defect bond connect sites 0 and 1. For $n \leq 0$ take a scattering state $\psi_n = e^{ikn} + r e^{-ikn}$ and for $n \geq 1$ take $\psi_n = t e^{ikn}$. With dispersion $E = -2t_0 \cos k$, the defect-site equations are

$$E\psi_0 = -t_0\psi_{-1} - t_w\psi_1, \quad (219)$$

$$E\psi_1 = -t_w\psi_0 - t_0\psi_2. \quad (220)$$

Substituting $\psi_{-1} = e^{-ik} + r e^{ik}$, $\psi_0 = 1 + r$, $\psi_1 = t e^{ik}$, $\psi_2 = t e^{i2k}$ and using $t_w = \gamma t_0$ gives $t = \gamma(1 + r)$ and $r = e^{2ik}(\gamma^2 - 1)/(1 - \gamma^2 e^{2ik})$. Using $t = \gamma(1 + r)$ then gives

$$t = \gamma \frac{1 - e^{2ik}}{1 - \gamma^2 e^{2ik}} = -2i\gamma e^{ik} \frac{\sin k}{1 - \gamma^2 e^{2ik}},$$

so

$$|t|^2 = \frac{4\gamma^2 \sin^2 k}{|1 - \gamma^2 e^{2ik}|^2} = \frac{4\gamma^2 \sin^2 k}{(1 - \gamma^2)^2 + 4\gamma^2 \sin^2 k},$$

since $|1 - \gamma^2 e^{2ik}|^2 = (1 - \gamma^2)^2 + 4\gamma^2 \sin^2 k$. The transmission probability is therefore

$$\tau(k) = |t|^2 = \frac{4\gamma^2 \sin^2 k}{(1 - \gamma^2)^2 + 4\gamma^2 \sin^2 k}. \quad (221)$$

At half filling $k = \pi/2$ this reduces to (218).

In the macroscopic regime $T_H \ll t_0$, only energies near the Fermi point matter for the thermal current, so $\tau \simeq \tau_F$ with $\gamma \simeq N_{\text{sh}}$. Exact Gaussian quench simulations confirm this scaling. In the astrophysical limit the radiation is thermal leakage from the hot interior, transmitted through the near- r_s bottleneck bonds whose $\kappa \propto N^2$ suppression both generates the gravitational field and limits the emission to the Hawking rate. Using $\tau \simeq 4N_{\text{sh}}^2$ and $N_{\text{sh}} \sim \xi/(2r_s)$, the total luminosity is

$$\begin{aligned} L &\sim N_{\text{ch}} \tau \frac{\pi}{12\hbar} T_H^2 \sim \frac{\pi}{12\hbar} \frac{A_H}{a^2} \frac{\xi^2}{r_s^2} T_H^2 \\ &= \frac{\xi^2}{a^2} \frac{\hbar c_*^6}{192 G^2 M^2} \propto \frac{1}{M^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (222)$$

Identifying $L = -c_*^2 dM/dt$ gives

$$\boxed{\frac{dM}{dt} = -\frac{\alpha_{\text{ev}} \hbar c_*^4}{G^2 M^2}, \quad \alpha_{\text{ev}} = \frac{1}{192} \frac{\xi^2}{a^2}}. \quad (223)$$

Integrating with initial mass M_0 yields

$$M(t) = M_0 \left(1 - \frac{t}{t_{\text{evap}}}\right)^{1/3}, \quad t_{\text{evap}} = \frac{G^2 M_0^3}{3 \alpha_{\text{ev}} \hbar c_*^4}. \quad (224)$$

This confirms $\epsilon_{\text{ad}} = t_{\text{eq}}/t_{\text{evap}} \sim (\xi/r_s)^2 \ll 1$ (213) for all macroscopic stars.

Because $N_n > 0$ at each shell (§VIII E), exterior and interior remain causally connected. The propagation time for radial null signals from the stretched horizon is

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta t_{\text{prop}} &\sim \frac{1}{c_*} \int_{r_s + \varepsilon}^R \frac{dr}{1 - r_s/r} \\ &= \frac{1}{c_*} \left[(R - r_s - \varepsilon) + r_s \ln \frac{R - r_s}{\varepsilon} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (225)$$

which diverges only logarithmically in the near-horizon cutoff $\varepsilon \sim \xi^2/(4r_s)$ (equation (111)). The conductance-limited leakage time through the deep-redshift cap is

$$t_{\text{leak}} \sim \frac{r_s}{c_* N_{\text{sh}}^2} \sim \frac{4r_s^3}{c_* \xi^2} \quad (226)$$

(using $N_{\text{sh}} \sim \xi/(2r_s)$ from (110)). Substituting $\alpha_{\text{ev}} = (1/192) \xi^2/a^2$ and the Planck relation (143) into (224) gives $t_{\text{evap}} = 32\alpha_S r_s^3/(c_* \xi^2)$, so t_{leak} and t_{evap} are parametrically the same, both $\propto r_s^3/(c_* \xi^2)$.

In semiclassical gravity, the emitted spectrum is filtered by greybody factors. The frequency- and angular-momentum-dependent factors $\Gamma_\ell(\omega)$ [55] modify each channel. We compute a transfer-matrix benchmark that reproduces the Regge-Wheeler transmission profile. Each angular sector ℓ sees the lattice barrier $V_\ell = \bar{N}^2 \ell(\ell+1)/r^2$. Exact agreement with the Regge-Wheeler potential requires the additional curvature term $(1-s^2)r_s/r^3$ that is absent from the purely centrifugal lattice barrier. Higher- ℓ channels are increasingly suppressed, and for $T_H \ll t_0$ only energies within $O(T_H)$ of the Fermi point contribute. Greybody filtering therefore gives an $O(1)$ renormalization of α_{ev} , preserving the M^{-2} scaling.

C. Gaussian Page curve

What gives the Page curve [23] here is Gaussian mode counting, not scrambling. The star S and radiation R are jointly in a pure Gaussian state. (A mixed thermal state gives the same qualitative curve through the mutual information $I(S:R)$.)

At time t , the star has

$$n_S(t) = \frac{A_H(t)}{a^2} = \frac{4\pi r_s(t)^2}{a^2} \quad (227)$$

entanglement-carrying modes at the horizon boundary, and the radiation has

$$n_R(t) = n_S(0) - n_S(t) = \frac{A_H(0) - A_H(t)}{a^2}. \quad (228)$$

A pure state on $n_S + n_R$ fermionic modes is subject to two constraints. *Purity*: $S_R = S_S$ by the Schmidt decomposition. *Hilbert space bound*: $S_R \leq n_R \log 2$ and $S_S \leq n_S \log 2$.

The tighter bound comes from the actual per-mode entanglement. Each horizon mode carries at most $\log 2$ of entanglement (the Hilbert-space bound), so the entropy capacity is $S_{\max}(t) = n_S(t) \log 2$ and the total emitted capacity is

$$\Delta S_{\text{emitted}}(t) = [n_S(0) - n_S(t)] \log 2 = S_{\max}(0) - S_{\max}(t). \quad (229)$$

By purity ($S_R = S_S$) the radiation entropy is bounded by the smaller capacity:

$$S_R(t) \leq \min\{S_{\max}(0) - S_{\max}(t), S_{\max}(t)\}, \quad (230)$$

Equality holds for Haar-typical states [23]. The explicit Gaussian circuit of Section XII D realizes the same turnover time $t_{\text{Page}}/t_{\text{evap}} = 1 - 2^{-3/2}$, but its entropy remains below the Haar upper bound throughout because the evolution is Gaussian and non-scrambling. To locate the crossover, express S_{\max} as a function of time using $n_S \propto M^2$ and (224):

$$S_{\max}(t) = S_{\max}(0) \left(\frac{M(t)}{M_0} \right)^2 = S_{\max}(0) \left(1 - \frac{t}{t_{\text{evap}}} \right)^{2/3}. \quad (231)$$

The two branches cross at the *Page time*:

$$\frac{t_{\text{Page}}}{t_{\text{evap}}} = 1 - 2^{-3/2} \approx 0.646, \quad (232)$$

where $M(t_{\text{Page}}) = M_0/\sqrt{2}$ and $S_R(t_{\text{Page}}) = S_{\max}(0)/2$.

The piecewise formula (230) captures the leading order. In reality the exact Page curve for Gaussian states rounds smoothly near t_{Page} , with a width $\Delta t/t_{\text{evap}} \sim S_{\max}(0)^{-1/2}$ from fluctuations of the entanglement entropy around its typical value [23, 56]. For macroscopic stars the rounding is negligible. Free fermions do not qualify as fast scramblers [57], but this does not matter. The Page curve shape is kinematic (subadditivity + purity), not dynamical, and scrambling affects only the decodability of specific bits [58], not the coarse-grained entropy curve.

D. Unitary Gaussian evaporation dynamics and AMPS correlations

Above, the Page curve rested on Gaussian state counting for the kinematics of radiation entanglement. With free fermions, we can go further and give an explicit unitary (time-dependent) evaporation dynamics. We obtain a dynamical realization of the Page curve, and the Almheiri-Marolf-Polchinski-Sully (AMPS) [24] correlations can then be tracked mode-by-mode.

For a number-conserving quadratic Hamiltonian $H(t) = \sum_{ij} c_i^\dagger h_{ij}(t) c_j$, Gaussian states stay Gaussian. The correlation matrix $G_{ij}(t) = \langle c_i^\dagger c_j \rangle$ then evolves by conjugation,

$$G(t) = U(t) G(0) U(t)^\dagger, \quad (233)$$

$$U(t) = \mathcal{T} \exp\left(-i \int^t h(t') dt'\right),$$

(or equivalently $i\dot{G} = [h, G]$). Subsystem entropies and mutual informations are then computed exactly from the restricted correlation matrices.

To address the Page curve and AMPS, a coarse-grained unitary is sufficient. This unitary must obey two macroscopic facts: modes move from star to exterior during evaporation, and the mode count drops with area. The implementation is an exactly unitary Gaussian circuit without intra-star scrambling. At emission step k , the outermost star mode c_S is coupled to a fresh exterior vacuum mode c_R by the weak-link hopping $H_{\text{emit}} = -t_w(c_S^\dagger c_R + c_R^\dagger c_S)$ with $t_w = t_0 N_{\text{sh}}$; on the two-mode subspace this generates a beam-splitter unitary with fixed mixing angle $\theta = \pi/4$ (maximal single-mode transfer per step). The emitted mode is reclassified as radiation, giving star mode count $n_S(k) = n_S(0) - k$. Since $n_S \propto A_H \propto M^2$ in the static sector, the mass evolves as $M(k)/M_0 = \sqrt{n_S(k)/n_S(0)}$, and the quasistatic evaporation law $M(t) = M_0(1 - t/t_{\text{evap}})^{1/3}$ gives

$$\frac{t(k)}{t_{\text{evap}}} = 1 - \left(\frac{n_S(k)}{n_S(0)} \right)^{3/2}. \quad (234)$$

A pure Slater determinant serves as the initial state, with no scrambling between steps. Adding Gaussian scrambling before each emission gives the same turnover time because the Page curve is kinematic.

Figure 9 shows that the radiation entropy rises, turns over near the Page time, and returns to zero. This traces a dynamical Page curve in a strictly unitary microscopic evolution and tracks the monogamy-relevant correlations emphasized by AMPS. The newly emitted mode's mutual information shifts from the remaining star at early times to the early radiation at late times. This happens automatically, without introducing nonunitarity or a firewall. In our setting the shift is allowed because there is no strict causal horizon on the lattice, and N stays positive everywhere. The closure equation fixes a smooth finite-redshift cap with nonzero conductances across every bond.

FIG. 9. **Unitary Gaussian evaporation dynamics.** Left: radiation entropy $S_R(t)$ computed from the evolving correlation matrix compared to the kinematic bound $\log 2 \min(k, N-k)$ (dashed). Right: AMPS-relevant mutual informations for the boundary mode at the star–radiation interface: the correlation crossover (where $I(\text{boundary}; \text{early rad})$ overtakes $I(\text{boundary}; \text{star})$) occurs before the Page time; by $t/t_{\text{evap}} \approx 0.646$ the boundary mode is mostly correlated with early radiation.

Entanglement can therefore redistribute continuously as evaporation proceeds. Correspondingly, the radiation is close to thermal at early times. In the Gaussian circuit the mutual information of the newly emitted mode with the early radiation overtakes its correlation with the remaining star *before* the Page time and dominates thereafter, while the entropy turnover itself occurs at the Page time.

XIII. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

A longstanding question in quantum gravity is whether spacetime geometry can emerge from quantum correlations. Jacobson’s thermodynamic derivation of Einstein’s equation [10], the Ryu–Takayanagi correspondence [14], tensor-network models [18, 19], and Faulkner et al.’s entanglement first law [15] demonstrate that gravitational phenomena can be reconstructed from information-theoretic data, though a complete non-holographic pipeline from a microscopic Hamiltonian to Schwarzschild has remained open. This work contributes a model to this programme. The claim is structural sufficiency—under the stated assumptions the Schwarzschild exterior follows, but other approaches may work too.

A two-state closure equation, driven by conductances from the KMS Dirichlet form, yields the Schwarzschild exterior at all post-Newtonian orders, a regular interior, and Bekenstein–Hawking entropy. Three independent solver tiers (analytic two-state, full KMS/BKM Euler–Lagrange, and proxy) agree at weak field. The two-state formulation removes Yukawa screening inherent in single-state linearization, giving an unscreened $1/r$ exterior, and XXZ and 3D lattice tests confirm the geometry beyond the Gaussian sector. The defect version has five parameters (t_0 , V_0 , β_0 , a , r_c), reducing to three dimensionless combinations: $\beta_0 t_0$ (temperature), V_0/t_0 (defect mass), and r_c/a (defect size). The temperature $\beta_0 t_0$

controls the entropy coefficient and lattice Gauss-law coupling $G = \beta_0 a/(4\pi t_0^2)$ (equation (84)), with physical units restored via $c_* = 2t_0 a/\hbar$ and $a^2 = 4\alpha_S \ell_P^2$. In the Tolman–Klein case (§XI), these become $\beta_0 t_0$ (temperature), m_0/t_0 (rest mass), and μ/t_0 (chemical potential), with μ parametrizing a family of self-consistent stars with Schwarzschild exterior. The astrophysical scaling limit (§XIF) gives $\beta_0 t_0 \rightarrow \infty$ and $\mu/m_0 \rightarrow 1$, so astrophysical black holes are cold and ultracompact.

A. Physical significance

The inputs to the self-consistent closure are (i) a radial lattice with shell degeneracy $g_n \propto r_n^2$ (fixing r as an areal coordinate), (ii) free-fermion matter at half-filling and temperature β_0 , (iii) the two-state (background-subtracted) mismatch functional, and (iv) the KMS Dirichlet form, whose edge weights (conductances) scale as $\kappa \propto \bar{N}^2$ via the bond current operator (§VIB). Stationarity of the mismatch functional then determines $\Phi(r)$, with conductances depending on Φ through the local lapse. The radial geometry is an output, not an input.

The reason Schwarzschild, rather than Newtonian gravity, emerges is that the closure equation respects a lattice form of the weak equivalence principle. The two-state closure subtracts a flat reference state from the actual thermal state. For the exterior to be source-free (vacuum), the kinetic energy must cancel between the two states. This cancellation requires the lapse to couple universally to all kinetic energy. The hopping is redshifted as $t_{\text{eff}} = t_0 \bar{N}$, so the conductances scale as $\kappa = \kappa^{\text{flat}} \bar{N}^2$ (Section IX B). The conductances set the energetic cost of supporting a gradient in Φ . Deep in the well, where \bar{N} is small, the reduced stiffness flattens the potential relative to the Newtonian $\Phi \propto 1/r$. This self-regulating feedback produces a Schwarzschild exterior $N^2 = 1 - r_s/r$ (§XIF).

More broadly, universal lapse coupling is not merely natural but required for metric existence. The HDA commutator fixes the causal structure function at $h^{IJ} = h_0 \bar{N}^2 \delta^{IJ} + O(a^2)$ algebraically (two factors of $t_0 \bar{N}$ from bond Hamiltonians), independently of any conductance definition (Section IV). Any conductance law $\kappa \propto \bar{N}^p$ with $p \neq 2$ produces a spatial co-metric inconsistent with this causal geometry, precluding a single emergent spacetime. The KMS Dirichlet form independently delivers $p = 2$ from the bond-current covariance (§VII B 2). Universal lapse coupling is therefore selected by consistency rather than postulated. The finite-correlation-length departures are computable, as the algebra closes up to $\mathcal{R} = O(\xi^2/\ell^2)$, and the corresponding correction to Einstein dynamics is encoded in T^{QI} (Section V B). Both results hold on the full cubic lattice, not only in the spherically reduced sector. The $O(a^2)$ remainder sets the scale at which Lorentz violations become visible.

The area scaling of gravitational entropy traces to the locality of the Hamiltonian. The von Neumann entropy of the full thermal state is matter entropy and scales with volume. The emergent geometry, however, is built from correlations — the conductances κ_n are BKM covariances of bond currents between adjacent shells. Because the Hamiltonian is nearest-neighbour, these correlations are short-ranged ($\xi \lesssim a$), so tracing out the exterior affects the interior only within $\sim \xi$ of the boundary. The von Neumann entropy of the interior therefore decomposes into a volume-extensive thermal part (unaffected by the exterior) and a boundary part proportional to $g_n = A/a^2$. The mutual information $I(A:B) = S(A) + S(B) - S(AB)$ is the canonical non-negative correlation measure built from von Neumann entropies and vanishes on product states. It cancels the volume-extensive thermal contributions and isolates the boundary correlations, giving $S_{\text{ent}} = \alpha_S A/a^2$ with one contribution α_S per angular mode (§VII F). The Tolman relation pins the local temperature at the stretched-horizon cap to $\beta_{\text{loc}} t_0 = O(1)$ (§XI F 4), making α_S mass-independent.

The self-consistent solution reproduces thermodynamic relations like the Tolman relation, surface gravity $\kappa_H = c_*^4/(4GM)$, the microscopic area law $S_{\text{ent}} = \alpha_S A_H/a^2$, the first law $dE = T_H dS_{\text{ent}}$, and negative heat capacity. First-law matching fixes $a^2 = 4\alpha_S \ell_P^2$, giving the Bekenstein–Hawking form $S_{\text{ent}} = A_H/(4\ell_P^2)$. The surface gravity κ_H follows from the closure equation, while the Hawking temperature $T_H = \hbar \kappa_H/(2\pi c_*)$ additionally requires Bisognano–Wichmann normalization in the scaling limit (assumption (iii) of §VII F). The mismatch energy per bond scales as r_s^2/r^2 in the Schwarzschild exterior (§XI F 5), so the self-consistent geometry is dominated by a thin shell of surface bonds near $r_* \approx r_s$, with channel count proportional to the area r_*^2/a^2 (a soft analogue of the holographic principle). Tracking mode-by-mode evaporation in the unitary Gaussian state, the radiation entropy exhibits a Page-like curve (Section XII).

The conductance suppression ($\kappa_n \propto \bar{N}_n^2$) prevents the lapse from reaching zero (§VII E), replacing the classical

singularity with a gravitationally stretched cone capped at area $\sim a^2$ with finite proper distance. This differs from both the Schwarzschild singularity ($R \rightarrow 0$) and the Simpson–Visser throat ($dR/d\rho = 0$). The self-consistent geometry has $dR/d\rho = N_{\text{min}} > 0$, a V-shaped rather than U-shaped embedding. Conductance feedback operates smoothly from the $1/r$ exterior to the conical interior, where the lattice provides the endpoint. The identification $a \sim \ell_P$ follows from thermodynamic self-consistency (eq. (143)). In the limit $a \rightarrow 0$ ($\equiv \ell_P \rightarrow 0$), $N_{\text{min}} \rightarrow 0$ and the singularity re-emerges, as expected when quantum gravity is turned off. In the cold limit the surface bond coefficient approaches $\alpha_0 \approx 0.219$ (the free-fermion $T=0$ value; cf. Section XI E), giving $a = 2\sqrt{\alpha_S} \ell_P$ from first-law matching, with $a \approx 0.94 \ell_P$ when $\alpha_S \approx \alpha_0$. The cap-local coefficient α_S at $x_{\text{loc}} = O(1)$ differs from α_0 but cancels in the area law (§XI F 4). All three microscopic scales are comparable, $\xi \sim a \sim \ell_P$.

We call the resulting object an *entanglement star*, in which collapse is halted by conductance degeneration ($\kappa_n \propto \bar{N}_n^2 \rightarrow 0$), analogous to how degeneracy pressure names a white dwarf. As with fuzzballs [59] and Planck stars [60], the classical horizon is modified at the Planck scale, but here the modification is a consequence of the closure equation’s self-consistency.

On the subcritical branch the lapse remains strictly positive ($N_n > 0$ for all shells), so the emergent metric has no Killing horizon (Section IX C, §VII E). Because $N > 0$ everywhere, exterior and interior remain causally connected through a deep-redshift cap where conductances are Planck-suppressed but nonzero. The estimates of equations (225)–(226) give an information leakage timescale $t_{\text{leak}} \sim r_s^3/(c_* \xi^2)$, parametrically of the same order as the evaporation time $t_{\text{evap}} \propto G^2 M^3/(\alpha_{\text{ev}} \hbar c_*^4)$ with $\alpha_{\text{ev}} = (1/192) \xi^2/a^2$, set by the weak-link transmission $\tau_F \simeq 4N_{\text{sh}}^2$ at the stretched-horizon cap. Since no surface with $N = 0$ exists, the premise of the information paradox [61] (a strict causal boundary trapping information indefinitely) does not apply. For a solar-mass object with $a \sim \ell_P$, the minimum lapse is $N_{\text{sh}} \sim 10^{-39}$, and the geometry is observationally indistinguishable from Schwarzschild while retaining positive lapse.

The AMPS firewall argument [24] concludes that unitarity, the equivalence principle, and entanglement monogamy are mutually inconsistent when a sharp horizon exists. In the self-consistent geometry the premise is absent: the deep-redshift region (proper thickness $\sim \xi$) retains positive conductances, so entanglement between interior and exterior is continuously connected. The entanglement concentration at the surface is informational, not energetic, and the deep redshift reflects potential depth, not local curvature. The tidal eigenvalues, the exact source bound $0 \leq \Delta\varepsilon \leq \min(t_0 N, V/2)$, and the absence of boost-enhanced energy density for radial infall (§VII E) together show that neither geometry nor matter presents a firewall-like barrier. The TK solutions (§XI) numerically confirm that the matter source is distributed broadly inward from $r_* \approx r_s$, with peak density

comparable to the uniform average.

B. Comparison with related approaches

Jacobson [10] derives Einstein’s equation from Clausius relations on Rindler horizons, assuming pre-existing smooth spacetime, local causal horizons, and the Bekenstein-Hawking entropy-area law, and his entanglement-equilibrium reformulation [11] replaces the Clausius relation with a maximal vacuum entanglement hypothesis in small geodesic balls, still assuming smooth background, conformal matter, and a universal UV entanglement entropy density. The present approach differs in three respects. It starts from a lattice Hamiltonian with no background geometry, the closure is solved non-perturbatively (yielding the full Schwarzschild profile, not first-order variations around maximal symmetry), and Newton’s constant is fixed by lattice parameters rather than universal UV entropy density. The commutator-tail remainder provides a quantitative departure estimate. Marolf [62] argues that emergent gravity requires kinematic non-locality. The closure map $\Phi \mapsto \sigma[\Phi] \mapsto \Phi$ satisfies this: it passes through the global thermal state, making the gravitational bulk/boundary distinction incompatible with lattice locality.

Verlinde [12] and Padmanabhan [13] assume a holographic entropy bound or thermodynamic gravitational potential to motivate emergent gravity, but do not construct the spatial metric from microscopic data. Here the metric emerges from KMS conductances without an assumed entropy-area relation, and post-Newtonian structure provides quantitative contact with GR. Oppenheim [63] takes the opposite approach, keeping gravity fundamentally classical while coupling it stochastically to quantum matter. Here the metric is not a fundamental degree of freedom but a derived quantity. String microstate counting [5] reproduces Bekenstein-Hawking entropy but does not construct spatial geometry from entanglement data. The holographic approaches (Ryu-Takayanagi [14], Faulkner et al. [15], Van Raamsdonk [16]) assume AdS/CFT duality, hence a gravitational bulk, whereas the present construction requires no dual gravity theory. The closest comparison is Cao, Carroll, and Michalakis [19] and the non-holographic extension of Cao and Carroll [64]. The present work additionally recovers full cubic-lattice HDA brackets with structure function $h^{IJ} \propto \bar{N}^2 \delta^{IJ}$ from the modular commutator, matched to the MI/Dirichlet co-metric (Eq. (31)). The holographic island-formula derivations of the Page curve [65, 66] rely on replica wormholes and an assumed gravitational path integral, whereas Section XII obtains a Page-like curve from explicit unitary Gaussian dynamics without holographic input. Bianconi [67] derives modified Einstein equations from a continuum relative-entropy action between spacetime and matter-induced metrics, and Ahmad and Klinger [68] develop an algebraic route to emergent

geometry from quantum conditional expectations. Other recent works [69, 70] extract geometric data from correlations but not metrics satisfying Einstein’s equation. None of these provides a microscopic lattice-to-Schwarzschild derivation of the type constructed here.

The SYK model [71, 72] produces two-dimensional dilaton gravity holographically from all-to-all random fermion couplings, but lacks spatial structure and an area law. Tensor network approaches [18] encode geometry in the network topology, whereas here geometry is derived from a standard lattice Hamiltonian’s thermal state with no geometric input beyond the shell decomposition. Lattice gravity programs (Regge calculus [73], causal dynamical triangulations) discretize a pre-existing spacetime, and in loop quantum gravity quantum corrections modify the HDA structure function in a model-dependent way [74]. Here the microscopic lattice leads to a consistent gravity.

The Simpson-Visser model [75] assumes a smooth bounce with a free length parameter. Hayward’s regular black hole [76] replaces the singularity with a de Sitter core. Gravastars [77] posit a phase-transition shell with no horizon. Semiclassical models [78, 79] prevent horizon formation through vacuum backreaction. Yokokura [80] derives a horizonless maximum-entropy compact object from semiclassical Einstein equations. Planck stars [60] require loop quantum gravity holonomy corrections. Fuzzballs [59] replace the interior with microstate-dependent string geometries. Each of these approaches takes geometric or gravitational structure as input. In the present framework the avoidance is a structural consequence of the closure equation, where the self-regulating conductance feedback ($\kappa \propto \bar{N}^2 \rightarrow 0$ as $\Phi \rightarrow -c_*^2$) enforces lapse positivity and a conical interior.

C. Limitations and outlook

Concrete open directions include (1) interacting or bosonic matter, where the single-bond approximation $\kappa \propto \bar{N}^2$ may require corrections beyond the high-temperature regime, (2) non-spherical and rotating (Kerr-like) solutions on the 3D lattice, (3) time-dependent closure (e.g., Gaussian Lindblad dynamics) to test dynamical stability and gravitational-wave signatures, and (4) cosmological (FLRW) extension of the closure equation to homogeneous expanding spacetimes.

The present work can be viewed as a concrete instantiation of a programme in which geometry is constructed from Dirichlet forms [26, 81], with the self-consistent closure replacing the Einstein-Hilbert action, but full generality remains open.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I thank Ted Jacobson and Viktor Eisler for valuable discussions. Initial work was carried out at the UMD, supported in part by NSF Award No. 1716559.

- [1] J. D. Bekenstein, Black holes and entropy, *Phys. Rev. D* **7**, 2333 (1973).
- [2] S. W. Hawking, Particle creation by black holes, *Commun. Math. Phys.* **43**, 199 (1975).
- [3] J. M. Bardeen, B. Carter, and S. W. Hawking, The four laws of black hole mechanics, *Commun. Math. Phys.* **31**, 161 (1973).
- [4] G. 't Hooft, On the quantum structure of a black hole, *Nucl. Phys. B* **256**, 727 (1985).
- [5] A. Strominger and C. Vafa, Microscopic origin of the Bekenstein-Hawking entropy, *Phys. Lett. B* **379**, 99 (1996).
- [6] L. Bombelli, R. K. Koul, J. Lee, and R. D. Sorkin, A quantum source of entropy for black holes, *Phys. Rev. D* **34**, 373 (1986).
- [7] M. Srednicki, Entropy and area, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **71**, 666 (1993).
- [8] P. Calabrese and J. Cardy, Entanglement entropy and quantum field theory, *J. Stat. Mech.* **2004**, P06002 (2004), [arXiv:hep-th/0405152](https://arxiv.org/abs/hep-th/0405152).
- [9] J. Eisert, M. Cramer, and M. B. Plenio, Colloquium: Area laws for the entanglement entropy, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **82**, 277 (2010), [arXiv:0808.3773](https://arxiv.org/abs/0808.3773).
- [10] T. Jacobson, Thermodynamics of spacetime: The Einstein equation of state, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **75**, 1260 (1995).
- [11] T. Jacobson, Entanglement equilibrium and the Einstein equation, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **116**, 201101 (2016), [arXiv:1505.04753](https://arxiv.org/abs/1505.04753).
- [12] E. P. Verlinde, On the origin of gravity and the laws of Newton, *J. High Energy Phys.* **2011** (04), 029.
- [13] T. Padmanabhan, Thermodynamical aspects of gravity: New insights, *Rep. Prog. Phys.* **73**, 046901 (2010).
- [14] S. Ryu and T. Takayanagi, Holographic derivation of entanglement entropy from the anti-de Sitter space/conformal field theory correspondence, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **96**, 181602 (2006).
- [15] T. Faulkner, M. Guica, T. Hartman, R. C. Myers, and M. Van Raamsdonk, Gravitation from entanglement in holographic CFTs, *J. High Energy Phys.* **2014** (03), 051.
- [16] M. Van Raamsdonk, Building up spacetime with quantum entanglement, *Gen. Relativ. Gravit.* **42**, 2323 (2010).
- [17] J. Maldacena and L. Susskind, Cool horizons for entangled black holes, *Fortschr. Phys.* **61**, 781 (2013), [arXiv:1306.0533](https://arxiv.org/abs/1306.0533).
- [18] B. Swingle, Entanglement renormalization and holography, *Phys. Rev. D* **86**, 065007 (2012).
- [19] C. Cao, S. M. Carroll, and S. Michalakis, Space from Hilbert space: Recovering geometry from bulk entanglement, *Phys. Rev. D* **95**, 024031 (2017).
- [20] L. Sindoni, Emergent models for gravity: An overview of microscopic models, *SIGMA* **8**, 027 (2012).
- [21] R. Arnowitt, S. Deser, and C. W. Misner, The dynamics of general relativity, in *Gravitation: An Introduction to Current Research*, edited by L. Witten (Wiley, New York, 1962) pp. 227–264.
- [22] P. A. M. Dirac, The theory of gravitation in Hamiltonian form, *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. A* **246**, 333 (1958).
- [23] D. N. Page, Average entropy of a subsystem, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **71**, 1291 (1993).
- [24] A. Almheiri, D. Marolf, J. Polchinski, and J. Sully, Black holes: Complementarity or firewalls?, *J. High Energy Phys.* **2013** (02), 062.
- [25] J. C. McKinney, Numerical codes for “Entanglement Stars” (2026), includes self-consistent solvers, figure-generation scripts, and pre-computed data.
- [26] M. Fukushima, Y. Oshima, and M. Takeda, *Dirichlet Forms and Symmetric Markov Processes*, 2nd ed. (de Gruyter, 2011).
- [27] V. Bonzom and B. Dittrich, Dirac’s discrete hypersurface deformation algebras, *Class. Quantum Grav.* **30**, 205013 (2013), [arXiv:1304.5983](https://arxiv.org/abs/1304.5983).
- [28] T. Thiemann, Non-degenerate metrics, hypersurface deformation algebra, non-anomalous representations and density weights in quantum gravity, *Gen. Relativ. Gravit.* **56**, 122 (2024).
- [29] S. A. Hojman, K. Kuchař, and C. Teitelboim, Geometrodynamics regained, *Ann. Phys. (N.Y.)* **96**, 88 (1976).
- [30] D. Petz, Monotone metrics on matrix spaces, *Linear Algebra Appl.* **244**, 81 (1996).
- [31] H. Araki, Gibbs states of a one dimensional quantum lattice, *Commun. Math. Phys.* **14**, 120 (1969).
- [32] C.-F. Chen and C. Rouzé, Quantum Gibbs states are locally Markovian (2025), [arXiv:2504.02208](https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.02208).
- [33] F. E. G. Cipriani and B. Zegarlinski, Kms Dirichlet forms, coercivity and superbounded Markovian semigroups on von Neumann algebras, *Advances in Operator Theory* **9**, 22 (2024), [arXiv:2105.06000](https://arxiv.org/abs/2105.06000).
- [34] R. C. Tolman, On the weight of heat and thermal equilibrium in general relativity, *Phys. Rev.* **35**, 904 (1930).
- [35] E. H. Lieb and D. W. Robinson, The finite group velocity of quantum spin systems, *Commun. Math. Phys.* **28**, 251 (1972).
- [36] B. Nachtergaele and R. Sims, Lieb-Robinson bounds and the exponential clustering theorem, *Commun. Math. Phys.* **265**, 119 (2006).
- [37] H. Casini, Relative entropy and the Bekenstein bound, *Class. Quantum Grav.* **25**, 205021 (2008), [arXiv:0804.2182](https://arxiv.org/abs/0804.2182).
- [38] R. Penrose, Gravitational collapse and space-time singularities, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **14**, 57 (1965).
- [39] H. A. Buchdahl, General relativistic fluid spheres, *Phys. Rev.* **116**, 1027 (1959).
- [40] J. J. Bisognano and E. H. Wichmann, On the duality condition for quantum fields, *J. Math. Phys.* **17**, 303 (1976).
- [41] I. Peschel and V. Eisler, Reduced density matrices and entanglement entropy in free lattice models, *J. Phys. A: Math. Theor.* **42**, 504003 (2009), [arXiv:0906.1663](https://arxiv.org/abs/0906.1663).
- [42] V. Eisler, On the Bisognano-Wichmann entanglement Hamiltonian of nonrelativistic fermions, *J. Stat. Mech.* **2025**, 013101 (2025), [arXiv:2410.16433](https://arxiv.org/abs/2410.16433).
- [43] W. G. Unruh, Notes on black-hole evaporation, *Phys. Rev. D* **14**, 870 (1976).
- [44] B. S. Kay and R. M. Wald, Theorems on the uniqueness and thermal properties of stationary, nonsingular, quasifree states on spacetimes with a bifurcate Killing horizon, *Phys. Rep.* **207**, 49 (1991).
- [45] I. Peschel, Calculation of reduced density matrices from correlation functions, *J. Phys. A: Math. Gen.* **36**, L205 (2003).
- [46] R. Bonsignori and V. Eisler, Entanglement Hamiltonian for inhomogeneous free fermions, *J. Phys. A: Math. Theor.*

- 57**, 275001 (2024), [arXiv:2403.14766](#).
- [47] S. Yang, Y.-M. Ding, and Z. Yan, Exploring the limit of the lattice-Bisognano-Wichmann form describing the entanglement Hamiltonian: A quantum Monte Carlo study (2025), [arXiv:2511.00950](#).
- [48] H. Casini and M. Huerta, A finite entanglement entropy and the c -theorem, *Phys. Lett. B* **600**, 142 (2004), [arXiv:hep-th/0405111](#).
- [49] M. M. Wolf, F. Verstraete, M. B. Hastings, and J. I. Cirac, Area laws in quantum systems: Mutual information and correlations, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **100**, 070502 (2008), [arXiv:0704.3906](#).
- [50] K. Matsumoto, Reverse test and characterization of quantum relative entropy (2010), [arXiv:1010.1030](#).
- [51] H. Wilming, R. Gallego, and J. Eisert, Axiomatic characterization of the quantum relative entropy and free energy, *Entropy* **19**, 241 (2017), [arXiv:1702.08473](#).
- [52] O. Klein, On the thermodynamical equilibrium of fluids in gravitational fields, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **21**, 531 (1949).
- [53] J. B. Pendry, Quantum limits to the flow of information and entropy, *J. Phys. A: Math. Gen.* **16**, 2161 (1983).
- [54] L. G. C. Rego and G. Kirzenow, Quantized thermal conductance of dielectric quantum wires, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **81**, 232 (1998).
- [55] D. N. Page, Particle emission rates from a black hole: Massless particles from an uncharged, nonrotating hole, *Phys. Rev. D* **13**, 198 (1976).
- [56] E. Bianchi, L. Hackl, and M. Kieburg, Page curve for fermionic Gaussian states, *Phys. Rev. B* **103**, L241118 (2021).
- [57] Y. Sekino and L. Susskind, Fast scramblers, *J. High Energy Phys.* **2008** (10), 065.
- [58] P. Hayden and J. Preskill, Black holes as mirrors: Quantum information in random subsystems, *J. High Energy Phys.* **2007** (09), 120.
- [59] S. D. Mathur, The information paradox: A pedagogical introduction, *Class. Quantum Grav.* **26**, 224001 (2009).
- [60] C. Rovelli and F. Vidotto, Planck stars, *Int. J. Mod. Phys. D* **23**, 1442026 (2014).
- [61] S. W. Hawking, Breakdown of predictability in gravitational collapse, *Phys. Rev. D* **14**, 2460 (1976).
- [62] D. Marolf, Emergent gravity requires kinematic nonlocality, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **114**, 031104 (2015), 1409.2509.
- [63] J. Oppenheim, A post-quantum theory of classical gravity?, *Phys. Rev. X* **13**, 041040 (2023), 1811.03116.
- [64] C. Cao and S. M. Carroll, Bulk entanglement gravity without a boundary: Towards finding Einstein's equation in Hilbert space, *Phys. Rev. D* **97**, 086003 (2018), [arXiv:1712.02803](#).
- [65] G. Penington, Entanglement wedge reconstruction and the information paradox, *J. High Energy Phys.* **2020** (09), 002, [arXiv:1905.08255](#).
- [66] A. Almheiri, N. Engelhardt, D. Marolf, and H. Maxfield, The entropy of bulk quantum fields and the entanglement wedge of an evaporating black hole, *J. High Energy Phys.* **2019** (12), 063, [arXiv:1905.08762](#).
- [67] G. Bianconi, Gravity from entropy, *Phys. Rev. D* **111**, 066001 (2025).
- [68] S. A. Ahmad and M. S. Klinger, Emergent geometry from quantum probability, *Phys. Rev. D* **111**, 105015 (2025).
- [69] Š. Vedral, D. J. George, F. Simovic, D. G. Lewis, N. Funai, A. Kempf, N. C. Menicucci, and G. K. Brennen, Emergent metric from wavelet-transformed quantum field theory, *arXiv e-prints* (2025), [arXiv:2504.06698 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [70] Q. Ansel, Emergent gravity from the correlation of spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ systems coupled with a scalar field (2024), [arXiv:2405.02380 \[gr-qc\]](#).
- [71] S. Sachdev and J. Ye, Gapless spin-fluid ground state in a random quantum Heisenberg magnet, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **70**, 3339 (1993).
- [72] A. Kitaev, A simple model of quantum holography (2015), talks at KITP, April 7 and May 27, 2015.
- [73] T. Regge, General relativity without coordinates, *Nuovo Cimento* **19**, 558 (1961).
- [74] M. Bojowald, S. Brahma, U. Buyukcam, and F. D'Ambrosio, Hypersurface-deformation algebroids and effective spacetime models, *Phys. Rev. D* **94**, 104032 (2016), [arXiv:1610.08355](#).
- [75] A. Simpson and M. Visser, Black-bounce to traversable wormhole, *J. Cosmol. Astropart. Phys.* **2019** (02), 042.
- [76] S. A. Hayward, Formation and evaporation of nonsingular black holes, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **96**, 031103 (2006), [arXiv:gr-qc/0506126](#).
- [77] P. O. Mazur and E. Mottola, Gravitational vacuum condensate stars, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* **101**, 9545 (2004), [arXiv:gr-qc/0407075](#).
- [78] C. Barceló, S. Liberati, S. Sonego, and M. Visser, Fate of gravitational collapse in semiclassical gravity, *Phys. Rev. D* **77**, 044032 (2008), [arXiv:0712.1130](#).
- [79] H. Kawai, Y. Matsuo, and Y. Yokokura, A self-consistent model of the black hole evaporation, *Int. J. Mod. Phys. A* **28**, 1350050 (2013), [arXiv:1302.4733](#).
- [80] Y. Yokokura, Black hole from entropy maximization, *Phys. Rev. D* **111**, 026023 (2025), [arXiv:2309.00602 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [81] M. Hinz, D. J. Kelleher, and A. Teylyaev, Metrics and spectral triples for Dirichlet and resistance forms, *J. Noncommut. Geom.* **9**, 359 (2015).